

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

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Report on recommendations on Community Resilience and Recovery Models

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BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
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EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
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ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UCL	University College London	UK
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NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
<i>ABM</i>	Agent Based Model
<i>AHP</i>	Analytical Hierarchy Process
<i>ANP</i>	Analytical Network Process
<i>BN</i>	Bayesian Networks
<i>BOCR</i>	Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, Risks
<i>BOTG</i>	Behaviour Over Time Graph
<i>CIS</i>	Critical Infrastructure System
<i>CICS</i>	Critical Infrastructure-Community System
<i>CLD</i>	Causal Loop Diagram
<i>DPM</i>	Damage Probabilty Matrix
<i>DSS</i>	Decision Support Systems
<i>ETAS</i>	Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences
<i>EIL</i>	Earthquake Induced Liquefaction
<i>EPSS</i>	Electric Power Supply System
<i>FL</i>	Functionality Loss
<i>FR</i>	Functional Recovery
<i>FWCR</i>	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response
<i>GFL</i>	Gross Functionality Losses

<i>GMPEs</i>	Ground Motion Prediction Equations
<i>HABM</i>	Hierarchical Agent-Based Model
<i>IAoE</i>	Immediate Aftermath of Earthquake
<i>MLS</i>	Minimum Link Set
<i>OEF</i>	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
<i>PSHA</i>	Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis
<i>RN</i>	Road Network
<i>RR</i>	Rapid Response
<i>RRE</i>	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
<i>SD</i>	System Dynamics
<i>SDA</i>	System Dynamic Assessment
<i>SFD</i>	Stock and Flow Diagram
<i>SISZ</i>	South Iceland Seismic Zone
<i>TB</i>	Test Beds
<i>UNDRR</i>	United Nation Disaster Risk Reduction
<i>WCDR</i>	World Conference on Disaster Reduction

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Concept

Complex systems formed by communities and the Critical Infrastructure Systems (*CISs*) that support their modus operandi (Alesch 2005), thereby defined as Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems (*CICSSs*) are characterised by the continued inflow/outflow of goods and services underpinned by *CISs* that have been cybernetically engineered and networked, to ensure the best, or at least, adequate performances (Kröger and Zio 2011), to maintain and sustain the communities' socio-economic order.

Such order however, can be substantially disrupted by external events, such as the ones caused by natural hazards, and research has shown that the greater the complexity of the system of systems, the less controllable are the cascading effects and repercussions of any such disruptive event. Indeed, due to the ever-increasing degree of intra- and interdependences, seemingly insignificant local damage incurred by *CISs* can potentially propagate, and lead to full-blown cascade of failures (Buldyrev et al. 2010, Brummitt et al. 2012, Bashan et al. 2013). More crucially, the losses of *CICSSs* accumulated throughout the recovery process from disruptive events also tend to be severe, largely due to their interdependences, as well as the absence of expeditious and well-planned responses (Helbing 2013).

Against this backdrop, considerable research has been undertaken to explore viable pathways towards the resilience of *CICSSs* under a variety of disruptions. In 2005, community resilience was highlighted in the World Conference on Disaster Reduction (*WCDR*) and proposed as the new blueprint for the sustainability and security of *CICSSs* (International Strategy for Disaster Reduction 2005). More recently, Cutter (2013) highlighted the significance of identifying “building resilience” to disasters as the roadmap to sustainability. Moreover, from the political point of view, the path to disaster resilience necessitates the collective efforts of all societal sectors.

In relation to seismic hazard, Bruneau et al. (2003) proposed a broad definition of disaster resilience of *CICSSs* to cover all actions that reduce losses from hazardous events, including the effects of mitigation and efficient recovery. In this study seismic resilience of *CICSSs* is characterised as “the ability of social units (e.g. organizations, communities) to mitigate hazards, contain the effects of disasters when they occur, and carry out recovery activities in ways to minimize social disruption and mitigate the effect of future earthquakes”. They also suggested that resilience could be conceptualized along four dimensions: technical, organizational, societal and economic. The technical and economic dimension are related more directly to the resilience of *CISs*, while the other two dimensions, organizational and social, are more related to the resilience of the community.

The **Task 5.2** objective is the development of an adaptive and inclusive modelling framework for the rapid response-based recovery and resilience of *CICSSs* exposed to seismic hazards.

By Rapid Response (*RR*), within the *TURNkey* project, it is intended, the collective sum of actions that authorities in charge of disaster management need to deploy, rapidly and efficiently, in the immediate aftermath of the main shock, on the basis of a partial, qualitative and emotionally-biased knowledge of the rapidly evolving situation in the field. *RR* relies heavily on the near-real-

time estimates of the earthquake location and characteristics (e.g. magnitude), and the knowledge of the exposed assets and their vulnerabilities, to estimate the potential losses and the areas most affected by the event.

Therefore, of particular relevance to the applicability of the modelling framework developed within Task 5.2, is the time dependent status of the *CISs* considered and the time dependent quality and quantity of information relating to such status, which is usually increasing and changing in nature as time from the disruptive event elapses, but can also be affected by secondary events as time progresses, overlapping the immediate response and recovery phases. Such a framework will enable relevant stakeholders to identify specific risks of interest, and formulate relevant coordinated demands for preparedness and response actions. To that end, prioritization criteria will be developed to link the contingency simulations on the vulnerability, resilience and adaptive capacity of the individual *CIS* and the whole *CICS*, throughout seismic events. As an endeavour to deliver a holistic examination on those rapid response actions, a medium-term resilience and recovery model will be developed to gauge the improvement to *CICSs*, in terms of their robustness and resilience, in the wake of strong earthquakes. In addition, regarding the estimation of the time that a *CICS* needs to be restored to a particular functionality level after seismic events, an agent-based model (*ABM*) is established, whereby the time-dependent functionality can be tracked throughout seismic events, as well as the potential aftershock sequences. The conceptual framework proposed in this document will be applied to a number of *TBs* to determine limitations and constraint in real cases and needs for refinement of both the general methodology and the tools and models developed. This will serve to identify suitable procedure to upload on the TURNkey *DSS* platform.

1.2 Research Significance

The ever-increasing interdependence among *CISs*, and the penetration of artificial intelligence (*AI*) into many aspects of their operations have contributed to the increased performance of those physical systems (Duan et al., 2020; Esztergár-Kiss et al., 2020). Concurrently, such a tendency has also paved the way for the damage and/or disfunction at the local scale, to cascade and lead to connected systems' shutdown, even within a short course ensuing disruptive events (Helbing, 2013; Schneider et al., 2013).

Within TURNkey, Deliverable 5.2 sets out to produce a toolkit of modular routines and procedures, which can be linked and included in the TURNkey's Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response Platform (FWCR), to determine the resilience of integrated community and critical infrastructure systems during the immediate aftermath of an event, to produce appropriate and robust rapid response. Through the application of these models to the selected Test Beds, the objective is to identify the potential technical as well as sociological and socioeconomic barriers (financial, human, organisational and governance) to the use in practice of the TURNkey platform.

In this respect D5.2 fulfils specifically the TURNkey objective PO5: *Development of protocols for response, emergency management, and safety communication, including uncertainties, for technical stakeholders, nontechnical stakeholders, and the public.* Based on the decisional rules

forming the Decision Support Systems (*DSSs*), the models and methods outlined in this deliverable will be further customised and applied in task 5.4 with the overall joint goals of providing 1) rapid information to emergency decision-makers about the availability/unavailability of strategic critical infrastructure and possible consequences of evacuations and 2) rapid information to rescuers about available road network connections and need for emergency repairs. The focus on community resilience will allow to provide guidelines on protocols which are particularly effective to improve the short-term resilience of organisations, critical infrastructure providers and service providers to communities. Outcomes of the application of these resources to selected Test Beds will support the implementation of the *DSSs*.

1.3 Scope

The first submission of this deliverable includes the methodologies and conceptual modelling, for both critical infrastructure resilience and community resilience. A second submission on month 24 will include description of applications to the selected Test Beds and critical assessment of the performance of the toolkit.

The present document is articulated in nine chapters. This chapter gives an overview on the research background and the significance associated with the planned research in *Task 5.2*. Chapter 2 reviews the state of the art studies on the development of seismic resilience of modern *CISs* subject to strong earthquakes, as well as the modelling frameworks for seismic resilience developed to date. The unique role that transport networks and specifically the Road Networks (*RNs*) play in terms of seismic resilience of modern communities, is discussed and highlighted. In addition, the knowledge gap regarding systemic assessment and improvement of community resilience is reviewed and viable approaches to integrate community and critical infrastructure resilience measures for rapid response are proposed. Chapter 3 develops a conceptual modelling framework on the seismic resilience of the interdependent *CISs* throughout seismic events. Such a framework lays the foundation for the development of the optimally-planned rapid response, which will serve as viable and effective pathway to improve the seismic resilience of *CISs* in the immediate aftermath of disruptive events. Chapter 4 presents a Hierarchical Agent-Based Model (*HABM*) to look into the seismic resilience of *RNs*, whereby the impact of functional losses and contextual damage on the resilience of *RNs* is examined. It is proposed to apply the model to two different road networks Test Beds and the data needs are identified. Accordingly, the needs for societal post-shock rapid response are proposed as drivers to identify appropriate and optimal strategies for the post-shock recovery of *RNs* in the Immediate Aftermath of Earthquakes (*IAoEs*) and so as to ameliorate their seismic resilience thereof. This is illustrated through the interaction between hospital systems and road network.

Chapter 5 explores the models suitable for simulating rapid response considering interaction or dependency between infrastructure systems and the resulting cascading effects, with particular reference to port infrastructure. Chapter 6 looks into the decision-making regarding post-shock rapid response and recovery on *CISs*, under incomplete information that is common throughout seismic events. This shows how, by marrying *Bayesian Networks (BN)* analysis with the *HABM*, a compositional *Bayesian-HABM* framework is put forward to shed light on the stochastic resilience of

CISs subject to seismic hazards. Chapter 7 examines the adaptive decision-making on the post-shock and seismic resilience of *CISs*, incorporating the effect of the potential aftershock sequences. Such an impact can be integrated into the *Bayesian-HABM* framework developed in Chapter 6.

Chapter 8 develops the conceptual modelling framework to evaluate the benefits that the implementation and use of TURNkey's FWCR platform may deliver to private organisation and businesses, infrastructure providers and communities. This is achieved using two different approaches, the Analytical Hierarchy Process and the System Dynamics Assessment. The first will identify barriers and opportunities to improve rapid response resilience, the second will determine specific mechanisms that can be implemented at community level for rapid response of *CICSSs* under seismic hazards.

Chapter 9 draws the most significant conclusions, based on the review and proposed modelling applications. This chapter will be reviewed and consolidated in the second issue of the *Deliverable*.

2 STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Development of seismic resilience of modern CICSs

Catastrophic earthquake hazards have long since been imperilling civilized community in earthquake-prone regions, around the globe. Statistical studies have demonstrated that the resulting death toll and property loss of those communities, where the seismic disaster befalls, tend to be devastating (Nichols and Rodgers 2017).

2.1.1 Emergence of the concept of seismic resilience

Against this backdrop, considerable research focus has gravitated towards the resilience of communities and their CICSs, as it has become evident that the sound and quick recovery in the post-disaster stage is at least as critical as the disaster robustness to the disaster survival and continued post-disaster development of CICSs.

Conceptually, Norris et al. (2008) provide a definition of community resilience as the process involving a set of adaptive capacities to return to the required functionality after the shocks. Community resilience would be contingent upon four primary sets of adaptive capacities---Economic Development, Social Capital, Information and Communication, and Community Competence---that together serve as the pillars for disaster preparedness.

More recently, seismic disasters such as the *2011 Tohoku Earthquake*, have re-emphasized the need for the earthquake engineering profession and the public policy makers to develop viable measures to improve the seismic resilience of modern CICSs.

In 2014, Ayyub revisited the concept of disaster resilience and suggested it shall be gauged by the community's capacity to meet a set of requirements with clear relationships to the metrics of the relevant abstract notions of reliability and risk (Ayyub, 2014). Furthermore, it is argued that improvement of the resilience of CICSs to meet target levels requires the examination of the system enhancement alternatives in economic terms, following a decision-making framework, which often requires the examination of resilience based on its valuation from societal perspective. To that end, a method for the valuation and benefit-cost analysis based on concepts from risk analysis and management, is proposed.

With reference to the resilience and recovery of a community, individual buildings, whether residential or commercial, cannot function as a facility if the infrastructure services, such as water, electricity, telecommunications, and road access are not functioning. Therefore, a recovery process for buildings must include the full restoration of infrastructure services. CICSs repairs can be needed either at the building itself and therefore the responsibility of the owner, or elsewhere and hence the responsibility of the service provider. The Earthquake Engineering Research Institute published a white paper (EERI, 2019) that introduces a new term, *functional recovery*, linking building repair and infrastructure service repair. Functional recovery is defined as the second key milestone in the post-earthquake timeline. Therefore, for a building's recovery two stages can be identified:

- *reoccupancy*, i.e. the ability to re-enter, take shelter, and begin the recovery phase safely.
- followed by *functional recovery*, marking the restoration of building services as needed to support a significant measure of the building's intended pre-earthquake use.

Similarly, for infrastructure systems in this project we define *functional recovery (FR)* as the restoration of the system's ability to deliver the services needed to allow users to resume most of their pre-earthquake activities.

2.1.2 Quantification framework of seismic resilience of CICSs

In line with the framework established by Bruneau et al. (2003), Ouyang et al. (2012) put forward a model for the assessment of the functionality loss of the affected CICSs throughout seismic events. As shown in Figure 1, in such a model, the gross functionality loss is employed as a direct measure of seismic resilience (more accurately, loss of resilience) of a CICS. In particular, the period after an earthquake event is divided into three phases, namely, the absorption, the recovery and the post-shock phase.

Figure 1 Seismic resilience quantification model (adapted from Ouyang et al. 2012), where f_0 indicates the functionality in the pre-shock condition and in the post-shock condition at 100% recovery, and $f(t)$ is the variation of functionality with time during the absorption and recovery phases.

In principle, after the shock, the CICS deliverable functionality (capacity supply) may take some time to reach a minimum. This time identifies the end of the absorption phase. From then on, the CICS will start to restore its functionality, until it stabilizes at a new, recovered, post-shock level. The scale of duration of the absorption and recovery phases can be quite different (hours vs. days), especially after calamitous seismic events (Ge et al., 2010; Iuchi et al. 2013), where the recovery may take years. Based on the functionality status tracked in time during both the absorption and recovery phases, the Gross Functionality Losses (GFL) can be quantified as the shaded area illustrated in Figure 1. Mathematically, this is formalised in Eq. 1, where f_0 and $f(t)$ refer to the pre-shock functionality level of CICSs and their time-dependent functionality throughout the absorption and the recovery phases, respectively.

$$GFL = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} (f_0 - f(t)) dt \quad (1)$$

It should be noted that such a framework might be a viable modelling tool, for standalone CICSs. Nevertheless, it falls short of the applicability on real-world CICS or networked CICSs. First, such a framework assumes that the demand for the function of the CICS (from the community it serves) remain constant throughout the entire seismic event and during the recovery period, which cannot hold true in many cases. Second, the functionality of the CICSs and the urban community that they serve may

not necessarily be the same in the post-shock phase, as those before the seismic events. For example, the functionality level of an “adaptive” *CIS* can be higher after the shock, compared to the pre-shock one (Linkov et al. 2014). In this case, the shaded area in Figure 1 is not well defined, suggesting that there is a net functionality gain, which would be misleading for risk analysis and the corresponding decision-making. On the other hand, in case of a “ductile” system, whose functionality never restored to the pre-shock level, *Eq. 1* would result in an infinite functionality loss, which is also uninformative.

To remedy the deficiencies above, a novel compositional resilience quantification framework simultaneously tracking the service supply from *CISs* and the demand for service from the served community throughout the post-shock recovery period, is proposed by Sun et al. (2015). For most of the cases, the difference between the supply and demand for the service provided by the *CISs* is stable under normal operation conditions. However, as elaborated herein, during and after strong earthquakes, such a balance would be disrupted and needs to be rebuilt via a sustainable restoration, and then stabilized at some particular level. In such framework, the supply and demand should be separately tracked throughout their own “absorption” and “recovery” phases, respectively. Similar to the functionality supplies from any individual *CIS*, the corresponding demand from the affected community will also decrease ensuing a mainshock, as many of the users, e.g. residential buildings, schools as well as the industrial plants are physically damaged or shut down. Moreover, other *CISs* are also likely to have been affected by the shocks. As a consequence, livelihood and business activities of the community would be significantly disrupted, to the point that some inhabitants may be temporarily displaced. Therefore, a considerable fraction of the pre-shock demand will be expected to be lost in the absorption phase.

The restoration of the supply and demand can be achieved at different paces, in the recovery phase. Overall, the demand restoration rate tends to be lower than that of the supply, and could be faster should more resources be allocated to restart the livelihood of the community. In addition, the business activities cannot be restored until all the *CISs* and the basic public services have been substantially recovered.

Figure 2 The resilience behaviours of “Deliverable Functionality” and “Demand” (adapted from Sun et al. 2015)

With reference to Figure 2, similar to *Eq. 1*, the *CISs*’ functionality loss (*FL*) can be tracked and used to measure seismic resilience of the integrated *CICCS* throughout earthquake events. At the system level, such a loss will be quantified by the sum of the functionality deficit, denoted as $FD_k(t)$,

at each node k ($k = 1: N$, where N is the number of nodes of one particular *CIS*) that is obtained by aggregating the gap between the deliverable functionality (denoted as $DF_k(T)$) and the corresponding functionality demand (denoted as $D_k(t)$) during both the absorption and recovery phases.

$$FL(T) = \sum_{k=1}^N FD_k(T) \quad (2)$$

$$FD_k(T) = \sum_{l=1}^m \int_{t_{l,0}}^{t_{l,f}} (D_k(t) - DF_k(t)) dt \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), m is the total number of intervals until time point T , where $D_k(t)$ is larger than $DF_k(t)$, throughout the entire seismic event. Correspondingly, $t_{l,0}$ and $t_{l,f}$ refer to the start and the end points of each such intervals, respectively. For each node k , $D_k(t)$ will be obtained by the functionality demand from all the user across all the neighbourhoods served by it.

In 2015, Mieler et al. proposed a performance-based engineering framework to assess and ameliorate the seismic resilience of urban communities under earthquake hazards. In particular, the regulatory framework of nuclear power plant systems was adapted to a community setting. Consistent performance targets associated with the set of different subsystems as well as the community components can thereby be determined following the global resilience objective set on the community level (Mieler et al. 2015).

It is noteworthy to emphasize that, resilience of *CISs* lies not only in their capacity to restore the functionality to the pre-hazard level, but also the “antifragility” whereby they can potentially reach a higher functionality level, after the post-hazard restoration. This is common in real *CISs*, as component of an existing infrastructure system which have failed during an event will be generally reinstated and retrofitted to comply with new performance standards, which are normally higher than the ones for which the system was originally designed. As an endeavour to explore a pathway towards the antifragility, Fang and Sansavini (2017) developed an optimization-based model on the post-hazard restoration planning of *CISs*, considering the combined construction of new components and the repair on failed ones. The expected costs of repairing all the damaged components will therefore serve as the benchmark, and the ultimate goal of the model is to determine the optimal target system structure so that the performance after restoration can be maximized. The developed model was applied on a real-world 380-kV power transmission grid in Northern Italy, and the corresponding simulation results revealed that the antifragility behaviour of the network can be delivered indeed, with restoration investment that is significantly lower than the “benchmark” cost.

2.2 Vulnerability of transportation networks to seismological hazards from field evidence

Modern road networks are underpinning the well-being of urban *CICCSs*, which they are part of. In particular, their resilience is strategically crucial to the post-shock recovery and resilience of the integrated *CICCSs*, subject to seismic hazards. Nevertheless, as demonstrated by several real-world seismic events, road networks have turned out to be vulnerable and thereby significant damage can be induced.

During *May 12, 2008 Wenchuan Earthquake* in China, both the highway and railway bridge structures were seriously decimated by the main shock (Zhao and Taucer 2010) and by landslides and

mudslides triggered by the combined effect of shaking and oversaturated soil. Such physical damage, along with the damage of the other *CISs*, like power networks, led to significant functionality losses of the transportation network for a long-lasting period. In turn, it shall be noted that the resulting dysfunction of road network had a significant knock-on effect on the post-shock recovery, and thus caused a large number of fatalities (Yang et al. 2014).

During the 2010 Maule earthquake in Chile, although most of the *CISs* were shown to be relatively robust, damage to road, railway, and port networks still caused significant access problems in the days following the mainshock (Platt, 2019). Reconnaissance activity carried out by EEFIT (Lubkowski et al. 2011) showed that along a stretch of about 90 km on the Pan-American Highway Route 5, south direction between Santiago and Rancagua of the 16 bridges inspected, some 200 km from the epicentre, 20% were undamaged, 50% had minor damage and the rest had at least one collapsed span. Schanack et al. (2012) reports a survey of 80 bridges compiled by the Direccion de Vialidad, Chile, which identifies specific bridge typologies and corresponding damage types. According to this report of the 6,000 bridges in the affected area 30 were closed to traffic, and traffic was restricted for another 70 bridges.

Vis-à-vis the *March 11, 2011 Great East Japan Earthquake*, seismic damage to bridge structures was found to be pervasive (Kawashima and Buckle, 2013). In addition, based on the *in-situ* observation across *Ishinomaki*, a significant traffic congestion was found to be triggered immediately following the shock. Similar to the case of *Wenchuan Earthquake*, the evacuation of the wounded was then found to exasperate such a jam, which will, in turn, hinder the evacuation itself (Hara and Kuwahara, 2015).

In terms of the *April 25, 2015 Gorkha Earthquake* in Nepal, in addition the death toll of approximately 9,000, the transportation network throughout the affected area was also found to sustain a significant functionality loss, mainly due to the earthquake-induced landslides, rather than the seismic hazard itself. The resulting economic loss associated with the transportation network failure was estimated to be around USD 216 million (Shrestha et al., 2016). The livelihood of the locals was still disrupted months later, given the shortage of essential supplies, especially, the gas and petrol, due to the stagnant restoration of the transportation networks (Xie et al., 2017).

Most recently, during the, 2016 Central Italy earthquake sequence, the road network into the town of Amatrice was decimated by the seismic hazard. Due to the damage of the bridges, the North access road was closed, while the East access road was limited. Meanwhile, responsive actions were also undertaken shortly after the earthquake to maintain the functionality of these roads. In particular, owing to the collaboration between Italian Civil Protection and the Army, two temporary bridges were efficiently built. Owing to those endeavour, the emergency services and food supplies could be delivered within 72 hours of the first event (D'Ayala et al., 2019).

Seaports are critical elements of the intermodal connections of the overall transportation system within a nation or even among nations. In fact, the maritime transportation network is a key infrastructural system whose disruption may significantly affect the state of the economy, security, and the overall well-being of society. This effect has been dramatically demonstrated during historical earthquakes such as the Loma Prieta (USA, 1989), the Hyogoken-Nanbu (Japan, 1995), Tokachi-Oki

(Japan, 2003) and the more recent events of Port-au-Prince (Haiti, 2010), Maule (Chile, 2010), Tohoku (Japan, 2011) and Kaikoura (New Zealand, 2016) in which severe damage to seaport structures was caused by ground shaking, soil liquefaction, and tsunami. The recent 2016 M7.8 Kaikoura earthquake in New Zealand induced widespread manifestations of soil liquefaction and significant ground cracks at CentrePort, Wellington, which in turn damaged wharves and seaport facilities (Cubrinovski et al. 2018).

2.3 Seismic resilience of Critical Infrastructure Systems

Considerable studies have been carried out to explore the viable pathway towards the resilient *CISs* under a variety of disruptions, such as catastrophic earthquakes. Among those research endeavour, particular attention has been paid to seismic resilience of transportation systems, given their criticality, in terms of the sustainable functioning of *CICs*, as highlighted in Section 2.2.

Hu et al. (2016) examined the disaster resilience of *RNs* by focusing on their recovery ensuing earthquake hazards. The impact of different repair strategies on the resilience of *RNs* was highlighted by comparative studies. To that end, a total of three different targeted repair strategies, namely, greedy recovery (*GR*), preferential recovery based on nodal weight (*PRNW*) and periphery recovery (*PR*), were investigated. Specifically, *GR* is set to repair the damaged links in order by which the largest network functionality can be restored in every time step. By comparison, *PRNW* will preferentially repair those edges linking the isolated nodes serving the largest population to the functional component within the *RNs*. Finally, *PR* will prioritize the isolated nodes with the largest population. Random recovery (*RR*) was also considered, as the baseline strategy, but proved unable to restore the functionality of *RNs* in a satisfactory pattern. Based on the case-study results, it was found that the targeted repair strategies, especially *PRNW* and *PR*, could be way more effective. Given its computational tractability and high efficiency in terms of connecting the most populated areas, *PRNW* is suggested as a viable strategy for resource allocation to optimize the recovery process, by substantially shortening the needed time to restore *RN* functionality and reduce the associated losses, throughout earthquake events.

Gehl and D'Ayala (2018) proposed a multi-hazard risk assessment procedure for *RNs*. In such a procedure, bridge structures are decomposed in their components in order to account for the hazard-specific local damage mechanisms, which can be then linked to the existing functionality loss metrics. To that end, *Bayesian Networks (BNs)* have been employed in the developed procedure to assemble component fragility curves and generate functionality metrics at the bridge level, for a variety of combinations of hazards. This necessary change of scale between component and system levels proves to be instrumental in the refinement of the loss models, which can then be used to feed subsequent network analysis models. The various loss metrics that have been estimated (i.e. repair duration, functional loss in terms of speed reduction and lane closure) are key variables for the resilience assessment of road networks in both dimensions (i.e. magnitude and duration of the perturbation), provided that relevant traffic models and restoration strategies are applied. At the level of the road network, the functionality loss curves may be directly used to compute various system

performance indicators (e.g. connectivity loss, increased travel time, etc.), thus effectively replacing conventional fragility curves and facilitating the resilience quantification of the infrastructure system.

Kilanitis and Sextos (2019) developed a holistic framework for the multi-criterion assessment and management of the seismic risk and resilience of *RNs*. A variety of the sources of uncertainty that contribute to the overall network seismic risk, including the hazard and vulnerability, as well as the consequence estimation, are considered. Both the structural and monetary loss, along with the broader financial, connectivity and environmental impact of hazard levels with different annual rate of exceedance are all put into context and employed to gauge the seismic resilience of *RNs*. Such a framework can therefore serve as the decision-making tool for the stakeholders to come up with and examine the most cost-effective strategies to ameliorate the seismic resilience of *RNs*.

Dong and Frangopol (2017) have examined the seismic resilience of integrated healthcare-bridge network systems. In addition to the physical damage, the extra travel and waiting time are also employed as a resilience measure. Based on their study, the seismic performance of the interdependent systems will be contingent upon both of the two sub-systems. Per the outcome of the case study, bridge retrofit is found to be contributing remarkably to the improvement of seismic resilience of the integrated system, and the extra travel time of the injured can be reduced by up to 75%, owing to the retrofit.

Based on the compositional supply-demand resilience modelling framework, an agent-based model (*ABM*) was developed by Sun et al. (2019), whereby the collective influence of behavioural pattern of humans, the physical characteristics of the *CISs*, and the socio-economic context of the community, on the global resilience of *CICCS* can be examined. Such an *ABM* was then employed to examine the resilience of a virtual *CICS* under different seismic scenarios. As an application, the Electric Power Supply System (*EPSS*), the Road Network (*RN*), and the urban community served by them were included in the *CICS*. Accordingly, three principal players, the *EPSS Operator*, the *RN Operator* and the *Community Administrator* are defined as separate agents. The two *Operator* agents mobilize their resources and run the restoration on their *CISs*, whereas the *Administrator* agent is set to oversee the entire recovery campaign. Results show that the intervention of the *Administrator* agent to expedite the recovery process can be very effective. It can therefore be concluded that the interplay among different agents, as well as the interdependence between the *CISs* can profoundly affect the recovery path for the integrated *CICS*. Furthermore, the simulation also demonstrates that the sluggish restoration of *RN* could have a remarkable “bottleneck” effect on that of the other connected *CISs*, in particular, when mainshocks are not considered in isolation, but within a sequence of strong shocks occurring over relatively short periods of time (days or weeks), whereby damaged components of the road network might not have yet received repairs, or might be under repair when a second or third strong motion strikes.

2.4 Modelling critical infrastructure and community resilience from a social sciences stand point

2.4.1 Critical Infrastructure Models

Resilience is a construct that was first introduced by Holling (1973, 1996, 2001). He argued that resilience has two interconnected aspects: engineering and socio-ecological. Whereas the

former is concerned with retaining the stability of a system during and after a disaster event, the latter looks at the potential of a system to reorganise to a new state of equilibrium. Socio-ecological resilience is in essence concerned with the inherent potential (adaptive capacity) of a system to change as a result of a disaster event. Modelling resilience requires looking at both engineering and socio-ecological resilience. As such, to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR platform, a hybrid model will be developed that accounts for both aspects of resilience – as well as the interlinkages between them. A number of authors have examined the requirements of resilience frameworks and models (Sharifi, 2016; Nguyen and Akerkar, 2020; Gibson and Tarrant 2010; Lee et al. 2013; Bruneau et al. 2003; Cimellaro et al. 2010; Deyner, 2017; Cutter et al. 2008; Prior 2015; Morga et al. 2020) and whilst there is general consensus on the factors that affect resilience, there is less agreement on how to integrate these into explanatory/predictive models and practical toolkits to assess resilience to a disaster event - and in particular on how to integrate the factors into models that reflect local circumstances and context.

In the H2020 LIQUEFACT project, Morga et al. (2020) performed a detailed literature review of the factors that affect the resilience of critical infrastructure to *EIL* events. From this review Morga et al. (2020) identified a range of indicators, grouped into factors (organisation and management, technical systems, and operational delivery systems) that together constitute a complex arrangement of both hard (physical) and soft (people, economics etc.) infrastructures (see Aradau, 2010 for more details) that affect the resilience of critical infrastructure organisations to *EIL* events. In particular Morga et al. (2020) identified the need for resilience models to focus on the impact of an *EIL* event has on service delivery (to the end-user client), rather than on physical damage to physical assets, as the key criteria when evaluating the resilience of critical infrastructure.

To this end, whilst Morga et al. (2020) acknowledged the link between physical damage and service delivery, they also identified the degree to which the wider community context (described by the authors as the vagueness of system boundaries) affected the impact that a loss in service delivery had on the recovery trajectory of both the critical infrastructure organisation and wider community. To model this wider community context Morga et al. (2020) suggest that critical infrastructure resilience models needed to consider the influence of the various resilience indicators/factors across the whole life-cycle of a disaster event (preparedness, absorption, recovery, and adaptivity) and, model the complex interdependencies that exist between critical infrastructure organisations / systems (e.g. the reliance of one system on the effective functioning of another system, or on supply chain logistics within an interconnected system). Effectively, Morga et al. (2020) argue for a system of systems modelling approach that places critical infrastructure organisations within the institutional, regulatory, and economic realities of the wider system (community) that it serves. In conclusion, Morga et al. (2020) suggest the need for a hierarchical modelling approach to evaluating the resilience of critical infrastructure to *EIL* events (**Error! Reference source not found.**) mapping organisational specific metrics to key factors (organisation and management, technical systems, operational (service) delivery systems) and life cycle/governance issues.

Whilst the authors acknowledge that Morga et al.'s model is developed for a specific earthquake hazard, they believe the principles identified therein are applicable to the general earthquakes hazards being considered in the TURNkey project.

Figure 3 Hierarchy structure with cross cutting issues

2.4.2 Community Resilience Models

Nguyan and Akerkar (2020) and Sharifi (2016) critically reviewed a wide range of models used to identify and quantify community resilience to a range of hazard events. Nguyan and Akerkar (2020) conducted a detailed analysis of 77 studies, projects and tools published between 2000 and 2020 to identify alternative approaches to measuring community resilience (amongst other objectives) to hazard events at the rural, urban and community level. Nguyan and Akerkar (2020) identified modelling, measurement and visualisation as the key constituents to determine, measure and present the factors that affect community resilience. The factors were generally grouped into components, with most resilience models comprising between 3 and 7 interconnected components, with individual factors potentially influencing multiple components. From their analysis Nguyan and Akerkar (2020) identified the following community resilience characteristics:

- adaptation - the ability to adjust and update over time;
- attribute - the need to represent both internal and external entities;
- continuity - the need for inherent, dynamic and persistent characteristics;
- dependency - the need to interact and integrate with a wide range of models and frameworks;

- dynamic - the need to effectively manage resources to speed recovery;
- equity - the need to be fair and impartial to all community stakeholders;
- orientation - consistency of assumptions;
- ownership - the need for collected buy-in by stakeholders;
- rapidity - capability of a community to prepare, respond, adapt, and recover from disasters promptly;
- redundancy - the need for diversity;
- resourcefulness - the ability to mobilise;
- robustness - the capacity to withstand the impacts of disaster events;
- simplicity - the importance to translate complicated factors into simple models;
- sustainability - the need to safeguard resources for future use;
- trajectory - the need to aim for positive outcomes after a disaster event; and
- quality - the crucial services and goods needed to ensure a positive outcome.

These factors need to be considered when developing community resilience models to a greater or lesser extent. This said, Nguyen and Akerar (2020) acknowledge that not all of the characteristics will be appropriate to all communities or all hazard circumstances.

In addition to identifying the key characteristics of community resilience models, Nguyen and Akerar (2020) also examined the strengths and weaknesses of different methodological approaches to measuring the characteristics in community resilience models; identifying a range of qualitative, quantitative and hybrid approaches that could be used to aggregate the characteristics within these models. For qualitative models Nguyen and Akerar (2020) explored the anatomy of qualitative frameworks, identifying the various stages in the model development (engagement, scope, development, assessment, implementation, and monitoring) and critiqued the various methodologies that could be used to gather data at each stage in the model development. For quantitative models Nguyen and Akerar (2020) identified the basic constituents of the models that include the aggregation of indicators (measurable metrics) within components and then the aggregation of components to derive an overall community resilience score. The aggregation of indicators within components, and components within the overall community resilience score can include simple summation or the use of a weighted average, or standardised (e.g. z-scores) methodology. One further refinement identified by Nguyen and Akerar (2020) was the use of priority (importance) setting methodology such as the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in which component (and overall community resilience) scores are calculated through a combination of the criterion score (normally on an ordinal scale) and their priority/importance weights established through a pairwise comparison among stakeholders. For hybrid models Nguyen and Akerar (2020) cited the work of Cutter et al. (2008) who use a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches in the Disaster Resilience of Place model. However, Nguyen and Akerar (2020) stress the practical limitations of adopting such methods in terms of the effort and time required to develop and analyse the community resilience models.

Nguyan and Akerar (2020) also considered how the results of community resilience models could be presented to different stakeholders (visualisations). Nguyan and Akerar (2020) identified the need to use multiple visualisation techniques to understand the large amounts of information generated when preparing for and responding to the hazard events. These visualisation techniques include the use of geospatial mapping, management style charts and diagrams, and statistical graphs; brought together through a dashboard which allows the different visualisations to be viewed holistically.

In summarising their findings Nguyan and Akerar (2020) identified 3 steps for assessing community resilience to hazard events:

1. The need to identify and contextualise the components and factors that describe the hazard event and the community that is impacted by the event. In identifying the components/factors care needs to be taken to avoid (or at least be aware of, overlaps) between the components/factors; particularly when they are broken down into a hierarchy.

2. Be clear on the objectives of the resilience model; this will influence not only the type of model developed (e.g. index, scorecard etc.) but also the tools (qualitative, quantitative, or hybrid) used to collect data.

3. Clearly map the data to the goals/objectives of the resilience model and develop robust procedures for converting data into information; paying particular attention to the problems of aggregating static and dynamic information within modelling frameworks.

Sharifi (2016) also published a critical review of 36 community resilience assessment tools to identify the critical attributes that tools required to effectively measure community resilience at different physical scales (individual built assets through to national community levels) against different risk scenarios (single to multiple risks; natural to economic stressors). This categorised each tool against 15 characteristics to identify the critical characteristics for different applications. Sharifi (2016) identified the need for models to:

- be comprehensive and accommodate multiple dimensions of community resilience, including the need to group criteria (indicators/metrics) into categories/components.
- consider cross-scale relationships and in particular the need to view each community as an open system nested within a hierarchy of spatial scales.
- consider temporal issues including modelling both pre-and post-hazard scenarios.
- address uncertainties in both hazard predictions and impact thresholds.
- employ participatory approaches that engage a broader array of stakeholders in the decision-making process.
- develop action plans as a result of resilience assessments to prioritise intervention strategies and provide a roadmap for transition to a more resilient community.

Sharifi (2016) concluded that whilst these characteristics were present in some models, they were not present in all. Further, even where the characteristics were present there was a need for further

refinement of the models to accommodate dynamic temporal and geo-spatial effects and for the use of scenario-based planning to better understand and address uncertainties.

2.4.3 System Dynamics conceptual models

System Dynamics (*SD*) is a modelling approach to study systems behaviour over time. It differs from other modelling approaches with its emphasis on feedback loops, non-linearity, and time delays that influence the behaviour of the entire system (Bures, 2015). A system is seen as elements, interconnections and a function (non-human systems) or purpose (human systems), however, elements do not have to be tangible (Meadows, 2008). For example, Meadows (2008) describes a university admission process as a system, which might include school pride and academic prowess as its elements; standards for admission, requirements for degrees, examination, grades, and budget, being the interconnections and the communication of knowledge being its purpose.

System Dynamics is a methodology to understand the behaviour and dynamics of complex systems over time (Forrester, 1998; Goh and Love, 2012). Jay W. Forrester, an electrical and computer engineer at Massachusetts Institute of Technology, applied his background in computer sciences and engineering to the development of computer modelling and analysis of social systems leading to the field of system dynamics. System dynamics arose from seeking a better understanding of systems' management (Forrester, 1998). Forrester developed a structure for system dynamics using a four-tiered structural hierarchy (Richardson, 2011):

1. Closed system boundary (i.e., dynamic behaviour arises internally)
2. Feedback loops as the basic structural elements within the boundary
3. Level (state) variables representing accumulations within the feedback loops
4. Rate (flow) variables representing activity within the feedback loops.

Model conceptualization, i.e. conceptualization of a problem, is the first step when building a SD model. Conceptualization is an important activity in the development of a system dynamics model (Luna-Reyes, 2003). It is the most creative part of the modelling process requiring careful consideration. Conceptualization defines the purpose of the model, the model boundary and identifies key variables, describes the behaviour of the key variables, and presents the basic feedback loops of the system. The conceptualization includes the development of two diagrams, a Causal Loop Diagram (*CLD*) and a Stock and Flow Diagram (*SFD*).

A *CLD* in Figure 4 demonstrates a *CLD* of the basic mechanism of a company (Albin, 1997), showing key variables and their causal relationships. The (+) and (-) indicate whether any variables pairs increase or decrease (+) or move in opposite directions (-). Figure 5 shows the corresponding *SFD*, which is a prerequisite to building equations in the System Dynamics software.

Figure 4 An example of a Casual Loop Diagram: The basic mechanism of a company, i.e., influence factors on inventory and profit (Albin, 1997).

Figure 5 An example of a stock and flow diagram: The basic mechanism of a company, i.e., influence factors on inventory and profit (Albin, 1997).

System Dynamics methodology has been adapted for school children by the Water Foundation, who have produced diagrams that are useful for all ages, such as the diagram in Figure 6 (Water Foundation 2020). This highlights the need to state clearly the assumptions that underpin the model. SD models are usually developed as group work and it is vital that there is agreement in the group on the assumptions that the model is built on. Without a common agreement on the assumptions the modelling work cannot continue. Next the diagram shows key aspects of depicting the model structure in the form of a CLD and a SFD. The third item shown in the diagram is the need to understand patterns of behaviour within the system, which are used in the computer model. Research

and stakeholder interviews are usually required to develop such behaviour patterns. These three stages are required to analyse events. The diagram also highlights the importance of finding leverage points. For example, what and where in the recovery process can be strengthened in order to improve the recovery process.

A key challenge to modelling is finding the level of complexity required to answer these questions, and not going beyond that. It is easy to get lost in the details of the real world, calling for clear modelling boundaries to contain the research and development work.

Figure 6 Diagram of System Dynamics Methodology

Hovmand (2014) structured System Dynamics model types into Learning, Coordination, Restructuring and Analysis problems (see Figure 7 **Error! Reference source not found.**). The two modelling strategies to be used in the TURNkey project are the restructuring problem and the analysis problem. A restructuring problem in a recovery process occurs when a stakeholder has to move from its day-to-day working procedures over to recovery procedures. The two sets of procedures are quite different and the shift needs to be understood by the relevant stakeholders. Once the shift to the recovery procedures has been made the problem becomes an analysis problem, i.e., to analyse which policies are useful and how to implement them.

Figure 7 Framing System Dynamics problems

2.5 Challenges to be addressed and proposed models

Seismic recovery and resilience of *CICSs* is a complicated and transdisciplinary research issue involving earthquake engineering, complex networks, economics, and social sciences (Brummitt et al., 2013). The-increasing interconnection within globally integrated modern *CICSs* have created specific vulnerability which might result in a rapid and pervasive spread of failures (Helbing, 2013). This renders the sophisticated interwoven socio-technical networks vulnerable on a planetary scale. Therefore, the state-of-the-art knowledge still falls short of the development of an adaptive and inclusive recovery and resilience modelling framework of *CICSs*. In general, the modelling frameworks established to date mainly focus upon tracking the time-varying functionality of the *CISs* ensuing seismic events. However, it shall be noted that the significance associated with different time-window throughout the post-shock phase is not differentiated. Meanwhile, for most cases, it is most crucial to deliver a rapid-response and effective repairs in the immediate aftermath of earthquake, to prevent the initial physical damage from creating further cascading effects within and across *CICSs*. Moreover, the evacuation, rescue and treatment of the wounded can be achieved only if the functionality of a set of *CISs* (e.g. transport, power, water, telecommunication) are functional or can be duly recovered within the immediate aftermath period (Tang et al. 2019; BBC 2020).

Against this backdrop, *Task 5.2* proposes an interdisciplinary modelling framework which addresses the modelling of the technical aspects of the *CIS* response, including technical decision making, simulated by Agent Based models supported by Bayesian Networks, and the socio-cultural and management aspects of community resilience and rapid response modelled through Analytical Hierarchy Process and System Dynamics modelling. A number of tailored applications to specific Test Beds are proposed using the framework outlined in Chapter 3 of this deliverable. By comparing with the baseline case where the rapid response measures are absent, a parametric investigation can be carried out to examine the effect of different earthquake magnitude, and the different responsive patterns. The selection of the Test Beds is dependent on their focus on critical infrastructure and/or communities, and their availability of data to address the five core issues emerging from the literature review in relation to the rapid response phase of the recovery. These are further discussed in the

following subsections. The rationale for choosing a specific test beds is further addressed in the following chapters.

2.5.1 Rapid response-oriented recovery and resilience model for CISOs

The seismic resilience modelling frameworks developed so far attempt to gauge the capacity of the CISOs to meet the demand of the community, following earthquakes. As elaborated above, the criticality of different time span within the post-shock recovery phase was not differentiated. This can be, however, misleading for real-world cases, as the sound and optimally-planned restoration in the immediate aftermath of earthquakes (*IAoE*) tend to be most decisive to the seismic resilience of the affected region. As an endeavour to remedy such a deficiency, this sub-task will come up with an inclusive framework, in order to explore the viability and effectiveness of different rapid response strategies, in terms of the alleviation of the lack of resilience. In particular, regarding *RNs*, based on the observation on the real-world seismic events, it was found that their functionality (and hence the ability to support the rapid response of other agencies) can be deteriorated by the “non-structural” damage, such as traffic jams or debris cause by failure of other structures, throughout the *IAoE* (Feng et al. 2020; Aydin et al. 2018). In this sense, such a sub-task will attempt to establish a hierarchical *ABM* to address:

- (1) The proactive, real-time coordination on the evacuation flow, and the emergent repair, as a new rapid response mechanism to improve seismic resilience of *RNs* throughout *IAoE*;
- (2) The seismic resilience of the interconnected Hospital-*RN* system.

These will be discussed in detail in Chapter 3 and 4.

2.5.2 Interdependence-informed recovery and resilience model of CISOs

The effect of cascading failures in the risk and reliability assessment of CISOs has been investigated (e.g., Duenas-Osorio and Vemuru 2009) with reference to power transmission networks (e.g., Guo et al. 2017; Li et al. 2018). Among the causes of a cascading failure, Vaiman et al. (2012) distinguished between exogenous and endogenous events. The latter includes disasters from natural hazards, such as earthquakes.

With specific reference to earthquake-induced cascading effects on structures and infrastructures, the European research project SYNER-G (*Systemic Seismic Vulnerability and Risk Analysis for Buildings, Lifeline Networks and Infrastructures Safety Gain*) represents a milestone. Indeed, this project focused on systemic seismic vulnerability and risk analysis of buildings, bridges, lifelines, and infrastructures, such as roads (Cavaliere et al. 2012b), oil and gas (Esposito and Iervolino 2012), and electric power networks (Cavaliere et al. 2012c). One of the main outcomes of SYNER-G is OOFIMS (*Object-Oriented Framework for Infrastructure Modeling and Simulation*), a computer program able to model and analyze the performance of interconnected/interdependent infrastructural systems and sets of buildings, at the urban/regional scale, in ordinary or “disturbed” conditions (e.g., due to the impact of a natural or human-made hazards).

CISOs are increasingly interdependent and interwoven through sharing and exchange of the operation resources and information (Kröger and Zio 2011, Helbing 2013). Such a tendency

underpins the efficient functioning of the *CISs*. Nevertheless, it simultaneously renders them more vulnerable to disruptive events, like strong earthquakes. Based on *in-situ* observations on the recent calamitous seismic events around the globe, the functionality of the damaged *CISs* is often struggling to recover from the earthquake-induced losses (Hollnagel and Fujita, 2013; Hwang et al., 2015). Besides, the prolonged restoration of one standalone *CIS* often hinders the recovery of a set of other *CISs*, as well as the rescue and evacuation of people in the affected areas (Kawashima et al., 2009; Lekkas et al., 2012).

Many studies have been conducted on the seismic behaviour of integrated *CISs* across modern urban communities. Based on those findings, seismic behaviour of the interdependent *CISs* can be improved by increasing their robustness and reparability (Farr et al., 2014). However, it shall be pointed out that the majority of research efforts have been put on robustness alone, so far (Dueñas-Osorio and Vemuru, 2009; Buldyrev et al., 2010; Zio and Sansavini, 2011; Bashan et al., 2013). By comparison, much fewer researches have been conducted on the repair and recovery of *CISs* (Gehl and D'Ayala 2018). Given the profound interdependence and the vulnerability of *CISs*, such a sub-task also looks into the seismic resilience of the interwoven *CISs* in order to:

- (1) Model the dynamic and looped interdependence among *CISs*, and gauge its impact on the seismic resilience of *RNs* throughout *IAoE*;
- (2) Develop an interdependence-informed, optimally-planned recovery model, based on the findings above.

Modelling of *CIS* interconnections and cascading effects cascading are addressed in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5.

2.5.3 The recovery of *CISs* under incomplete information

The findings from the sub-tasks elaborated above have laid the foundation for the rapid response mechanism and the modelling framework thereof. However, it shall also be noted that, due to the physical damage on the *Telecommunication*, *Power* and *Internet* infrastructure systems, the data around the real-time functionality and the damage heatmap of the interwoven *CISs* is usually hard to access, throughout the *IAoE* (Krishnamurthy et al., 2016; Kammouh et al., 2018). It indicates that the decision-making related to the rapid response discussed herein can only be delivered under evolving and incomplete information. Against this backdrop, this sub-task will, along with the hierarchical *ABM*, propose a Bayesian Network approach as a viable tool, whereby the real-time coordination and decision-making can be achieved. The modelling strategies for coupling *ABM* and *BNM* to study the effect of incomplete information and evolving knowledge during the rapid response phase are presented in Chapter 6.

2.5.4 The recovery of *CISs* incorporating the effect of aftershocks: seismicity forecasting models

Real-world earthquake events are characterised by mainshocks followed by sequences of aftershocks with damage potential, which usually decrease in magnitude and frequency obeying known seismological patterns, but can also increase (Reasenber and Jones 1994). Such aftershock

sequences can have a significant impact on the post-main shock recovery of *CISs*, especially in the early recovery. Nevertheless, research on such a front is somehow scant thus far.

Dong and Frangopol (2015) studied the additional risk that the aftershock sequences would pose to *RNs*, and highlighted that aftershocks can substantially affect the repair cost and residual functionality of bridge structures. To gauge the impact of the main shock and aftershock sequence on highway bridges, economic repair costs, bridge functionality losses, and indirect losses, i.e. resulting detour costs, were all included. Accordingly, they put forward a modelling framework relevant for the pre-shock decision-making on the retrofit of bridge assets to meet acceptable resilience and/or risk performance level. Such a framework can also be employed to inform the decision maker, as to the post-shock repair/rehabilitation activities to reduce economic and societal impacts.

On short time scales, less than a few months, earthquake sequences show a high degree of clustering in space and time. The probability of triggering increases with initial shock's magnitude and decays with elapsed time according to simple scaling laws. The first generation of models used for short-term clustering of earthquakes are the Omori law (Omori, 1894), Omori-Utsu law (also known as Modified-Omori), and then Reasenber and Jones (1989), in chronological order. The *Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences (ETAS) model*, is a space-time-magnitude forecasting model introduced by Ogata (1988). According to several studies (e.g. Marzocchi and Lombardi, 2009, Nandan et al. 2017, 2019, Schorlemmer et al., 2018, Taroni et al., 2018), *ETAS* model ranks top among the best models of earthquake forecasting developed to date and it outperforms several published models (e.g. physics-based and statistical models). *ETAS* model considers the effect of secondary aftershock sequences (i.e. for sequences with large aftershocks that trigger many of their own aftershocks), as every earthquake is regarded as both triggered by earlier events and a potential trigger for subsequent earthquakes. This allow forecasting the evolution of complex seismic sequences (e.g. 2016-2017 Amatrice-Norcia). The application of this modelling technique within the TURNkey framework and its use in the rapid response decision making phase is discussed in Chapter 7.

2.5.5 *CICs* resilience and recovery management models

As discussed in section 2.4.2 the work of Nguyen and Akerar (2020) and Sharifi (2016) examined different perspectives of community resilience. Nonetheless both references generally agreed on the anatomy of an effective community resilience model, as visualised with the flow chart in Figure 8, showing the process of modelling resilience to a hazard threat. This anatomy will be used to assess community resilience management to earthquakes events in the TURNkey project. Specifically, TURNkey will contextualise the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities (UNDRR, 2017), which possesses all these criteria (to a greater or lesser extent), to provide an assessment of community resilience to an earthquake scenario with and without the use of TURNkey *FWCR* platform. This deliverable describes two approaches to modelling critical infrastructure and community resilience management: the *Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) modelling* and the *System Dynamics (SD) modelling*. *AHP* modelling will be used to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform on critical infrastructure and community resilience, in the manner just described. UNDRR defines resilience as ‘the ability of a system, community or society exposed to

hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate, adapt to, transform and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions through risk management'. As such, resilience is shaped by factors across all phases of the disaster risk management cycle. In order to analyse the potential impact of the FWCR platform on critical infrastructure and community resilience, the *AHP* model will therefore take a holistic approach and look at factors that mark disaster preparedness, response and recovery. It will be discussed in detail in section 8.1. The *SD* modelling will be used to zoom in on the role of disaster operations during the rapid recovery phase. Details of this application are presented in section 8.2.

Figure 8 process of modelling resilience to a hazard threat

As an application to test the Nguyen and Akerar (2020) findings the TURNkey project addresses the 3-step community resilience assessment through an analysis of a multi-stakeholder recovery process following a destructive earthquake using System Dynamics methodology. The 3 steps are adapted to the TURNkey project as follows:

1. *Components and factors:*

- a. Hazard event: Will be provided by the TURNkey platform
- b. Community: Will be modelled based on Icelandic testbeds from the perspective of the affected population, municipality staff, repair stakeholders, and infrastructure operators

2. *Objectives of the resilience model:* The focus in D5.2 is on Rapid Recovery, not pre-earthquake activities, therefore, the model objectives will focus on disaster operations, in particular, the four disaster operations provided by Thorvaldsdottir and Sigbjörnsson (2014), outlined in D1.5. These are: a) to monitor and control rising hazards and/or damaging processes (impact operations); b) to save lives (life-saving operations), c) to provide support to those affected, temporary repairs and other temporary measures (relief operations), and d) to implement non-temporary measures to return a community to normalcy (recovery operations).
3. *Mapping of data to the goals/objectives of the resilience model and developing robust procedures for converting data into information; paying particular attention to the problems of aggregating static and dynamic information within modelling frameworks:* The general objectives listed in step 2 will be adapted to the specific objectives of the stakeholders involved in the model, through a stakeholder mapping process. Procedures for converting data into information will be developed by converting TURNkey platform output data into information for decision making processes and policy (strategy) development. Attention to problems associated with static and dynamic information will be addressed by applying System Dynamics frameworks and modelling techniques.

3 TURNkey RAPID RESPONSE-ORIENTED RESILIENCE MODELLING FRAMEWORK OF INTERDEPENDENT CICSs

As discussed in Chapter 2, modern *CISs* are functioning in an interdependent manner, and thereby paving the potential pathways for the local damage and/or dysfunction to cascade promptly and pervasively. Furthermore, it is also widely agreed that seismic resilience of interconnected *CISs* needs to be considered as a time-varying process, rather than an instantaneous state (Michel-Kerjan 2015).

As elaborated in *Section 2.5.1*, the rapid-response in the *Immediate Aftermath of Earthquakes (IAoEs)* plays a very crucial role in determining the overall recovery, and hence the measured resilience of interdependent *CISs* throughout seismic sequences, insomuch as the emergency rescue and repair are often most needed in *IAoEs*, whereas hardest to be delivered, in particular, when an effective *rapid-response* is impaired. Furthermore, the seismological pattern indicates that strong shocks are usually succeeded by a series of aftershocks, which could have a significant impact on the post-shock recovery. In addition, as modern urban communities are the organically collected system of people, organizations, and patterned relationships as well as interdependences (Alesch 2005), their post-shock recovery and resilience will be shaped by the interplay among different stakeholders. It is anticipated that the perception of each of the stakeholders will be time-varying and driving the recovery on the physical assets and, in turn, reshaped by it thereafter.

Therefore, a resilience modelling framework for interdependent *CISs*, accounting for the above aspects should be able to provide answer to the following questions:

1. How can the *Rapid Response* contribute to the recovery and resilience of *CISs* across the post-shock phase?
2. How can the *Rapid Response* be schemed, given the (looped and dynamic) interdependence among *CISs* and given the partial knowledge on the recovery state of any of the *CIS*?
3. How decision-making shall be delivered to balance the trade-offs, in light of the risk posed by potential aftershocks?
4. How shall the *Dynamic Stakeholder Response* be quantified, given the post-shock recovery on the physical *CISs*? How to gauge its impact on the post-shock recovery of the *CISs* and the overall community?

3.1 Overview of the modelling framework

As discussed in *Section 2.1.2*, in such a framework developed in this *Deliverable*, seismic resilience of *CISs* will be examined in the separated *Absorption* and *Recovery* stages. Essentially, the focus on the *Absorption* stage is centred around the estimation on the functionality losses inflicted following the shock, while the corresponding restored functionality will be tracked in the *Recovery* stage.

In principle, the *Absorption* phase refers to a short period in the wake of the earthquake events. Throughout such a phase, the interwoven *CISs* undergo the damage induced by the seismic hazards,

while finding out a path towards the new equilibrium on a substantially lower (usually) functionality level.

Following the Absorption phase, the system of *CISs* will enter the *Recovery* phases, which will often last for a much longer time. In this framework, restoration of the function of the *CISs* was tracked by the *ABM*. Specifically, the repair of any individual *CIS* is supposed to be managed by its own *Operator*, whose behaviour will be modelled by an *Agent*. In general, at each time point, each *Agent* will make a decision in relation to the recovery scheme thereafter, based on the analysis on the functionality status of the *CIS* it is responsible for, as well as the other *CISs*, in order to maximize the “utility” of the recovery campaign, until all the damaged components have been fully repaired.

3.2 Absorption phase resilience assessment

In this framework, damage to various components of *CISs* is quantified by considering seismic vulnerability functions, which provide a measure of the probability that particular components will maintain a certain fraction of their functionality, conditioned on the intensity measure of the earthquake ground motion at its geographic site. This is in line with the approach used in Task 4.1 deliverable 4.2, “Recommendation on Fragility functions for buildings and infrastructure components to be used in a rapid response context”, and will exploit the result of task 4.2, deliverable 4.3 “Simplified models for the estimation of seismic functional and systemic losses”.

To this end seismic fragility functions will firstly be employed to classify the Damage State (*DS*) of the *CIS* components (e.g. bridges across a road networks). Without loss of generality, as shown in Figure 9, a total of four damage states are considered, i.e. no damage (*DS1*), minor damage (*DS2*), moderate damage (*DS3*), and extensive damage (*DS4*). Vulnerability of each component is then assessed by quantifying its remaining degree of functionality, according to its *DS*. Typically, no loss of functionality would be assumed if a component is in *DS1*, total loss of the functionality is assumed if the component is in *DS4*, and an intermediate interpolated degree of functionality loss is assumed for those components in either *DS2*, or *DS3*.

Regarding the realization of the vulnerability analysis in each single simulation, the seismic intensity measure will first be derived by the hazard model, given the earthquake scenarios, produced in WP3. The intervals corresponding to each individual *DSs* can then be characterized, based on the exceedance probability obtained from the corresponding fragility models. Using Monte-Carlo simulation approach, the damage state for each component of the network will be sampled randomly in relation to the IM at the site. The decreased functionality of such a component will be quantified based on the pre-defined relationship between the *DS* and functionality losses. A typical set of functionality loss states, $FL_A(T)$, at the end of the absorption phase, and $FL_R(T)$ during the recovery phase, are shown in Table 1. The timeframe within which each component moves from FL_A to FL_R is a strategic decision that can be determined by several criteria, and can be simulated through the *HABM* to determine optimal outcomes, for the functionality of the global *CISs*, which is computed by aggregating the decreased/increased functionality of the components, according to its operational dynamics, and the topology of the network.

Figure 9 Determination of the DSs of CIS components

Table 1: Functionality loss matrix

Damage state	Disruption duration (days)	FLA	FLR
DS1			
DS2	1-90	25-50% speed reduction	0-10% speed reduction
DS3	60-120	100% lane closure	50% lane closure
DS4	90-150	100% lane closure	100% lane closure

As shown in Table 1 the duration of the disruption is highly variable, as reported in literature and from direct survey of road networks operators (Gehl & D'Ayala 2018; Shinozuka et al. 2003) and there is substantial overlap in time of recovery for different damage states. This is highly dependent on the specific component damaged (i.e. type of bridge, subcomponent damaged within the bridge) the mode of damage and the resources of the operator to repair or replace the component. Therefore the recovery process is affected by a high degree of epistemic uncertainty as to the quickest path of recovery and this will be simulated by considering probabilistic distribution of disruption times and implementing a suite of realisations sampling different values within such distributions.

3.3 Rapid Response phase resilience assessment

As elaborated in Section 3.1, standard modelling of interconnected system of CISs assumes that the restoration of their functionality starts when all damage induced by the earthquake hazards has been “absorbed”. Nevertheless, many of the lessons learnt from past earthquake events have highlighted that one of the main deficiencies regarding state-of-the-art resilience modelling frameworks lie in their indiscriminate characterization on the criticality associated with different time-windows, throughout the post-shock recovery stage. On the other hand, it shall be noted that, the gap between the CISs deliverable functionality ($DF(t)$) (e.g. access, power, water, medical treatment and etc.) and the corresponding demand (D) from the community often turns out to be devastating. For instance,

in the aftermath of April 25, 2015 Gorkha earthquake in Nepal, hundreds of thousands of people were left homeless, and more importantly, struggling to receive aid due to the lack of government response and coordination (The Guardian 2015). Likewise, the damage induced by the leakage of hazardous materials will be irreparable, should not effective countermeasure be in place (Aki 2017). In this sense, it can be stated that the mismatch between the often-to-be soaring functionality demand and the corresponding declining supply capacity in the immediate aftermath of disruptive events has become a deeply-rooted cause of the lack of resilience, for Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems (CICSSs). Moreover, such a lack of resilience can be further exasperated, given the seismological pattern that strong shocks are often followed by a series of aftershocks.

Therefore, the proposed TURNkey resilience assessment model considers a subdivision of the post-shock recovery phase, in two stages: the immediate aftermath of the hazards (*IAoEs*), and the medium to long-term recovery thereafter. As illustrated in Figure 10, the time points t_0 and t_r denote the moment when the seismic event occurs, and the end of the *IAoEs*, respectively, whereby the system has recovered sufficiently, to satisfy the level of reduced demand set by the post-event state of the community (e.g. reduced need of public transport because school and business are down). Naturally, the duration of *IAoE* is set to be case-specific, so as to be adaptive to the different magnitude of the earthquake hazards, the different vulnerability, and the societal context of *CICSSs* (SPUR, 2009; Smith, 2013).

Figure 10 Post-shock rapid responses, where $DF(t)$ is the deliverable functionality and $D(t)$ the corresponding Community Demand

Correspondingly, for each *CISs*, it can be postulated that Equation (4):

$$RR = \operatorname{argmin} \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_r} (D(t) - DF(t, a)) dt \right) \quad (4)$$

defines the rapid response *RR* as the set of actions taken by the *Operator* of each individual *CIS* to minimize the functionality deficit throughout the *IAoEs*, where $D(t)$ refers to the functionality demand, while $DF(t, a)$ denotes the recovering deliverable functionality, conditioned on the action a taken by the *Operator*.

However, given the interdependence of *CISs* constituting *CICSSs* and given the partial knowledge condition under which the *Operators* action will be taken, Figure 11 provides a holistic description of the *RR* process. Three different stages can be identified: the immediate start of the recovery, based

on limited real information and prior knowledge (such as the one produced by TURNkey platform); whereby operators actions are usually poorly coordinated, a proper *RR*, relying on evolving information, clear perception of affected interdependencies and improved *Operators* coordination, and finally a *Recovery* phase, affected by aftershocks, but informed by the new level of risks computed on the basis of a better knowledge of the actual functionality and damage losses. The actions of the *Operators* to restore functionality are determined to an extent by the community (public) needs, hereby represented by the *Dynamic Stakeholder Response (DSR)*.

Figure 11 Recovery modelling framework of the interconnected CICSs subject to seismic hazards ($FL(t)$ refers to the Functionality Loss, while $DF(t)$ is the Deliverable Functionality and $DSR(t)$ denotes the Dynamic Stakeholder Response)

Accordingly, the modelling framework for the post-shock recovery will consist of the modules on the rapid-response (Chapter 4), the impact of interdependence on the rapid response and recovery (Chapter 5), the rapid response and recovery under incomplete information (Chapter 6), the rapid response under potential aftershocks (Chapter 7), and the rapid response-oriented community resilience (Chapter 8). The output from the modules will be used to address the requirement of the TURNkey's *DSSs* emerging from other activities within the project..

4 RAPID RESPONSE-ORIENTED RECOVERY MODELS

In this Chapter, an inclusive agent-based model (*ABM*) is proposed to shed light on the post-shock recovery of both the individual and coupled *CISs*, particularly, throughout the *IAoE* phase. *ABM* has now been widely employed as an effective tool to capture the behaviour of a broad array of social, economic and political systems where the interaction of constituents (autonomous agents) depends on the particular state of the system and the interaction among the agents. Hence, it is capable of delivering a nuanced model of the post-earthquake rapid responses and account for different strategies and capabilities of all players involved in such a process.

In *Section 4.1*, such a rapid response-oriented, agent-based modelling framework is applied on seismic resilience of the standalone road network. *Section 4.2*, outlines the objective functions of the *AB* model which provide measures of the *RN* resilience. In section 4.3 the Emergency Hospital network, whose *RR* is most critical throughout *IAoE*, is also considered and integrated with the road network. The *HABM* framework is then employed to highlight the effect of rapid response on seismic resilience of the coupled *Hospital- Road networks*, especially, with regard to the time-varying fatalities. Two Test Beds are chosen for the application of the *HABM*, as they offer the opportunity of testing the flexibility of the model when applied to *RNs* with diverse topological and structural characteristics, one regional and one urban, and their respective coupling with the Health Emergency networks.

4.1 Rapid response-based recovery and resilience model of individual *CISs*

Without significant loss of the generality, the modelling framework will be presented and exemplified for *Road Networks (RNs)*, as these play a strategically crucial role, in terms of the post-shock recovery of *CICs* (elaborated in Section 2.2). In the first realisation of this model, it is assumed that only the bridge structures can be damaged under seismic hazards, while the road segments are supposed to remain intact. This is due to the very limited information currently available on the slope conditions, especially in the regional case study. For the urban case study, road failure is highly unlikely as the urban centre considered is on a flat plane.

As discussed in *Section 3.2*, in the *Absorption phase*, the functionality status (accessibility) of each individual bridge will be determined, based on the vulnerability functions. As the earthquake scenarios have been generated, the Peak Ground Accelerations (*PGAs*) will first be computed, based on attenuation models appropriate to the site. The damage status can therefore be obtained, according to the set of the fragility models associated with each Damage State (*DS*). The functionality losses can be quantified with the loss estimation matrix

In the following *Recovery phase*, in this framework, *HABM* is employed to track the restoration trajectory of the *RNs*. The recovery is set to start with the functionality status obtained in the *Absorption phase*, and run in sequence. It shall be noted that, the repair of bridges on different *DSs* will be modelled separately. Specifically, the *HABM* will only be applied on those bridges with *DS2*, as those bridges with severe damage often need to be reconstructed, which would last for a significantly longer period of time (the process will therefore be modelled by the *Stochastic Recovery* functions). More crucially, as a viable *RR* strategy, the bridge with *DS2* can be ranked based on their

scaled betweenness centrality of each bridge. Mathematically, the betweenness centrality of each bridge v is as follows:

$$g(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (5)$$

Where σ_{st} is the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t , $\sigma_{st}(v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v .

This criterion, which sees the prioritization of bridges critical to the largest number of paths, is not exclusive and other rapid response strategies can be considered by the *Operator*, for instance the priority can be to recover access to specific other critical facilities (such decisions requiring a degree of coordination with other *Operators*). In each single simulation, the recovery agent is set to depart from the Repair Centre and start to repair the first bridge with DS2 (namely, the one with the largest value of betweenness centrality) on the ranked list, as shown in Figure 12. After such a bridge has been fully repaired, the *Agent* will proceed to restore the next bridge in the ranking list, until all the ones considered critical have been repaired. However, it shall be highlighted that the *Agent* may encounter inaccessible paths, due to bridges damaged to level DS3 and DS4. While in *HABMs* for long-term recovery, the Agent is assumed to be waiting for these bridges to be repaired, according to the stochastic model with time - lags identified in Table 1, a more sophisticated model, considering forms of rapid temporary intervention, will be developed to be more specifically relevant to the *RR* phase.

By doing that, the transportation capacity of the *RNs* can be restored in a most efficient pattern, throughout *IAoEs*. This can be particularly significant, when it comes to the restoration on the other *CISs*, as well as the emergent rescue of the wounded.

Figure 12 Flowchart of proposed modelling framework of seismic resilience

4.2 Resilience measures of road network under seismic hazards

For the purpose of the applications relevant to the TURNkeys and its inclusions in the FWCR, three different measures of seismic resilience of road network are currently considered:

A. *Functionality losses on the component level*

With the scenario-based modelling framework, it is significant to first examine the probabilistic distributions of the DSs of a set of the bridges, especially, those crucial ones. Such a distribution itself will be time-varying, as the repair is underway. Without loss of generality, in this framework, the distribution obtained immediately following the shock will be focused on (t_0 in Figure 10);

B. *Percentage of Functional bridges*

As indicated above, the functionality status of *RNs*, on both the component and the system level, will be time-varying. To capture the evolution of the functionality losses at the global level, the percentage of functional bridges will be tracked throughout the entire seismic events, and employed as another resilience measure;

C. *Time-varying travelling time*

The functionality of *RNs* is contingent not just upon the *Percentage of Functional bridges*, but also the topology of the network, in other words, their relative position. The viable network's topology is a function of time affected by the seismic event sequence and the repair/restoration strategy. For example, immediately following the seismic hazard, some of the road segments of the *RN* may become inaccessible, due to the damage of a set of the bridges associated with them. From the perspective of graph theory, the topology at time (t) is now different from the *RN* topology at time (t_0), as these inaccessible road segments are removed from the topological model representing the *RN*. Therefore, given the start and end points of interest, the shortest path between them may likely be substantially different from the one obtained at time (t_0) before the earthquake (without any damaged bridge), or there might not be an accessible path (travelling time $\Delta t \rightarrow \infty$). However, at any time after (t_a), representing the end of the absorption phase, as the rapid response and recovery are underway, the functionality of those damaged bridges will start to be restored. Therefore, those inaccessible paths can be available again, as those associated damaged bridges have been fully or partially repaired and they are passable. The shortest path between a particular pair of start and end points will also be updated (i.e. shortened, or even restored to the original one generated from the intact *RN*). This global dynamic behaviour of the network is well represented by the travel time between locations of interest ($\Delta t_{OD}(t)$), expressed as a function of the rapid response and recovery period.

4.3 Rapid response-based recovery and resilience model of coupled CISs

To further investigate the interaction between community and networks during rapid response, as depicted in Figure 11, within the TURNkey FWCR platform, a tailored model will be designed to study the effect of road network functionality losses on the rescue and delivery of the wounded to hospitals. The post-shock resilience of *Hospital* networks is strategically crucial to the timely

treatment of the wounded across the affected areas. However, the expeditious rescue can only be delivered as long as the functionality of the corresponding RN can also be effectively sustained/restored.

Figure 13 Resilience modelling framework of coupled RN-Hospital
($TB(t)$, $B(t)$, $DP(t)$, and $TP(t)$ denote the time-varying Temporarily functional Bridges, functional Bridges, Deliverable Patients, and Treatable Patients, respectively)

The *ABM* described in Figure 12 will be further developed, whereby a total of three agents will be included. Namely, a *RN Operator*, a *Hospital System Operator*, and the *Administrator* agent as shown in Figure 13. To be informative to the public, a new resilience measure, *Expected Fatality* (t) ($EF(t)$), will be proposed. At each time point t , $EF(t)$ will be obtained by aggregating the wounded people for which treatment cannot be delivered, due to the gap between the *Hospital* functionality (the number of Treated Patients, $TP(t)$) and the corresponding *Demand* (Dispatched Patients, $DP(t)$), in addition to the undeliverable wounded due to the inaccessible roads across the *RN*.

Similar to the *ABM* discussed in Section 4.1, the two Operator agents will run the recovery of their own physical assets, respectively. In particular, the *RN* recovery is set to be hierarchical. Specifically, as shown in Figure 13, such a recovery endeavour comprises the full restoration of the functionality of damaged bridges, and the partial functionality restoration, in terms of those crucial bridges, yet sustaining extensive damage.

In the meantime, the *Administrator*, is set to oversee the recovery on the networked *RN - Hospital*. Its perception with regard to the time-varying $EF(t)$ can be modelled according to the Dynamic Stakeholder Response model that will be elaborated in Chapter 8. Given such a perception on $EF(t)$, it will communicate with the *HS* operator, so as to minimize its value thereafter. Furthermore, the *Contingency Dispatch* will also be proposed as *Rapid Response* of the *Administrator* agent. Similar to the notion of “Triage”, in such a *Dispatch* strategy, $DP(t)$ will first be ranked based on the severity of the injury the wounded have sustained. In the meantime, given the $TP(t)$, the wounded will be dispatched into different *Hospitals*, in order to further minimize *Expected Fatality*.

4.4 Case studies

4.4.1 Rapid Recovery of the road network in the Luchon region, France, TB2

To demonstrate the adaptability and applicability of the developed framework, a case-study will be run on a real-world network in the region of *Luchon, France*. This is a historic and touristic region, one of the valleys of the Pyrenees connecting France to Spain, served by a hierarchical RN composed of a route nationale (N125), several route départementales (Dxx), and rural roads. Given the mountainous topography and the presence of many water courses, the network is characterised by 118 bridges. In the model the road hierarchy is maintained by classifying them in main roads, regional roads and local roads. A representation of the network is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 *Road Network* across the Luchon valley

4.4.2 Rapid response-based recovery and resilience model of interconnected Hospital-RN systems. Application to TB1, Bucharest, Romania.

The case study of the Luchon valley, France considers a mountainous region where the road network has very little redundancy, only one main path and localised secondary paths and a large number of vulnerable points represented by the bridges. Other vulnerable points might be represented by sections of the roads exposed to secondary hazards, such as earthquake triggered rockfall or slope failure, which are not currently included in the model.

However, in urban settings the redundancy of the network is usually much higher and the number of vulnerable points is comparatively low, although there might be pinch points that create high criticality in the delivery of other services, for instance medical rapid response and rescue teams. Therefore the attention of this second modelling framework is to consider the rapid response and

resilience of the interconnected system of *Hospital network-RN*, during the *IAoE* period in urban settings. This will be done in collaboration between UCL and INFP.

The case study chosen is the TURNkey TB1, Bucharest, Romania, and the framework builds on work developed by Toma-Danila et al. (2020), who developed an open-source toolbox, “Network- Risk” capable of determining and visualising areas of high risk blockages on the road network following seismic events (see Figure 15).

Figure 15 : Methodology underpinning the Network-risk Toolbox

For the proposed application the resilience measure chosen will be the capability of providing a prompt medical intervention, based on the medical assumption of the “golden hour” for survivability (Lerner and Moscati, 2001). Therefore in order to measure the resilience of the network of A&E surgical hospitals’ location and the road network serving them, in relation to vulnerable neighbours of the city, the framework developed in section 4.1 will be used to evaluate the time needed for medical rapid response units to reach an affected area and to return to a suitable emergency hospital given the typical wounds of an earthquake, given a RN post-earthquake affected scenario. This resilience measure can be defined as the *chances of survival in case of severe injury due to an earthquake*. For the analysis to be of relevance and the metric to be meaningful, critical information is needed: spatial location of hospitals, location of medical rapid response units diverse from hospitals, a scenario in which some of the victims are transported by on-site available cars. To calculate the proposed metric, the data requirements are:

- Location of ambulances, which are usually distributed in the city beyond the location of emergency hospitals. Also, special units from search and rescue, such as the Mobile Emergency Service for Resuscitation and Extrication (*SMURD* in Bucharest) are of special interest in *IAoE*, being able to provide emergency medical services on site.

- Location of emergency hospitals and their treatment capabilities (treatment for orthopaedic trauma, surgical amputation or burns) accounting, besides medical specialities and equipment, also for medical personnel availability in the *IAoE* period. Some of these hospitals might be affected and not usable, therefore vulnerability analysis of hospital structures (fragility functions can be determined and used and/or functionality loss functions) will be considered, leading to an evaluation of second-best emergency hospital alternatives, in terms of delivery time.

- Areas where severely injured people are expected to be. This will be identified through studying the distribution of different building typologies, through the city. Vulnerable buildings can inflict different type of casualties and injuries to different number of people: for example, the severe damage of high-rise buildings would generate substantial numbers of head, face, and brain injuries, as well as potential fire outbreaks, while the collapse of masonry low-rise buildings would result in fewer, but possibly more lethal injuries.

- Scenarios for affected RN, given direct and indirect damage on network components and other post-earthquake implications, from debris blocking the roads to emergency traffic patterns. Indeed, it should be considered that not all injured cases will be attended by emergency services on site, as many might be delivered to hospitals in private cars, leading to near-hospital potential chaos.

- In computing fastest or safest routes between affected areas and hospitals, in some cases such as in Bucharest, the impact of designated emergency vehicle lanes (which can use for example tram lines) can be modelled.

The aforementioned resilience measure links eventually the time needed for being reached and reaching medical optimum treatment with the decreasing chances of survival given specific injuries, considering both under debris and out of debris time. We will further elaborate this model in the TURNkey Project.

Potential applications of such a measure would also be on testing the best locations for deploying mobile emergency hospitals – with respect also to RN accessibility. Also, this resilient measure is of interest both for urban areas, where the number of emergency facilities and vehicles is in general relatively large, but also casualties can be significant in neighbours at high risk, but also in rural and in a regional context, where the distances between affected areas and emergency facilities are much more considerable and potential road obstructions can lead to time-costly detours. The result of the analysis can provide in some cases conclusions upon the utility of helicopter medical intervention.

When using fire-fighter locations instead of ambulance locations in the analysis, insights upon capabilities to intervene in case of fire outbreaks or debris rescue (given also vehicle and personnel capabilities) can be obtained. Given the size of some of the fire engines, the limited access on narrow streets can be accounted for. Beside accessibility analysis, aspects regarding resilience can be quantified in a performance metric reflecting the timely efficient fire-extinguishing capabilities.

5 INTERDEPENDENCE-INFORMED RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE MODELS

5.1 Introduction

Besides the interaction between hospitals and road networks, presented in the previous section, the effect of systems interdependence and cascading effect within and without a *CIS* and its community, is analysed in detail with reference to a sea port, as is a system that more easily allows a clear definition of spatial and systemic boundary conditions.

A port is composed of interconnected components that constitute a framework supporting the functionality of the entire multi-component system. A variety of facilities exists within a seaport, such as infrastructure for cargo handling and storage, passenger terminals, road and rail transportation lines, utility systems, such as electric power and water supply networks, and fuel storage tanks. Potential disruptions of one element caused by a seismic event may trigger a domino effect that influences the performance of the entire system.

Seismic risk assessment of seaports has rarely addressed interdependency problems, also referred to in the literature as cascade or domino effects (e.g., Mota de Sá et al. 2016). A first attempt to address the interdependencies among the elements of a port system was performed with reference to the port of Thessaloniki in Greece (Kakderi et al. 2013).

EUCENTRE has gained significant experience in the field of seismic vulnerability and risk assessment of seaports both at national and international level. For the Italian Department of Civil Protection, EUCENTRE developed a web-based GIS computational platform for Italian seaports, which is an interactive tool that allows users to assess the seismic risk of maritime ports. Moreover, technical data and metadata, and the results of calculations, are made available on the Internet through specific functionalities of webGIS applications. The webGIS computational platform for seaports developed by EUCENTRE (Bozzoni et al. 2018) has been equipped with a GIS-based tool for the evaluation of seismic damage at a seaport, including the assessment of the seismic hazard and vulnerability of the individual port facilities.

Recently, at EUCENTRE a novel procedure was developed to account for cascading effects when assessing the seismic risk of seaport systems (Conca et al. 2020). The developed procedure combines a simulation-based framework with a detailed definition of seismic hazard that accounts for both site effects and liquefaction potential, a novelty in the current technical literature. The port system is typically composed of a number of terminals. Each terminal represents a subsystem of the port and is composed of waterfront structures, operating cranes, and electric power systems. Modelling the interdependencies among port elements represents one of the critical phases in assessing the seismic vulnerability of a multi-component system. Conca et al. (2020) illustrates an application of the novel procedure with reference to the port of Gioia Tauro, which is the largest port for container transshipment in Italy and is located in a territory characterized by high seismicity. The port of Gioia Tauro is the Test-Bed 5 within the TURNkey project. Two alternative models were considered to account for the cascading effects, the results of which were compared with the outcomes of a scenario in which the interdependencies were neglected.

Further details on the methodology developed at EUCENTRE to assess seismic risk of a port system, are provided in Section 5.2 and the application of the methodology with reference to the port of Gioia Tauro is briefly presented in Section 5.3.

5.2 Methodology developed at EUCENTRE to assess seismic risk of a port system by addressing interdependencies among port component

Various approaches are proposed in the literature to predict the performance of a multi-component system subjected to earthquake loading by taking into account their interdependencies. A simulation-based method was chosen to solve the actual problem because of its generality and robustness (Cavalieri et al., 2012a). Indeed, applications of this method within the SYNER-G project can be found in Cavalieri et al. (2012a, b, c, 2014, 2016), Kakderi et al. (2012), Esposito and Iervolino (2012), and Esposito et al. (2015). In South Korea, a simulation-based method has been successfully applied in the seismic loss estimation of seaport transportation systems (e.g., Na and Shinozuka, 2009). Figure 16 illustrates a flowchart of the procedure developed at EUCENTRE to assess the seismic risk of a multicomponent port system.

The required input data are:

- seismic hazard parameters with their associated probabilistic distributions,
- port system topology, namely, the vulnerable elements to be considered, their spatial layout, and their connections, and
- fragility model of components represented by fragility functions.

Figure 16 Flow-chart of the procedure developed at EUCENTRE to assess the seismic risk of a multicomponent port system (originally in Bozzoni et al. 2018, updated in Conca et al. 2020).

Seismic damage observed at seaports is the result of different types of concurrent hazards besides the mainshock, namely, liquefaction, soil settlements, and - although rare - surface fault rupture. Thus, according to Bozzoni et al. (2014), the procedure to quantify the seismic hazard and related co-seismic effects involves seismic hazard assessments for standard outcropping bedrock site conditions; local ground response analyses; evaluation of liquefaction potential; and induced displacements. Next, after defining the hazards, the seismic risk assessment of a seaport multicomponent system requires joint knowledge of geological, geotechnical, and bathymetric data of the port site with the technical information associated with the structural and infrastructural elements making up the facility.

The port subjected to earthquake loading is modelled in Conca et al. (2020) as a multicomponent system in which the vulnerability of every single element is estimated using an appropriate fragility function. Assessment of the systemic vulnerability of the entire system is accomplished through a simulation-based method that considers the interdependencies among the elements at risk. In each simulation (or scenario), a Monte Carlo analysis is used to sample the value of the seismic parameters from the associated probabilistic distributions to be used as intensity measures for the fragility functions. The physical damage of all of the components is then sampled from the fragility functions. Based on the sampled damage state of the single components in each scenario, the functionality of the port elements is evaluated. The functionality relies not only on the direct damage to the elements but also on the damage suffered by the elements as a result of the interconnected components. At the end of the simulation, the results are calculated in terms of system performance and total loss. Furthermore, for each component, a non-functionality level is calculated as the probability that the element is out of service. Once the functionality of each element is evaluated, the system performance of each scenario is measured by a performance indicator (*PI*), according to Kakderi et al. (2013). The methodology has been implemented in the MATLAB computing environment by the Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) paradigm by adopting the *OOFIMS* simulation tool as guidance. This procedure is repeated several times until the process converges toward stable results (achieved when the moving average of the *PI* converges to a constant) to fully characterize the uncertainty represented by the probability distributions of the input parameters and of the fragility models adopted.

5.3 Application to the multi-component port of TB5, Gioia Tauro (Southern Italy)

The port of Gioia Tauro is located in the province of Reggio Calabria in Southern Italy, along the Tyrrhenian coast. More than one-third of all national transshipment traffic takes place at the port of Gioia Tauro, which by Italian law is classified as a port of international economic relevance. Gioia Tauro is at the centre of the Mediterranean Sea, along the route connecting the Suez Canal to Gibraltar - one of the busiest maritime corridors in the world that links East Asia to Northern Europe and America. The main infrastructure at Gioia Tauro port consists of an artificial channel, 200m (min) - 250m (max) wide and 3km long, running parallel to the coastline with a 300m wide entrance and an evolution basin of 750m in diameter. The port has eight docks for a total length greater than 5km.

The seismic risk of the Gioia Tauro port was assessed using the simulation-based methodology previously illustrated. For each return period (i.e., 100, 475, and 950 years), a total of 1,000 simulations were carried out. This number of simulations yielded stable estimates of the *PI*. The

results of the analyses in terms of *PI* and the performance loss are reported in Table 2. For the 100-year return period, the potential loss is low but significantly increases for the 475- and 950-year return periods. Table 2 also provides a comparison of the results obtained with and without modelling the interdependencies. The latter case (i.e., without interdependencies) leads to less conservative results because the domino effects are not addressed. As an example, the average loss for the 475-year return period computed by considering the cascading effects is 83%, while is 56% without them.

Table 2 Application of the EUCENTRE methodology at the port of Gioia Tauro: results of analysis in terms of PI (performance index) and average loss for three considered return periods (Conca et al. 2020).

Return period (year)	Port capacity (TEU/day)	
	PI seismic event ^a	Average loss (%)
No interdependencies		
100	2,996	17
475	2,040	43
950	1,572	56
Interdependencies		
100	2,385	34
475	1,045	71
950	614	83
Interdependencies (considering backup power supply for cargo handling system)		
100	3,008	16
475	2,045	43
950	1,587	56

Note: Comparison between results obtained considering and neglecting the interdependencies among port components and a backup power supply for cargo handling system is shown.

^aPI assumed in ordinary condition: 3600 TEU/day.

The GIS maps in Figure 17 indicate the non-functionality levels computed for cranes and terminals at the port of Gioia Tauro for the 475-year return period, considering the interdependencies among the port's components (a), and (b) ignoring the interdependencies, respectively. The level of non-functionality indicated in Figure 17(a) increases to medium for the central part of the port characterized by a more severe expected damage because of the interdependencies. The non-functionality levels are computed for those components whose functionality in the event of an earthquake is jeopardized by the damage state of other elements (i.e., cranes and wharf structures) and is defined as the probability for an element to end up out of service after the ground shaking.

These levels are calculated as the number of times that the element has been out of service (in percentage) - either for direct damage or for domino effects - during the simulations. The threshold beyond which an element is considered out of service is the moderate damage state (*DS*). Without considering the interdependencies, this threshold coincides with the probability of the moderate *DS* according to the fragility model adopted for the object port component. For example, a crane whose moderate *DS* has a probability of occurrence equal to 0.6 for a given ground motion parameter is out of service in approximately 60% of the simulations. Obviously, considering interdependencies, this probability increases. Depending on the percentage, the non-functionality levels of each element can be defined according to Kakderi et al. (2013) as follows: low (<30%), moderate (30%–70%), and

high (>70%). The most vulnerable elements at the Gioia Tauro port appear to be the cranes for both direct damages and given the interdependencies with other port elements. Indeed, the interdependency between the cargo handling system and power electrical unit seems to be crucial in the assessment of the seismic vulnerability of the port.

Figure 17. GIS maps showing non-functionality levels computed for cranes and terminals at the port of Gioia Tauro for the 475-year return period taking into account the interdependencies among elements in the (a) seismic vulnerability assessment; and (b) without addressing these interdependencies, respectively (Conca et al. 2020).

In light of this discussion, an alternative model of interdependencies among the port elements has been created at EUC by considering a backup power supply associated with the cranes (Conca et al. 2020). The hypothesis of the adoption of an emergency electric power generator able to supply the cargo handling system seems reasonable in such a relevant port multicomponent system. The results obtained by adopting this alternative model, presented in Table 2, are almost coincident with those obtained by neglecting the interdependencies. These results confirm the critical interdependency between the cargo handling system and the electrical power unit controls. Indeed, the adoption of a backup power supply for the cranes can significantly contribute to reducing the economic losses induced by an earthquake. The results of the aforementioned analyses can be exploited by decision makers at the port of Gioia Tauro (e.g., Port Authority) to properly identify countermeasures to reduce seismic induced economic losses.

Within TURNkey, a more detailed characterization of the interdependencies in the multicomponent port of Gioia Tauro (e.g. by implementing a model able to address the role of

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facilities aimed to control traffic, etc.) will be performed to confirm these preliminary results, and their relevance to rapid response.

6 THE POST-SHOCK RECOVERY OF CISs UNDER INCOMPLETE INFORMATION

During the early recovery phase (*IAoE*), the information regarding the heatmap of the global networked *CISs* will be dynamic and evolving, depending on the information that is gradually retrieved from the field. Therefore, a *Bayesian Network (BN)* framework has been adopted as the key approach for the rapid response phase in the TURNkey project. It is extensively developed in Work Package 4 (*Physical and Systematic Vulnerability Estimation for Rapid Loss Prediction Updating*), as part of the *Rapid Earthquake Loss Prediction Model*. The following paragraphs summarize the potential use of the *BN* outcomes as inputs to the recovery and resilience models, while demonstrating its application to a road network system.

6.1 Bayesian Networks as a tool for post-event loss updating

BNs organize random variables in the form of a directed acyclic graph, where the dependencies between the various nodes are represented by conditional probabilities. An inference is performed on the *BN* when one or more nodes are observed (i.e. evidence is entered by specifying a given state) and when the probabilities of the other nodes are updated. In the case of a forward analysis, evidence may be entered at the root nodes and the updated distributions can be estimated at the child nodes (e.g. distribution of infrastructure losses given the occurrence of some natural hazard events). Conversely, a backward analysis consists in the inference of the root nodes based on the observation of a given child node (e.g. updated distribution of the seismic intensity level given the observation of a given loss level).

Thanks to these features, *BNs* constitute an adequate solution for the loss assessment and updating of exposed *CISs* in the absorption phase (Bensi et al., 2015). The inference operations on a *BN* enable the combination of the initial estimates of losses (i.e., prior distribution provided by predictive models) and of field observations (i.e., evidence fixed at some nodes) in order to generate updated posterior distributions of the variables of interest, under Bayes' rule.

In the TURNkey context, the main sources of observations pertain to the knowledge of the intensity measure (*IM*) at some locations of the exposed area (either via accelerometric stations or via macroseismic testimonies) and the estimation of the damage state (*DS*) of some physical components (from structural health monitoring techniques). By building upon the *BN* framework for the derivation of shake-maps proposed in Work Package 3 (*Assessment of ground motions before, during and after an earthquake*), the hazard layer of the *BN* may then be augmented with component and system layers, as schematically shown in Figure 18. The hazard layer corresponds to the same variables involved in the derivation of shake-maps (Gehl et al., 2017, Guérin-Marthe et al., 2020): IM_i represents the distribution of the ground-motion parameter of interest (e.g., peak ground acceleration, PGA) at the location of the exposed components, W represents the distribution of the inter-event error term of the ground-motion model, and U_i the distribution of the intra-event error terms (spatially correlated field). The component layer consists of variables DS_i representing the damage states of the components, where the damage probabilities are obtained from fragility functions conditioned on the value of IM_i . Finally, the system performance node S may represent any performance metric that is

of interest for the system analysis (e.g., connectivity, functionality, serviceability), and it depends on the states of the components.

Figure 18. A BN for the loss assessment of an infrastructure system (The red nodes (DS_2 and IM_o) represent examples of evidenced variables, where observations are gathered and propagated across the network).

Bensi et al. (2011) have demonstrated the application of Bayesian networks to the seismic risk assessment of infrastructure systems. Modelling techniques are proposed in order to generate Gaussian random fields (i.e. to account for the spatial correlation of the ground motion field) and to assess the system performance as a function of the components' performance. However, physical infrastructure components are usually strongly interconnected and most of them contribute to the performance of the system (e.g., sets of bridges contributing to numerous possible routes in a road network). As a result, evaluation of the system performance measure (S) based on the combination of the states of n components is one typical case of dimensionality curse, as the size of the system node S (i.e., linked to the number of parent nodes) grows exponentially with the number of components (i.e., combinatory explosion). Bensi et al. (2013) have explored various strategies based on the BN's topology in order to alleviate this issue: they advocate the grouping of components into parallel or series sub-systems through the identification of minimum link sets or cut sets, thus limiting the amounts of edges converging towards a given node.

Alternative BN frameworks have also been proposed, such as the use of a compression algorithm in order to reduce the memory storage space of the conditional probability table of the system node S (Tien et al., 2016, 2017). On the other hand, Pozzi and Der Kiureghian (2013) have investigated Gaussian BNs, which consist of continuous variables and have therefore the merit of greatly reducing the sizes of (discrete) conditional probability tables. However, this approach requires all variables to

be represented by a Gaussian distribution, which is not the case of the components' states (i.e., discrete damage states). This strong limitation prevents the use of exact inference algorithms, and approximate inference engines such as importance sampling or Gibbs sampling have to be used instead. The aforementioned issues have been identified and characterized by Cavalieri et al. (2017), who examined current challenges posed by the *BN* modelling of real-world *CISs*, in terms of both computational complexity and level of system analysis (i.e., formulation of the system performance measure). These considerations have led to the development of an approximate *BN* approach (Gehl et al., 2018), where an incomplete naïve formulation (i.e., a set of component nodes converging towards the system node) is learned from off-line stochastic loss scenarios: although less straightforward to implement, this method is able to deal with large real-world systems and to estimate elaborate system performance measures (i.e., not limited to connectivity analyses).

6.2 Application of the BN framework to the TB2: RN in Luchon, France

Ongoing work in WP4 has led to the development of a rapid response BN framework, which is applied to the Test-Bed 2 (Pyrenees mountain range, France) road network in Luchon. The studied road network is located around the *Luchon* valley, it is composed of 118 bridges and it connects 53 municipalities (small villages and towns), as shown in Figure 14. Currently, a first version of the BN is built only to perform simple connectivity analyses (i.e., whether there is an accessible route between points A and B immediately after the earthquake event). To this end, the initial network topology is converted into a more conceptual layer, where, in this initial model, only the bridges are considered as vulnerable components: as a result, potentially impassable routes between network intersections are simplified (i.e., grouping of sets of bridges in series), as shown in Figure 19. Moreover, the network is decomposed into minimum link sets (*MLSs*), which represent the minimum sets of components that are required to ensure the desired function of the system (i.e., connection between points A and B).

Figure 19 Left: Conceptual network topology with simplified paths between intersections. Right: Example of a decomposition into MLs, defining all possible routes between points A and B. The blue stars in white circles represent the bridges.

As a result, the connectivity analysis between two points of the network is broken down into parallel sub-systems containing in-series components (i.e. several *MLSs* of in-series bridges). Such a system may be formulated in a *BN* (see Figure 20), which becomes less cumbersome to solve than a naïve formulation (i.e., convergence of all components towards the system node). Moreover, it enables the identification of the probability of accessibility of different routes (i.e., different *MLSs*).

Figure 20 . Illustration of the proposed *BN* for the connectivity loss assessment of the studied road network. Here, $n = 118$ (number of bridges) and $k = 10$ (number of *MLSs* between points A and B).

Currently, the proposed *BN* is implemented and solved in the OpenBUGS software (Lunn et al., 2009): thanks to a Markov-chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) sampling scheme, it is able to model both discrete and continuous variables. The trade-off is the use of an approximate inference scheme, which provides empirical posterior distributions of the variables (i.e., the distribution is built from the MCMC samples). However, this modelling choice avoids the pitfalls of exact inference algorithms (see previous sub-section) and it offers a robust solution for the updating of loss projections in the *IAoE* phase.

As an example, a hypothetical earthquake scenario is demonstrated, assuming several ground-motion measurements in the vicinity and the identification of the damage states of some bridges (i.e., either intact or non-functional). For the given network configuration (i.e., evaluation of the connectivity between points A and B), the *BN* is solved within several minutes and the computations provide the updated posterior distributions of the probability of losing all connectivity (see Figure 21).

Figure 21 Posterior distribution of the performance of the road network, in terms of MLSs and connectivity between two points, estimated from field observations directly after the earthquake event.

In the end, the *BN* framework used in a rapid response context provides a probabilistic snapshot of the situation, and it may be continuously updated depending on observations that are gradually conveyed from the field. This information may then be exploited by crisis managers to decide where to engage resources and inspection efforts: such a task will help defining the recovery strategy, as discussed in the next sub-section.

6.3 Feeding incomplete information into the ABM of seismic recovery

The aforementioned *BN* approach provides a snapshot of the situation directly after the earthquake event, during the absorption phase: however, due the uncertainties involved, the information is of probabilistic nature, even though it can be gradually refined thanks to additional field observations. Such information cannot be directly used as input to the *ABM* for the identification of recovery strategies, since engaging repair operations on a bridge implies the gathering of detailed and verified information on the state of the potential damaged bridge. Therefore, an intermediate step is proposed,

where structural inspections on some bridges are conducted before planning repairs: due to limited resources, this step would also be sequential and subject to the accessibility of the bridges by the inspectors. As stated by Limongelli et al. (2019), even visual inspections may be useful to identify the damage state of a bridge and to support decisions on the bridge functionality (e.g., bridge immediately opened to traffic, or bridge closed before repair operations are engaged).

Based on the results of the inspections, a more deterministic picture of the situation may then be obtained, before planning the sequence of repairs with the *ABM*. However, a similar *ABM* may be applied to the inspection strategy, in order to optimize the inspection sequence (as shown in Figure 22). Several criteria are to be considered, such as the bridges with the highest probability of damage (information provided by the *BN* outcome), the accessibility of the bridge for inspection, or the criticality of the bridge with respect to the system performance. The latter criterion may be assessed through the betweenness centrality measure, as discussed in Chapter 4, which is easily computed for any type of networks. However, thanks to the *MLS* decomposition in the *BN*, it also becomes possible to directly identify the set of bridges which compose a given *MLS*, representing for instance the shortest route or the one that has the highest probability of being accessible. This criterion has the benefit of being more specific with respect to a given target (i.e., instead of a decomposition into *MLSs* prioritising a given $A \rightarrow B$ connectivity path, for instance, from damaged areas to the nearest hospital). The proposed framework is summarised in Figure 22, and it will be refined and investigated in Task 5.4 of this Work Package.

Figure 22 Proposed framework for the integration of the *BN* outcomes into the *ABM* strategies.

7 THE RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE OF CISS INCORPORATING THE EFFECT OF POTENTIAL AFTERSHOCK SEQUENCES

7.1 Introduction

The *Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences (ETAS)* seismicity model is used widely for short-term operational earthquake forecasting (*OEF*), in particular after a large event. This model will be implemented within the TURNkey platform for the purpose of developing an operational system for computing short-term seismicity forecasts. The *ETAS* model provides spatial earthquake occurrence for magnitude larger than a defined threshold for a specific forecasting time interval. The short-term forecasting time window can range from hours to weeks. The resultant short-term earthquake occurrence rate will be directly exploited within the seismic hazard assessment framework. In order to obtain short-term hazard values accounting for epistemic uncertainties, the resultant short-term seismicity rates from *ETAS* could be combined with non-seismic information, if available and relevant, in a logic tree framework. However, work reported in D3.4 concluded that the impact of the non-seismic branch is not influential to the final results (i.e., increase of hazard value in the short-term). As the main product of the *OEF* system, the short-term probabilities of exceedance from a threshold *PGA* are generated for a specific target region.

Iceland is recognized as a land of natural hazards and intense seismic and volcanic activity. The multiple monitoring networks of various geophysical markers and the availability of detailed earthquake catalogues complete down to small earthquake magnitudes make this testbed (i.e. TB3) an ideal test region in the TURNkey project for exploring the feasibility and limits of *OEF*. For this purpose, the June 2000 earthquake sequence that occurred in the South Iceland Seismic Zone (*SISZ*) has retrospectively been studied using the spatio-temporal *ETAS* model as a part of Deliverable 3.4. The short-term seismic hazard projections consider various source of uncertainties (e.g. ground motion models, aftershock zone, maximum magnitudes) for this sequence which is particularly useful for further investigation. The application of this approach and methodology to other seismic sequences in TB3 and/or seismic sequences in other Testbeds will be investigated to interact with the rapid response resilience framework, as discussed in Chapter 3.

7.2 Spatio-temporal *ETAS* model

The Bayesian-based spatio-temporal *ETAS* model proposed by Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017) has shown promising results in the case of the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence in central Italy, and it fits well the goal in the *TURNkey* project in terms of flexibility, quantifying uncertainty, and automatic updating of model parameters, and it is therefore selected for this work. One of the strong features of the approach is the robust presentation of seismicity forecasts that capture uncertainty not only in the parameter estimation for the sequence of events that occurred before the beginning of the forecasting interval, but also in the sequence of events that are expected to happen during the desired forecasting interval.

Figure 23 Schematic sketch of the seismicity forecasting framework using sequence-based Bayesian spatio-temporal ETAS model

Figure 23 indicates the schematic sketch of the sequence-based Bayesian spatio-temporal *ETAS* forecasting model which is discussed in Deliverable 3.4 in detail. The expected number of earthquakes (denoted as N) obtained by the *ETAS* model is calculated using **Error! Reference source not found.**. The first term, on the right hand side, is the background seismicity (N_b) which is usually considered time-independent. The second part is the triggering function which determines the rate of occurrence of events with potential of triggering offspring of its own during the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$ (denoted as λ in Eq. 6).

$$N(x, y, m | seq, M_l) = N_b(x, y, m | M_l) + \int_{\Omega_\theta} \left[\int_{\Omega_{seq_g}} \int_{T_{end}}^{T_{start}} \left(\lambda(t, x, y, m | seq_g, \theta, seq, M_l) dt \right) \cdot p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l) dseq_g \right] \cdot p(\theta | seq, M_l) d\theta \quad (6)$$

$N()$ is the expected number of events in the spatial cell unit (x,y) with $M \geq m$ in the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$ given the seq and lower cut-off magnitude M_l . seq is the observation history of events which have taken place in the time windows starting from the origin time of the main shock up to the beginning of the forecasting interval. θ is a vector representing the spatio-temporal *ETAS* model parameters (see Eq. 7). The *ETAS* model is applied to the most recent earthquake sequence to assess the possible increase in the seismicity rate for the next days/weeks. Therefore, the previous sequence can be added as a background seismicity and the beginning of the ongoing sequence will be re-defined when a new sequence starts. Note that M_l is defined as the magnitude completeness of the catalogue to which the *ETAS* model is applied. $p(\theta | seq, M_l)$ is the conditional probability distribution function (*PDF*) for θ given the seq and M_l . $p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l)$ is the *PDF* for the sequence of events generated within the forecasting interval (denoted as seq_g), given θ and seq (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

As indicated in Eq. 7, the spatio-temporal *ETAS* triggering function consists of three main functions as follows: 1) magnitude-dependent aftershock productivity associated with the Gutenberg-Richter relationship, 2) temporal decay of aftershocks which is defined by the Modified Omori's Law, 3) spatial decay of aftershocks relative to the epicenter of the parent event.

$$\lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m | \theta, seq_t, M_l) = e^{-\beta(m-M_l)} \sum_{t_j < t} K \cdot e^{\beta(M_j - M_l)} \cdot \frac{K_t}{(t - t_j + c)^p} \cdot \frac{K_R}{(r_j^2 + d^2)^q} \quad (7)$$

The *ETAS* model parameters are represented as the vector θ , whose components are $[\beta, c, p, d, q]$ as shown in Eq. 7. Note that K, K_t, K_R are defined as functions of θ . In order to generate samples of θ from the probability distribution of $p(\theta | seq, M_l)$, Markov Chain Monte Carlo (*MCMC*) simulation routine based on Metropolis-Hastings (*MH*) algorithm is employed. $p(\theta | seq, M_l)$ is computed using Bayesian approach and a lognormal distribution is considered as prior information for each of $[\beta, c, p, d, q]$ parameters with coefficient of variation (*CV*) of 0.3. To generate daily forecasts, the *ETAS* parameters are updated daily and their corresponding statistics, i.e. mean and *CV*, are reported on a daily basis. The first few samples during an initial transition time are often thrown away and after accumulating sufficient number of events, the model reflect samples from the $p(\theta | seq, M_l)$.

In order to generate a seq_g (i.e. ongoing aftershock sequence generated within the forecasting interval) given seq, M_l and the sampled values of θ , a stochastic procedure is adopted according to Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017). The probability distribution $p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l)$ is given by Eq. 8 as follows:

$$p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l) = \prod_i p(IAT_i, x_i, y_i, M_i | seq_{g_{i-1}}, \theta, seq, M_l) \quad (8)$$

Where $seq_g(i) = \{seq_g(i-1), (IAT_i, x_i, y_i, M_i)\}$ and $IAT_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$ stands for inter-arrival time for i th event and shows the time between two consecutive events occurred within seq_g .

Finally, robust estimate for the number of events with $M \geq m$ in a spatial cell centered at (x, y) within the aftershock zone considering the uncertainties in the spatio-temporal distribution of the sequence of events, denoted as $N(x, y, m | seq, M_l)$, can be determined from Eq. 6. For detailed information please refer to Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017).

7.3 Retrospective Study of the June 2000 Seismic Sequence Using a Bayesian Spatio-temporal *ETAS* model

The validation of the Bayesian *ETAS* model chosen, within the TURNkey project, is carried out through a retrospective forecasting experiment of recent strong seismic sequences in the *SISZ* in June 2000. Moreover, this study potentially improves our understanding of the space-time characterization of impending large earthquakes in the *SISZ* and ensure the feasibility of operational earthquake forecasting for this region. Details of this study are reported in deliverable 3.4.

At 15:40 on 17 June 2000 and at 00:51 on 21 June 2000, two largest events of *SISZ* caused by two parallel faults (see Figure 24 **Error! Reference source not found.**). The moment magnitudes of these

events are calculated Mw 6.4 and 6.5, respectively. Following the double large earthquakes, seismicity greatly increased in the whole southwestern Iceland, triggering 19000 microevents recorded by *SIL* network and activating 90 km of the plate boundary. The triggering was partially attributed to dynamic processes (Antonioli et al., 2006) but mostly static triggering. The mainshock was followed in a few tens of seconds by three other large events (Mw > 5.2) located as far away as 80 km (Árnadóttir 2004).

Figure 24 shows the 2000 earthquake sequence from 17 June 2000 up to 25 June 2000 with Mw > 2.0. Earthquakes are classified w.r.t their corresponding moment magnitude. The 17 June 2000 (Mw6.4) and 21 June 2000 (Mw6.5) large earthquakes are depicted by yellow stars. The active faults are plotted based on Einarsson (2014), Einarsson et al. (2020) and Steigerwald et al. (2020) shown by black lines. *SIL* stations are indicated by red triangles. The pink polygon (region) illustrates the Hveragerdi town, one of the two towns included in TB3, located within the highly seismic fracture zone of SISZ.

Figure 24 : Geographical distribution of the June 2000 earthquake sequence in SISZ and RPOR. Hveragerdi (TB3) is depicted by the pink polygon.

The validation of the model consists of generating daily spatial seismicity forecasts for the 2000 seismic sequence after the first day. Statistical tests are performed on the posterior distribution of the *ETAS* model parameters to assess their reliability, together with a sensitivity study of various influential input variables, such as available prior knowledge for the target region, number of posterior samples, number of Markov chains, and lower cut-off magnitude. The results are discussed in detail in deliverable 3.4.

In this section, in Figure 25, we display the spatial seismicity forecast map produced for earthquakes with magnitude 5.5 or larger for the 24-hour forecasting interval of 18 June 2000 (one day after the occurrence of the first large shock of the June 2000 seismic sequence) across the

aftershock zone (i.e., *SISZ* and *RPOR*). The predicted number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 4.5$, 5.5 and 6.5 for the interested time interval is calculated for all cell units with size of $0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$ enclosing the aftershock zone and their aggregation over the entire aftershock zone is presented in the bottom left side of the forecast map (see

Figure 25). Various confidence intervals of the estimated number of events, namely 2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th percentiles, are computed and summed over the surrounding circular area of approx. 20 km² around each cell. Then, the forecasted daily probabilities of one or more earthquakes equal to or greater than 5.5 per 20 km² is calculated using Eq. 9 to map the spatial distribution of the forecasted earthquake occurrence probability. Note that in this section, 98th percentile of the expected number of earthquakes is used to generate seismicity forecasts maps.

$$\Pr(M \geq m) = 1 - e^{-N(m|\text{seq}, M_l)} \quad (9)$$

As can be seen in Figure 25, the observed events during the target forecasting interval with $M_w \geq M_l$ (here $M_l=2$) are plotted by different symbols, as indicated in the legend. The right-hand side error-bar illustrates the forecasted number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ for the whole aftershock zone using the median value (within the grey-filled square) \pm one and two standard deviations, presenting the interval between 16th and 84th (black numbers) as well as 2nd and 98th percentiles (blue numbers), respectively. Also, to check the validity of the resultant forecasts, the number of observed earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ occurred during the desired forecasting interval within the entire aftershock zone is shown by red star.

Figure 25. Seismicity forecast map for earthquakes with $M_w \geq 5.5$ for the forecasting time window of 24-hour starting from 18 June 2000, 00:00 UTC across southwest-Iceland

7.4 Short-Term Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment for TB3

One of the scientific outputs of the *OEF* system is the short-term probability of ground shaking. The objective is to determine the increased seismic hazard in the *TB3* town (Hveragerdi) in south Iceland, by performing short-term hazard analysis using the forecasted number of earthquakes with different magnitudes that estimated spatially across the whole southwest Iceland and during a short-term forecasting time interval.

The daily probability of ground shaking with different intensities are generated for the center of the Hveragerdi town (*TB3*) using a selection of ground motion prediction equations (*GMPEs*), and computing the daily and annual exceedance rates using the conventional Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis (*PSHA*) framework. Also, their corresponding probability of exceedance are calculated using the Poisson distribution. It should be noted that to maintain consistency with other *TBs* and European countries, the parameters required for *PSHA* calculation are extracted from ESHM13 project (Woessner et al. 2015). Parenthetically we note that the hazard values obtained for south Iceland are preliminary and the fundamental inputs of ESHM13 for seismic hazard assessment in Iceland are currently under revision. Therefore, the results must be taken with caution as they need to be thoroughly validated.]

To track the time evolution of increased hazard during the 2000 seismic sequence, we determine the daily *PSHA* results for 7 days starting from 18 June 2000 (1 day after 17 June strong earthquake M6.4) until 24 June 2000 (3 days after the 21 June M6.5 event). For all cases, the forecasting time interval is 24 hours.

Figure 26 depicts the forecasted hazard curves for *PGA* thresholds calculated from individual *GMPEs* at Hveragerdi site in south Iceland (*TB3*). The hazard curves correspond to CY14 (Chiou and Youngs 2014), Z06 (Zhao et al. 2006) and Kea20 (Kowsari et al. 2020) *GMPEs* as well as depth of 10 km and maximum magnitude of 7.4. The daily rate of exceedance is displayed on the right panel and the daily probability of exceedance are depicted on the left panel. Red curves show the short-term hazard values, and the black curves indicate the conventional *PSHA* results. Note that to assess the short-term hazard curves, the daily forecasted seismicity (i.e. number of forecasted events occurred in a cell within the aftershock zone occurring during the specific time window) determined from the Bayesian spatiotemporal *ETAS* model are used. As can be seen in Figure 26 **Error! Reference source not found.**, the hazard curves illustrate significant increase in daily rate of exceedance compared to the conventional daily hazard curves across all intensity thresholds. The reason is on 17 June 2000, a strong earthquake with Mw6.4 along with large number of aftershocks were triggered.

It is well known that strong earthquakes are followed by intense aftershock activity. When the corresponding ground motions of the mainshocks are large enough, due to large earthquake magnitude and/or short epicentral distances, the exposed infrastructure may suffer damage. In those cases the systems in place to respond to such natural disasters become activated (e.g., search and rescue teams). Intense aftershock sequences that commence after a strong earthquake progressively add to the cumulative earthquake action on structures and systems and may cause progressive damage. The specification of short-term hazard (increase) and its uncertainty is useful to

progressively and quantifiably learn through repeated strong earthquake occurrences and their aftershocks how to optimally respond to such natural disasters.

Figure 26: Daily seismic hazard curves for PGA at Hveragerdi site (TB3) for forecasting interval of 18 June 2000.

8 CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE

This section of the report introduces alternative approaches that will be used in the TURNkey project to model the potential effect that the use of the TURNkey Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response (*FWCR*) platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.

Section 8.1 describes how Analytical Hierarchy Process (*AHP*) modelling will be used to analyse the potential impact of the TURNkey platform on critical infrastructure and community resilience. As outlined under 2.5, resilience will be modelled holistically and include factors that mark disaster preparedness, response and recovery. A hybrid model will be developed that includes both the engineering and socio-ecological aspects of resilience. The section starts with a general introduction that describes how this deliverable builds on the work carried out under D5.1. It then goes on to provide an overview of *AHP* modelling. It discusses a simplified form of *AHP*, called *AHP-express* as well as a network-based variant of *AHP* called Analytic Network Process (*ANP*). It describes how the degree of inconsistency in an *AHP* hierarchy can be measured. The section concludes with an overview as to how this approach will be applied.

Section 8.2 describes how System Dynamics (*SD*) modelling will be used to analyse disaster operations during the rapid recovery phase. As seen in section 2.4 and 2.5 a modelling method that includes such diverse factors as data, decisions, policy, within one dynamic system lends itself well to modelling multiple stakeholders with different objectives working towards the common goal of recovery following a destructive earthquake. Furthermore, the *SD* modelling process lends itself well to stakeholder interaction through mediated modelling. Mediated modelling helps to build consensus in small increments by finding common ground regarding the goal of the model, constructing a simulation model, and running scenarios to evaluate the desirability of the potential outcomes of various actions (Van den Belt, 2004). The *SD* modelling will involve a combination of desk and field-based studies within the two Icelandic sites of TURNkey in north and south Iceland, and interviews with the Icelandic TURNkey project partners. Chapter 8.2 outlines the key concepts of the *SD* methodology, how it will be adapted to a multi-stakeholder earthquake recovery process, the approach taken to modelling damage and behaviour, and finally, the anticipated application of the model.

8.1 Modelling the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquakes - methodological approach

As part of Deliverable D1.2, Jones (2020) has mapped the potential impacts that the earthquake early warning and operational earthquake forecasting tools, forming the basis of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform, could have on the range of resilience factors and indicators that are used in the majority of community resilience models currently employed across the world. Deliverable D5.1 (Jones et al. 2020b) extended the review work done by both Jones (2016, 2020) and Morga et al. (2020) to identify a range of performance metrics that could be used to assess the impact that the TURNkey *FWCR* platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events. In particular, Deliverable D5.1 (Jones et al. 2020b) sought to identify the logical links between the components of the *FWCR* platform (operational earthquake forecasting, earthquake early

warning, and rapid response to earthquakes) and earthquake resilience expressed in terms of the critical requirements derived from the end-user use cases developed in Deliverable D1.4 (Jones, 2020a) and to map these against a range of metrics derived from the latest resilience theory and toolkits (see Table 15, and Tables 17 to 22 in Deliverable D1.5 for details). Deliverable D5.1 concluded that resilience (business, critical infrastructure and community) is shaped by a combination of physical, organisational, operational, and governance factors and that the metrics contained in the UNDRR scorecards^{1,2} and REDi TM rating system³ could form the basis of models to assess the potential impacts of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform on business and community resilience to earthquake events. Deliverable D5.1 also concluded that, whilst none of the critical infrastructure resilience frameworks or metrics fully addressed the resilience issues associated with critical infrastructure organisations, an extension developed by Morga et al. (2020) in the LIQUEFACT project provided a good starting point to develop a new framework in the TURNkey project. Deliverable D5.2 will extend the work of D5.1 by considering how individual metrics can be aggregated within a framework model to obtain a measure of organisation, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events.

An initial (theoretical) mapping of United Nation Disaster Risk Reduction (*UNDRR*) scorecard against the *FWCR* platform can be found in Deliverable D5.1. This mapping will be validated during the participatory action research (currently underway in TURNkey Work Package 2) and this Deliverable. The decision to use the *UNDRR* scorecard as the basis for assessing community resilience to earthquake events is also consistent with the work of Burton et al. (2017) who developed and validated a scorecard methodology similar to the *UNDRR* Scorecard, and with the work of Morga et al. (2020) who customised the *UNDRR* scorecard for earthquake induced liquefaction disaster events in the LIQUEFACT project.

Building on these premises, the extensive review conducted in D5.1 for organisational resilience and the critical review of relevant literature relating to infrastructure resilience and community resilience models reported in section 2.5 of this document, this section will:

- discuss the role of the *AHP* as the basis for evaluating the potential impact that the TURNkey *FWCR* platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience;
- outline the data collection and modelling process that will be used to operationalise the *AHP* methodology in selected TURNkey testbeds;
- outline the next steps in the development of deliverable D5.2.

The work presented in this section should be considered as a work in progress which will be amended and modified throughout the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified through the participatory action research programme.

¹ Available at www.undrr.org/publication/disaster-resilience-scorecard-cities

² Available at www.preventionweb.net/files/69845_undrrbuildingscorecardfinalv1.3.pdf

³ Available at www.arup.com/perspectives/publications/research/section/redi-rating-system

8.1.1 Modelling Resilience to Earthquake Events using the AHP/ANP

Many authors (Alshehri et al., 2015, Bruneau et al., 2003; Cimellaro et al., 2010; Cutter et al., 2020; Dojutrek et al., 2016; Linkov et al., 2006; Orencio and Jujii, 2012; Morga et al. 2020; Prior, 2015; Xu et al., 2020; Zhong et al., 2020; have identified the need to apply multi-criteria methods that support the integration of both quantitative and qualitative data into integrated models of resilience to disaster events. Whilst the approaches adopted by each author vary, more recent studies (Xu et al. 2020; Zhong et al, 2020) have tended to develop hierarchical models of the system under consideration (in terms of the system factors) that affect resilience and then apply prioritisation techniques (e.g. the analytic hierarchy/network process) to evaluate the impact that changes to factors in the hierarchy have on system resilience.

The *AHP* (Saaty, 1990) is a method for resolving a complex decision-making problem into a hierarchy of a primary goal (community resilience) and component levels (e.g. the *UNDRR* Essentials) comprising sub-components (e.g. areas) and subjects/issues (metrics). Priorities are then established at the subject/issues, sub-component and component levels through pairwise comparison. By evaluating the impact that different potential solutions have on each metric the relative importance of the subject/issue can be calculated at the sub-component level; the importance of each sub-component can be calculated at the component level; and the importance of each component can be calculated against the primary goal. Saaty (1996) extended the AHP approach to accommodate a more complicated modelling arrangement in which a number of inter-related hierarchies co-exist within a system. To model these multiple hierarchies, and to account for feedback between the hierarchies Saaty (*ibid*) developed the analytic network process (*ANP*) (Saaty, 1996). The *ANP* follows the same principles as the *AHP* method.

The *AHP* and the *ANP* were developed by Thomas Saaty (1996) as a selection and prioritisation methodology which allows decision makers to evaluate the impact of alternate interventions on complex problems by evaluating individual impacts that interventions have at different levels in a hierarchy (Figure 27).

Figure 27 The Analytical Hierarchy Process

The *AHP* structures a system in terms of its goal; the criteria/sub-criteria (components and elements) layers represent the various objectives pertinent to that goal, expressed as children of the objectives, grandchildren of the objectives, great-grandchildren of the objectives etc; and the bottom layer of the hierarchy contains all the alternative approaches to the resolution of the problem.

Once the fundamental hierarchy has been established, the relative importance of the objectives in achieving the goal are determined through pair-wise comparisons. Each objective is compared against the others in the objective layer to determine each objective's importance in achieving the goal (e.g. the relative importance of $C_1, C_2 \dots C_n$ in achieving the primary goal; the relative importance of $C_{11}, C_{12}, \dots C_{1n}$ in achieving objective C_1). Comparisons are repeated in this way for every layer of the hierarchy.

Comparisons are made using a 1-9 numeric scale that translates qualitative statements into numeric scores (Table 3) expressed as a priority vector.

Table 3 pairwise comparison scoring system (source: Saaty, 2006)

Qualitative Statement	Numeric score
Equal importance	1
Moderate importance of one over another	3
Strong essential importance	5
Very strong or demonstrated importance	7
Extreme importance	9
Intermediate values	2, 4, 6, 8
Use of reciprocal is for inverse comparisons	

The calculation of the priority vector for a typical 3 criteria model is demonstrated in Saaty (1996) and repeated here.

Firstly, we need to establish the relative importance of the 3 criteria to each other. In this example, criteria C2 is considered to be between equally and moderately more important than criteria C1 so a numeric score of 2 is assigned. Criteria C3 is considered to be between moderately and strongly more important than criteria C1 so a numeric score of 4 is assigned. Criteria C3 is considered to be between equally and moderately more important than criteria C2 so a score of 2 is assigned (Table 4).

Table 4 Priority scores

	C1	C2	C3
C1	1	1/2	1/4
C2	2	1	1/2
C3	4	2	1
Column Total	7	3.5	1.75

The priority scores are normalised by dividing each entry in each column by the sum of the entries in the column. The overall relative priorities across the three criteria are calculated by summing the scores in each row and dividing by the number entries in each row Table 5.

Table 5 Normalised matrix and priority score

	C1	C2	C3	Priority Vector
C1	0.1428	0.1428	0.1428	0.1428
C2	0.2857	0.2857	0.2857	0.2857
C3	0.5714	0.5714	0.5714	0.5714

In this example, because all the pairwise comparisons used to construct the priority matrix are internally consistent, we can conclude that the C1 accounts for 14.28% of the final goal, C2 accounts for 28.57% of the final goal and C3 accounts for 57.14% of the final goal.

However, internal consistency cannot always be guaranteed so Saaty (1996) provides a mechanism to check the level of inconsistency within any set of pairwise comparisons.

When the matrix is consistent the sum of entries in each row provides a measure of the dominance of one element over the other's in achieving the goal and the sum of the entries in each column tells us how much one element is dominated by the others. For consistent matrices the elements in the columns should be the reciprocal of the elements in the rows; and both should be equal to 1.0. Further, the product of the column sums and normalised row sums should equal n (the number of entities). However, when the matrices are inconsistent these relationships do not hold. If the matrices are inconsistent then the product sum is greater than 1.0 and dividing the difference by n gives us a measure of the inconsistency.

Saaty (1996) presents a numeric methodology for calculating the level of inconsistency by raising the judgement matrix by large powers (e.g. by squaring it, then squaring it again etc) and calculating the normalised vector until the point at which the difference between iterations is within acceptable

accuracy limits. At which point the normalised vector represents the principal eigenvector of the matrix whose associated eigenvalue λ_{max} can be used to calculate inconsistency of judgements.

Repeating the previous example (again extracted from Saaty, 1996) for an inconsistent matrix (Tables 7 and 8) gives

Table 6 Inconsistent judgment matrix

	C1	C2	C3
C1	1	1/2	1/4
C2	2	1	1/4
C3	4	4	1
Column Total	7	5.5	1.5

Table 7 Normalised matrix and priority score

	C1	C2	C3	Priority Vector (PV)
C1	0.1429	0.0909	0.1667	0.1334
C2	0.2857	0.1818	0.1667	0.2114
C3	0.5714	0.7273	0.6667	0.6551

As can be seen by comparing Table 5 and Table 7 the priority vector has changed.

We can compare the degree of change to that would be expected if the judgements were all randomly generated by multiplying the first column of the inconsistent judgement matrix (Table 6) by the relative priority of C1 (0.1334), multiplying the 2nd column by the relative priority of C2 (0.2114), and the 3rd column by the relative priority of C3 (0.6551) and summing the entities in each row (Table 8).

Table 8 Totalling the entries

	C1	C2	C3	Row Totals
C1	0.1334	0.1057	0.1638	0.4029
C2	0.2668	0.2114	0.1638	0.642
C3	0.5336	0.8456	0.6551	2.034

If we now divide the column of row totals (Table 8) by the corresponding entry in the priority vector (Table 7) and average the entries in the final column (Table 9) we get an approximation of $\lambda_{max} = 3.054$.

Table 9 Determining λ_{max}

Row Total (RT)	Priority Vector (PV)	RT/PV
0.4029	0.1334	3.0202
0.642	0.2114	3.0369
2.034	0.6551	3.1049

The consistency index (CI) where the $n = 3$ can then be calculated by $(\lambda_{max} - n)/n-1 = (3.054 - 3)/2 = 0.027$ which can be compared with the random value of CI for $n=3$ of 0.52 (obtained by Saaty from a sample of 500 matrices) to obtain the consistency ratio $(0.027/0.52) = 0.052$ which is better than the 10% normal accepted limit.

Finally, a sensitivity analysis should be carried out by varying the priorities of each criterion to determine their influence on the goal and stability of the decision to be tested.

Whilst *AHP* has many advantages, including its ability to measure both tangible and intangible criteria (Saaty & Sagir, 2009), to measure the consistency and stability of a decision, to be used alongside other processes such as goal programming (Sarkis and Sundarraj, 2006) it also has a number of weaknesses including:

- the possibility of rank reversal;
- it is an additive complete aggregation tool which can allow good scores to compensate for bad scores;
- as the hierarchy is made up of objectives and various levels of sub-objectives the amount of pairwise decisions to be made can be quite extensive, and
- the process can become quite time consuming (Macharis et al, 2004);
- the 9-point scale can be problematic as a decision maker may not be able to determine the difference between the values during the pairwise process. Hajkowicz et al., (2000) reduced the 9 point scale to a 3 point scale to overcome this problem, requiring the decision maker to determine if one criterion was more, less or equal important than the other.

AHP/ANP forms the basis of the software tools, Expert Choice, TransparentChoice, SpiceLogic and SuperDecisions These tools are widely used in strategic planning and risk management, e.g. in asset management, homeland security, infrastructure and technology. In this project, we will examine the suitability of this software for TURNkey.

8.1.2 AHP-express

AHP-express (Leal, J. E., 2020) is a simplified version of the analytical hierarchy process method, described in the previous section. As outlined, *AHP* is a powerful multicriteria decision making tool, however it requires a very large number of comparisons in order to make a decision. The benefit of *AHP-express* is that it requires fewer comparisons for each criterion or between criteria. The simplified *AHP-express* method is based on the following assumptions: 1) evaluation consistency; 2) inconsistency occurs primarily in evaluations between alternatives that are seemingly of minor importance to the decision maker. As a result, criteria of lower importance to the decision maker are not compared against each other, on the understanding that decision makers are less likely to hold carefully considered views on seemingly unimportant matters. Therefore, *AHP-express* calculates the priorities of each alternative against a set of criteria with only $(n-1)$ comparisons of n alternatives for each criterion, compared to $(n^2-n)/2$ comparisons required in the original method. This saves time and reduces inconsistency. This approach can also be applied to the pairwise comparisons used in the analytical network process (*ANP*), described below.

The *AHP-express* method consists of the steps outlined below (Leal, J. E., 2020):

1. Determine the main goal (or primary objective) of the decision-making process. This is placed on top of a hierarchy, which takes the form of an upside-down tree.

2. Define secondary objectives (or partial objectives). They are placed at the second level and jointly meet the main goal.
3. If necessary, define third level objectives (partial objectives) that jointly meet their corresponding secondary objective.
4. Starting at the lowest level, all alternatives are compared pairwise, see Table 3.
5. For each pair of elements in a level, the following should be done:
 - i. Determine which element is more important to the corresponding (partial) objective at the next level.
 - ii. Apply the formula in Eq. 10 to calculate the elements of the vector of priorities for the criterion under consideration.
6. Going up the tree towards the main goal, calculate the priorities for each alternative for each corresponding criterion.

$$pr_j = \frac{1}{a_{ij} * \sum_k 1/a_{ik}} \quad (10)$$

Where

j = the element for which one wishes to calculate the priority

i = the element taken as the basis for the comparison

a_{ij} = the comparison value of alternative i with alternative j

pr_j = the priority of alternative j against the criterion considered

8.1.3 The Analytical Network Process (ANP)

Saaty (2006) developed the *Analytic Network Process (ANP)* as a generalised version of *AHP* to accommodate the modelling of complex problems where interaction and interdependency are better described in an influence network of clusters and nodes rather than a simple one-dimensional hierarchy of criteria. By adopting a multi-dimensional approach, *ANP* not only considers the relative importance of criteria to determine the impact that alternative solutions can have on achieving the goal, but also models the interaction between alternatives allowing for feedback to support future (as opposed to present) goals.

Whilst *ANP* uses the same basic pairwise comparison for establishing priorities between criteria, it is not structured as a top-to bottom hierarchy but as an interconnected network of clusters of elements where elements in one cluster are connected to elements in another cluster (outer dependence) or to elements in the same cluster (inner dependence). Outer dependence describes the influence that elements in one cluster have on elements in another cluster with respect to a control criterion (note: control criterion are multiple outcomes from the model, e.g. improved resilience to earthquake events). Inner dependence describes the influence of elements within a cluster on each

other. By considering outer and inner dependency ANP allows us to reflect the views of different stakeholders and to model the interdependency between them (Figure 28)

Figure 28 Feedback network with components having inner and outer dependences among their elements.

Source: Saaty, 2006

In relation to Figure 28, the arrows between *clusters* indicates the outer dependence of elements in C_i on the elements in C_j with respect to a common property; while the loop-in a *cluster* indicates inner dependence of the elements in that *cluster* with respect to a common property. By way of comparison, a hierarchy can be considered as a one-directional network in which the levels in the hierarchy correspond to the clusters in a network

The process of decision making requires us to analyse a decision according to its *benefits*, *opportunities*, *costs* and *risks*. *Benefits* (B) are the positive outcomes that would result from taking the decision; *Opportunities* (O) are the potentially positive outcomes that can result in the future from taking the decision; *Costs* (C) are the negative outgoings that would result from taking the decision; and *Risks* (R) are the potential negative outgoings that can result from taking the decision. The *BOCR* are known as the ‘four merits’.

In developing an ANP model the pairwise comparison matrices are entered into a super matrix in which steady-state priorities are sought (note: in complex problems not all super matrices will converge). Whilst ANP modelling is inherently complicated and mathematically demanding, software solutions have been developed (e.g. <http://www.superdecisions.com/>) to guide the user through the modelling process. In addition, Saaty (2006) identified 12 steps to develop an ANP model. These are:

1. Describe the decision problems objectives, criteria/sub criteria, actors and their objectives and possible outcomes. Give details of influences that determine how that decision is made.
2. Determine the control criteria/sub criteria in the 4 decision control hierarchies (benefits, opportunities, costs and risks) of the decision and obtain priorities from paired comparison matrices.
3. Determine the most general network of clusters (or components) and their elements that apply to all control criteria.

4. For each control criterion/sub criterion, determine the clusters of the general feedback system with their elements and connect them according to their outer and inner dependence influences.
5. Determine the approach to follow in the analysis of each cluster or element, influencing other clusters and elements with respect to a criterion, or being influenced by other clusters and elements.
6. For each control criterion, construct a super matrix.
7. Perform pairwise comparisons on the elements within the clusters themselves according to their influence on each element in another cluster they are connected to (outer dependence) or on elements in their own cluster (inner dependence).
8. Perform pairwise comparisons on the clusters as they influence each cluster to which they are connected with respect to the given control criterion.
9. Compute the limit priorities of the stochastic super matrix according to whether it is irreducible or reducible.
10. Synthesise the limiting priorities by weighting each idealised limit vector by the weight of each control criterion and adding the resulting vectors for each of the 4 control criteria (the benefits, opportunities, costs and risks, i.e. the 4 *BOCR* merits).
11. Determine strategic criteria and their priorities to rate the 4 *BOCR* merits one at a time. Normalise the 4 ratings and use them to calculate the overall synthesis by subtracting the costs and risks from the sum of the benefits and opportunities.
12. Perform a sensitivity analysis on the final outcome.

8.1.4 Inconsistency in AHP pairwise comparisons

Inconsistency is one of the fundamental problems encountered by those using *AHP* pairwise comparisons in decision-making. Inconsistency occurs when the internal mathematical logic linking the relative importance of one criterion to another fails. By way of example, consider that you are comparing 3 criteria (A, B and C). Suppose you answer (using Saaty's 9 point judgement scale) that A is 3B (i.e. A is moderately more important than B) and that B is 2C (i.e. B is slightly less than moderately more important than C). Using mathematical logic then A must = 6C (i.e. A is between strongly and very strongly more important than C). The problem is in *AHP* we don't ask people to use mathematical logic but to use qualitative statements that are then converted using Saaty's 9-point judgement scale. This approach inevitably introduces the risk of inconsistency, either because:

- people by nature make inconsistent judgements;
- people don't have enough information to make consistent judgements;
- the use of Saaty's discrete scale doesn't provide a consistent direct numerical comparison either because there is no direct comparison score in the scale (e.g. suppose you score $A=2B$ and $A=3C$ then for consistency $B=1.5C$ but we do not have a 1.5 numeric score on Saaty's scale) or

because the logic numeric score greater than that allowed on the scale (e.g. suppose you score $A=3B$ and $B=4C$ for consistency $A=12C$ but we do not have a 12 numeric score on Saaty's scale).

Whilst the problem of inconsistency is well known; so are the steps that can be taken to reduce inconsistency within an *AHP* model. The following guidance is provided by Opydo (2020) for reducing inconsistency:

- keep the number of components in any branch/level of the hierarchy to as few as possible, and always less than 9;
- don't compare components that exhibit large differences in priority (if one or more components dominate the branch/level of the hierarchy then they are probably in the wrong level;
- when eliciting qualitative scores from people, encourage them to use the lower end of Saaty's scale. The elicitation of pairwise comparisons requires a degree of expertise and practice on behalf of the facilitator;
- avoid obvious contradictions in pairwise comparisons by using such contradictions to explore the underlying relationships upon which people are basing their judgements (i.e. question the logic of their qualitative scoring).

It is worth noting that inconsistency in itself is not a problem; but the degree of inconsistency can be. In real world situations some level of inconsistency is to be expected (in fact a perfectly consistent *AHP* model should raise concerns about its validity amongst researchers/users).

As described above, the degree of inconsistency in an *AHP* hierarchy can be measured by its consistency ratio. Saaty (1990) developed a methodology for comparing the level of inconsistency within an *AHP* model to that which would be expected from a randomly generated model having the same number of components. Saaty (1990) suggested that a consistency ratio of less than 10% should be acceptable for the majority of applications.

As outlined, the *AHP* approach described in this section will be used to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform on community resilience. The initial theoretical mapping of the *UNDRR* scorecard against the platform presented in D5.1 constitutes the foundation of this work. The model will be built using *AHP* modelling software, such as that provided by TransparentChoice, SuperDecisions, SpiceLogic and ExpertChoice. The models will be applied in TURNkey Test Bed 3, e.g. the municipalities Hveragerði and Husavik in Iceland, and inform the further development of the TURNkey platform and decision-making toolbox.

8.2 Roadmap to Engineering Community Resilience

An adaptive and resilient urban system requires that the affected population, the municipality, the repair stakeholders, and the infrastructure operators be aware of each other's needs and activities, monitor a joint recovery timeline, and decide their actions in a coordinated manner towards a common goal. This study will conclude with recommendations of coordination procedures for all the stakeholders in the study, to enable them to be a part of a resilient integrated response system, which can be supported by the *FWCR* TURNkey platform.

8.2.1 Application of System Dynamics to the Recovery Process

It is proposed to apply the system Dynamics approach to the recovery process past an earthquake damaging event. Test Bed 3 consisting of two sites in South and North Iceland, is chosen for this application.

The full gamut of stakeholders considered in the proposed recovery model are those in the repair chain of residential buildings, in the repair chain of the infrastructure services to residential buildings, and those who provide relief services. Table 10 summarises the principal stakeholders and their roles in the process of post-earthquake repair.

Table 10 : Stakeholder and their role in the process of household repairs post-earthquake

Stakeholder	Role
Civil Protection	Assess that people don't live in dangerous buildings, and don't evacuate safe buildings With Welfare Department provides the household with temporary support (relief)
Building owners	Report damage to their insurance company, Receive insurance pay out Hire design engineer for design repair Hire contractor to implement repairs Moves back into repaired and functioning home
Insurance companies	Refer claim to National Catastrophe Fund, Receive payments terms from National Catastrophe Fund, Disburse payment to building owners
Structural/seismic engineer	Design repairs and applies for repair permits to Building and Safety Department
Services infrastructure companies	Restore services to repaired houses

In regard to the infrastructure companies, the two different testbed areas in Iceland (north and south) are serviced by different companies. Further investigation of these companies will determine whether it is of value to model both.

The list of stakeholders includes two municipality departments, the Building and Safety Department and the Welfare Department. Their staff members work according to existing rules and guidelines. The local government has the mandate to implement policies and change rules and guidelines in order to better support homeowners. Therefore, the local government, i.e. the town council, is an additional stakeholder to the process.

In the modelling process the stakeholders will be characterized as Management Systems. A management system is defined by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO 2013) as the objectives and procedures a stakeholder uses to reach its goal. Therefore, part of the research work for this Deliverable is to outline the overall goals, objectives and procedures for each stakeholder, both for normal day-to-day procedures, and procedures, if any, to use after a damaging earthquake.

An initial draft of a Causal Loop Diagram (*CLD*) for the recovery process is presented in Figure 29. This *CLD* addresses damaged buildings and the stakeholders required to repair them. It does not take into account cascading damage or damage to infrastructure, which will be added in later work.

The *CLD* consists of two connected balancing loops. The first (B1) addresses the number of buildings damaged and stakeholder activities and reads as follows: An earthquake produces damage to buildings, the bigger the earthquake the more buildings are damaged; Increased number of damaged buildings leads to increased number of insurance claims, leading to increased number of engineer projects, which leads to an increased number of building repair permits, which lead to an increased requirement of repair crews, which leads to increased number of repaired buildings, which decreases the number of damaged buildings.

From this loop the recovery time can be estimated through the insurance process delays, the time it takes to acquire a design engineer, building permit processing delays and the time it takes to get a repair crew.

The second balancing loop (B2) centres around the recovery timeline and municipality budget expenditure, and reads as follows: The longer the recovery, the longer the relief time will be due to households being evacuated from their homes; This leads to additional relief cost and increased budget spending; Increased budget spending allows for more staff to be hired, more available staff can be used to reduce the delay of the building permit process, which will reduce the recovery time.

A key aspect of the *CLD* is the accumulated delay. Each of the stakeholders has a process to implement their work if approached by a single homeowner whose home has been damaged. Each has a capacity to process one (or a few) such requests in a known amount of time, i.e. their normal processing rate. Under normal circumstances there is a balance between the demand of repair and the supply of Design Engineers and Contractors. This means that in normal circumstances, if your home is damaged, you are not likely to acquire these resources instantly, there will be some wait, and it can be estimated. The question here is how much longer the wait becomes when many of your neighbours are requiring the services of these resources at the same time. When many homeowners request service at the same or similar time a queue develops around the service providers and the homeowners need to wait for their request to be processed, i.e. the processing rate increases, in some cases to an unknown level. The second key aspect in the *CLD* is expenditure (relief cost, additional staff) and financial gain (shortening relief time) for the municipality if they implement a policy to shorten the delays. The question is therefore how to balance between time and expenditure.

Figure 29 Causal Loop Diagram for a Recovery Process

8.2.2 Modelling Aspects

8.2.2.1 Modelling of Damages due to Seismic Activity

Damage data activates the SD model. The model is activated by a step-function with information about damaged buildings from the TURNkey platform. Three domains of damage will be modelled: the damage to residential buildings, cascading building damage due to fire and water-system flooding triggered by the seismic event, and damage to infrastructure systems. It is assumed that either the TURNkey platform will provide this information, or it is collected through field assessments and telecommunication.

In regard to residential buildings damage, this will be estimated based on vulnerability data developed from Icelandic earthquake data. In the summer of 2000, two significant earthquakes hit the South-Iceland Lowland causing considerable damage. A severe earthquake hit the South-Lowland in Iceland at 15:41 local time (GMT) on 17 June 2000, the National Independence Day of Iceland. Another damaging earthquake occurred three and a half days later, on 21 June at 00:47 local time, 17 km west of the first earthquake. The June 17 earthquake had a moment Magnitude $M_w=6.5$, the

hypocentre was at 6.3 km depth, and occurred on an 18 km long fault; The June 21 earthquake also had a moment Magnitude $M_w=6.5$, the hypocentre was located at 5.1 km depth, and occurred on a 16 km long fault (Sigbjornsson 2001, Thorarinsson et al. 2001), (see chapter 7 for more details).

Based on recordings from the Iceland Strong Ground Motion Network, maintained by the Earthquake Engineering Research Institute of the University of Iceland in Selfoss, the highest recorded peak ground acceleration recorded on June 17 was 65% g and on June 21 was 84% g (Thorarinsson et al. 2001). The majority of structures experienced below 47% g. Despite the fact that none of the buildings collapsed in the earthquake sequence, a significant amount of structural and non-structural damage was reported to, and reimbursed by, the Icelandic Catastrophe Insurance Agency.

The Icelandic Catastrophe Insurance database is the basis for the Damage Probability Matrix (*DPMs*) used in this study. There are *DPMs* available for the Iceland testbeds developed from the 2000, 2008 and joint 2000 and 2008 datasets. The first *DPMs* to be produced from the 2000 dataset were produced in the EU FORESIGHT project (Thorvaldssdottir 2006). An example of *DPMs* in FORESIGHT for Single Family Dwellings for brick, concrete and timber is presented in Figure 30. Recent work produced by Bessason et al. (2020) produced fragility curves based on a new vulnerability model for the three building types, as shown in Figure 31. Damage Ratio information from Bessason et al. is presented in Figure 32. The definition of the Damage States (*DS*) used by Bessason et al. (2020) are:

- DS0 – minor, loss less than 1% of replacement value,
- DS1 – slight, loss less than 1-5 % of replacement value,
- DS2 – moderate, loss less than 5-20 % of replacement value,
- DS3 – substantial, loss less than 20-50% of replacement value

9.0 MATERIAL by PGA (3864 Total buildings)

DPM 9.1: Brick, Single Family Dwellings 429 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	92,5	86,4	41,0
2-slight	0-1	0.5	0,0	2,3	1,6
3-light	1-10	5	6,0	7,0	27,9
4-moderate	10-30	20	1,5	2,0	11,5
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,0	1,3	4,9
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,0	1,0	13,1

DPM 9.2: Concrete, Single Family Dwellings 1914 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	93,8	90,7	43,1
2-slight	0-1	0.5	1,5	2,0	3,4
3-light	1-10	5	3,7	6,6	38,4
4-moderate	10-30	20	0,5	0,7	8,8
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,2	0,0	3,7
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,2	0,1	2,7

DPM 9.3: Wood, Single Family Dwellings 1521 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	93,6	96,4	63,7
2-slight	0-1	0.5	1,1	0,5	6,0
3-light	1-10	5	4,5	2,0	20,7
4-moderate	10-30	20	0,0	0,9	6,0
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,4	0,2	2,0
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,4	0,0	1,6

Figure 30 Example of DPM from FORESIGHT Project

Detailed exposure data in the north and south testbeds is available within the TURNkey project. While the *DPMs* are all constructed from the damage data in recent South Iceland earthquakes, the construction and design of buildings are similar in the north and south and the *DPMs* easily apply to the north of Iceland.

Figure 31 Fragility curves from Bessason et al. (2020)

Figure 32 Damage Ratio information (Bessason et al. 2020)

8.2.2.2 Model Formulation, Testing and Implementation

The model building process is divided into formulation, testing and implementation. Formulation is converting the stock and flow diagrams to level and rate equations through System Dynamics software, determining initial conditions, and determining Behaviour Over Time Graphs (BOTG, or reference modes). The BOTG within TURNkey will be developed with TURNkey stakeholders in the Test Bed 3. The formulation will take into account accumulation of items which cause delays, such as building permits, insurance claims and lack of resources.

Testing involves testing the model's assumptions, the model behaviour and sensitivity to perturbations. Each variable will be tested to determine whether it behaves as expected, and thus ensure that the model is correctly set up. It is considered good practice to build simple components of a model and then make sure the model runs as intended before adding more components to it, thus building the model in stages.

Implementation tests the model's response to different policies. This allows the analyst to translate study's insights into an accessible format that can be communicated to the stakeholders.

8.2.3 Exploitation of the System Dynamic Model

The following are the expected outcomes from the model and how a municipality can use the results for immediate and long-term recovery planning.

8.2.3.1 Using CLD for Overview Planning

Even before the earthquake, the municipality can use the CLD to provide its staff with an understanding of which issues could become obstacles during the recovery. By studying the CLD the municipality has a guide of which issues to monitor during the recovery period and can investigate prior to the earthquake how to address them to possibly improve the recovery process. For example, the municipality can identify from it the main stakeholders, where delays might be created, and the importance of monitoring relief cost in association with the recovery duration. Even if the CLD is not used before the earthquake, it is still of value after the earthquake.

8.2.3.2 Using TURNkey Platform Results for Recovery Planning

In real life information about damaged buildings does not come in at once, i.e. it is not a step function, but is collected via field assessments, and telecommunication. One of the goals of this study is to find out how much faster the stakeholders get an idea of the magnitude of the problem they are facing through the TURNkey platform versus conventional ways. This question will be addressed in further work in WP5.2.

The TURNkey platform will provide information about the damage ratio and the number of buildings in each Damage State. The damage ratio provides the municipality with a scope of the damage. For example, the damage ratio is an indication how many insurance claims there are likely to be and how many subsequent building-permits they will need to process. Having prior information about how process rates of the building-permits will allow the Building and Safety Department to

estimate its backlog, plan their activities, set up a monitoring scheme and call for extra resources in advance of serious delays.

Information of how many buildings are in each Damage State is an indication of the relief needs because buildings with minor damage are not likely to be evacuated and relief support not required. This information can be used by the Welfare department to estimate their workload, plan their activities, set up a monitoring scheme, and call for extra resources in advance of serious delays.

8.2.3.3 *Using Policy Analysis for short and long-term planning*

The results from the SD model will include graphs of the recovery timeline. The study will analyse the effect of various policies implemented, or initiated, by the municipality on the recovery timeline. The study will investigate where leverage points can be found in the model and how to use them to increase the quality of the recovery process, thus increasing the resiliency.

The policies to be studied will include the following, listed below in the order of appearance in the CLD, other policies may be identified during the modelling process:

- Policy 1: Increasing insurance assistance rate.
- Policy 2: Increasing availability of engineers.
- Policy 3: Increasing repair permit processing rate.
- Policy 4: Increasing availability of repair crews.
- Policy 5: Decreasing relief cost.
- Policy 6: Decreasing recovery cost.
- Policy 7: Increasing the response capacity of the fire department
- Policy 8: Reducing delays through coordinating infrastructure operators' activities.

8.3 Conclusions

Considering “building resilience” to disasters as a roadmap to sustainability, as suggested by Cutter (2013), a roadmap is required to guide the engineering (i.e., design,) of building resilience. A roadmap for Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems is based on the collective perspectives and relationships of all societal sectors. The relationships between all these actors are complicated and complex. Any model of their relationships in a roadmap will be a simplification of real life. The TURNkey project works with two community level models in order to provide sound suggestions on what to include in the TURNkey platform for a community resilience perspective.

Whereas the Analytical Hierarchy Process model will analyse the potential impact of the TURNkey platform on community resilience holistically, the System Dynamics model will zoom in on the role of disaster operations during the rapid recovery phase. Both approaches will inform the design of decision support systems and tools aimed at guiding earthquake risk/resilience management within TURNkey – and enable the evaluation of the platform's impact, both holistically and specifically in the context of *RRE*.

9 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Seismic resilience of modern CISs is strategically critical to the health of modern civilized communities under earthquake hazards. Nevertheless, field observations on real-world seismic events have repeatedly demonstrated that the scant resilience of CISs springs from their inherent physical vulnerabilities, and the interdependence among them.

The *Task 5.2* objective is the development of an adaptive and inclusive modelling framework for the rapid response-based recovery and resilience of Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems (CICSS) exposed to seismic hazards. The strong interaction between the physical resilience and recovery of the critical infrastructure systems and the socio-economic resilience and recovery of the community is recognised and set at the centre of the modelling framework. Both aspects and their reciprocal influences are considered in the time and knowledge domains which are also interdependent.

By *Rapid Response (RR)*, within the TURNkey project, it is intended, the collective sum of actions that authorities in charge of disaster management need to deploy, rapidly and efficiently, in the immediate aftermath of the main shock, on the basis of a partial, qualitative and emotionally-biased knowledge of the rapidly evolving situation in the field. *RR* relies heavily on the near-real-time estimates of the earthquake location and characteristics (e.g. magnitude), and the knowledge of the exposed assets and their vulnerabilities, to estimate the potential losses and the areas most affected by the event.

Of particular relevance to the applicability of the modelling framework developed within Task 5.2, is the time dependent status of the CISs considered and the time dependent quality and quantity of information relating to such status, which is usually increasing and changing in nature as time elapses from the disruptive event, but can also be affected by secondary events as time progresses, overlapping the immediate response and recovery phases. The application to the Test Beds is central to the modelling and informs it, so that outputs and outcomes are of immediate relevance and benefit to the stakeholders engaged in the TURNkey project. Given the resources within the Test Beds and their configuration, the study focuses on transport networks, specifically, road networks and ports, and the networked emergency health facilities, for what concern the rapid response of physical critical infrastructure to earthquake sequence. The rapid response of the community is studied, by looking at the process of residential recovery and the demands on the recovered status of critical infrastructure for such recovery to take place. The strategy and modelling choices to represent such phenomena can be articulated as follows:

1. A Hierarchical Agent Based Model is chosen to represent the dynamics of the damage and the short-term recovery of RN considering alternative repair strategies. This is implemented to a regional and an urban road network.
2. The effects of traffic disruption on Emergency health services is studied within the urban environment considering the two networks as different agents in the AB model and a third agent is represented by an administrator which coordinates the response choices of the two infrastructure systems.

3. To address the issue of limited knowledge on the status of damage of specific components in the immediate aftermath of the earthquake and how this affects decision for the *Rapid Response* strategy, an inspection phase is introduced, simulated with the ABM, and the outcome of the ABM model in terms of the status of specific bridges is used as input of a BN that can then describe and updated state of accessibility of the network. This in turn becomes input to a second ABM which selects best repair and recovery strategy.
4. Bayesian spatiotemporal *ETAS* model are used to modelled the forecasting of aftershocks in the rapid response period and hence use the foreseen event sequence as input to determine the state of accessibility of the network during the recovery. This modelling will provide updated GMPE and daily PGA probability of exceedance that can be used as input in the ABM and BN rapid response simulations of the network to determine their updated state in time.
5. Finally a System Dynamic Model is used to determine the Behaviour Over Time Graphs for the Community recovery process, as influenced by a number of sociotechnical constraints that determine its dynamic behaviour. This will allow to describe the Dynamic Stakeholder Response (DSR), as it affects and is affected by the Physical Resilience models described above. By identifying through this process hurdles and opportunities, policies for planning and decision making can be identified and tested.

The outcome from this initial methodological scoping and its applications to Test Beds 1 2, 3 and 5 will provide input to the *DSS* and the *FWCR*.

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D 5.2

(PHASE 2)

Report on recommendations on Community Resilience and Recovery Models

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ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
<i>ABM</i>	Agent Based Model
<i>AHP</i>	Analytical Hierarchy Process
<i>ANP</i>	Analytical Network Process
<i>BN</i>	Bayesian Networks
<i>BOCR</i>	Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, Risks
<i>BOTG</i>	Behaviour Over Time Graph
<i>CIS</i>	Critical Infrastructure System
<i>CICS</i>	Critical Infrastructure-Community System
<i>CLD</i>	Causal Loop Diagram
<i>DPM</i>	Damage Probability Matrix
<i>DSS</i>	Decision Support Systems
<i>ETAS</i>	Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences
<i>EIL</i>	Earthquake Induced Liquefaction
<i>EPSS</i>	Electric Power Supply System
<i>FL</i>	Functionality Loss
<i>FR</i>	Functional Recovery
<i>FWCR</i>	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response
<i>GFL</i>	Gross Functionality Losses

<i>GMPEs</i>	Ground Motion Prediction Equations
<i>HABM</i>	Hierarchical Agent-Based Model
<i>IAoE</i>	Immediate Aftermath of Earthquake
<i>MLS</i>	Minimum Link Set
<i>OEF</i>	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
<i>PSHA</i>	Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis
<i>RN</i>	Road Network
<i>RR</i>	Rapid Response
<i>RRE</i>	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
<i>SD</i>	System Dynamics
<i>SDA</i>	System Dynamic Assessment
<i>SFD</i>	Stock and Flow Diagram
<i>SISZ</i>	South Iceland Seismic Zone
<i>TB</i>	Test Beds
<i>UNDRR</i>	United Nation Disaster Risk Reduction
<i>WCDR</i>	World Conference on Disaster Reduction

10 INTRODUCTION

10.1 Concept

Modus operandi of modern Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems (*CICSs*) are underpinned by a host of Critical Infrastructure Systems (*CISs*) that have been cybernetically engineered and networked, to ensure the best, or at least, adequate performances (Kröger and Zio 2011).

Functionality of those *CISs*, however, have shown to be susceptible to the disruption, caused by natural hazards, as highlighted once again, by the flood hazard devastating both *West Europe* and *Asia* (CNN 2021, BBC 2021).

State-of-the-art studies have revealed that the greater the complexity of the system of *CISs* is, the less controllable are the cascading effects and repercussions associated with those disruptive events. Due to the ever-increasing degree of intra- and interdependences, seemingly insignificant local damage or dysfunction incurred by one *CIS* can potentially propagate, and thus induce the full-blown cascade of failures (Buldyrev et al. 2010, Brummitt et al. 2012, Bashan et al. 2013). Besides, the losses of *CICSs* accumulated throughout the recovery process following disruptive events also tend to be overwhelming, largely due to their interdependences, as well as the absence of expeditious and well-planned responses (Helbing 2013).

Against this backdrop, considerable research has been conducted to explore viable pathways towards resilient *CICSs* under hazardous events. In 2005, community resilience was highlighted in the World Conference on Disaster Reduction (*WCDR*) and proposed as the bedrock for the well-being of *CICSs* (International Strategy for Disaster Reduction 2005). More recently, Cutter (2013) highlighted the significance of identifying “building resilience” to disasters as the roadmap to sustainability. From the political point of view, the path towards disaster resilience necessitates the collective efforts of all societal sectors.

In particular, regarding seismic hazards, Bruneau et al. (2003) developed an inclusive definition of disaster resilience of *CICSs* to incorporate all actions that minimize losses from hazardous events, including the effects of mitigation and sound recovery. Hence, seismic resilience of *CICSs* is characterised as “the ability of social units (e.g. organizations, communities) to mitigate hazards, contain the effects of disasters when they occur, and carry out recovery activities in ways to minimize social disruption and mitigate the effect of future earthquakes”. They further suggested that resilience could be conceptualized along four dimensions: technical, organizational, societal and economic. The technical and economic dimension are related more directly to the resilience of *CISs*, while the other two dimensions, organizational and social, are more relevant to the resilience of the community.

The research objective of **Task 5.2** is to develop an adaptive and inclusive modelling framework for the rapid response-based recovery and resilience of *CICSs*, under seismic

hazards.

Within *TURNkey* project, Rapid Response (*RR*) is characterized as the array of actions that authorities in charge of disaster management need to deploy, expeditiously and effectively, in the immediate aftermath of the main shock, on the basis of a partial, qualitative and emotionally-biased knowledge regarding the evolving situation in the field. In this sense, *RR* relies heavily on the near-real-time inference on the earthquake location and characteristics (e.g. magnitude), and the knowledge of the exposed assets and their vulnerabilities, to estimate the potential losses and the areas most affected by the earthquake.

Hence, of particular criticality to the applicability of the framework established within *Task 5.2*, is how the time-varying status of *CISs* and the time-dependent quality and quantity of the information regarding such status, which is usually growing as the time from the disruptive event elapses, shall be interpreted, so as to shed light on the decision-making regarding *RRs*.

As an endeavour to deliver a holistic examination on those rapid response actions, a multi-time scale resilience and recovery model will be established to gauge the improvement to *CICSs*, in terms of their robustness and resilience, in the wake of strong earthquakes. Besides, regarding the estimation of the time that a *CICS* needs to be restored to a particular functionality level after seismic events, an agent-based model (*ABM*) is established, whereby the time-dependent functionality can be tracked throughout seismic events, as well as the potential aftershock sequences. The conceptual framework proposed in this Deliverable will be applied to a number of *TBs* to examine the limitations and constraint in real-world systems and needs for refinement of both the general methodology and the tools and models developed.

10.2 Research Significance

The ever-growing interdependence among *CISs*, and the penetration of artificial intelligence (*AI*) into many aspects of their operations have contributed to the functionality of those physical systems (Duan et al. 2020, Esztergár-Kiss et al. 2020). Concurrently, such a tendency has also paved the way for the damage and/or disfunction at a local scale, to cascade and induce the connected systems' shutdown, even within a short course ensuing disruptive events (Helbing, 2013; Schneider et al. 2013).

Within *TURNkey*, Deliverable 5.2 sets out to come up with a toolkit of modular routines and procedures, which can be linked and included in the *TURNkey's* Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response Platform (*FWCR*), to determine the resilience of integrated *CICSs* throughout the immediate aftermath of an event, to formulate appropriate and robust rapid responses. Through the application of these models to the selected Test Beds, the objective is to identify the potential technical as well as sociological and socioeconomic barriers (financial, human, organisational and governance) to the use in practice of the *TURNkey* platform.

In this respect D5.2 fulfils specifically the TURNkey objective PO5: *Development of protocols for response, emergency management, and safety communication, including uncertainties, for technical stakeholders, nontechnical stakeholders, and the public*. Based on the decisional rules forming the Decision Support Systems (DSSs), the models and methods outlined in this *Deliverable* will be further customised and applied in task 5.4 with the overall joint goals of providing 1) rapid information to emergency decision-makers about the availability/unavailability of strategic critical infrastructure and possible consequences of evacuations and 2) rapid information to rescuers about available road network connections and need for emergency repairs. The focus on community resilience will allow to provide guidelines on protocols which are particularly effective to improve the short-term resilience of organisations, critical infrastructure providers and service providers to communities. Outcomes of the application of these resources to selected Test Beds will support the implementation of the DSSs.

10.3 Scope

The second submission of this *Deliverable* includes applications to selected Test Beds and critical assessment of the performance of the toolkit.

The present document is articulated in six chapters.

This chapter gives an overview on the research background and the significance associated with the planned research in *Task 5.2*.

Chapter 11 proposes an adaptive, agent-based model (ABM) on post-shock rapid response with regard to road networks (RNs), under earthquake hazards. In particular, the contribution made by rapid response to the resilience improvements of RNs is gauged and discussed in-depth;

Chapter 12 develops a *Bayesian Network (BN)*, based on the ABM mentioned above. Such a BN can be used to estimate damage probabilities of particular bridges and the connectivity of critical paths. Therefore, it can serve as a viable tool to improve the situational awareness, especially through the introduction of additional metrics that are related to the recovery phase;

Chapter 13 employs Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) modelling to analyse the potential impact of the TURNkey platform on businesses, critical infrastructure and community resilience, which is measured from both the engineering and socio-ecological point of view;

Chapter 14 show the application of System Dynamics approach to the repair and recovery of damaged houses in Iceland. Rather than simulating a specific event, given the dearth of specific data, a proof of concept of a housing recovery and relief simulation model is developed, and information is collected for future modelling work. A management system has been therefore studied to help guide stakeholders to balance their efforts between short-duration and cost-demanding recovery;

Chapter 15 draws the most significant conclusions, based on the review and proposed modelling applications.

11 RAPID RESPONSE-ORIENTED RESILIENCE MODELLING FRAMEWORK OF ROAD NETWORKS

In this Chapter, an agent-based modelling (*ABM*) framework on post-shock rapid response throughout the phase of immediate aftermath of earthquakes (*IAoEs*), has been established. Such a framework is applied to gauge seismic resilience of the road network, in *Luchon, France*. In *Section 4.1*, the principle of the modelling framework has been elaborated on. The resilience of the *Luchon* network under different earthquake scenarios has been examined following such a framework, and the corresponding outcome has been presented in *Section 4.2*.

11.1 Overview of the modelling framework

Within this study, the functionality of the Road Networks (*RNs*) is tracked in the separate *Absorption*, *IAoE*, and *Long-term recovery* stages, respectively. Essentially, the focus during the *Absorption* stage lies in the estimation of the functionality losses of *RNs* immediately following the shock. Throughout the following *IAoE*, the *ABM* will be employed to examine how the functionality restoration of *RNs* is shaped by both the *rapid-response* and *regular repair*. In this *Deliverable*, the post-shock *rapid response* is defined as the set of activities to restore the functionality of the earthquake-damaged bridges to a fractional, yet minimal acceptable level, whereby the emergency rescue and evacuation could be delivered. In practice, given the structural characteristics of the damaged bridges, such rapid responses could usually be implemented by building temporary bridges, ramps or bypasses (Schanack et al. 2012, Durante et al. 2018), or delivering the *rapid repair* on critical damaged members (Parks et al. 2016, Sun et al. 2017). In the following case-study, the *rapid response* will only be delivered to those bridges with severe damage. Ideally, rapid responses should be delivered in a few days. Although specific time frames for the rapid repair delivery are not clearly defined in practice, state-of-the-art research aims at interventions to be accomplished by squads of two people within 24 hours (e.g. Fakharifafa et al. 2016). However, from the real-world perspective, such endeavours tend to be impeded by the widespread damage of the *RN*, as well as the interaction with the other interdependent *infrastructure systems*, throughout *IAoEs*. From evidence available in literature, it is realistic to assume that it would take around a week to complete a rapid response on a critical bridge (Duranter et al. 2018, Norton 2020). Conversely, *regular repair* refers to the set of actions employed to deliver the full restoration of the functionality of the damaged bridges, regardless of their damage state.

Beyond the rapid response phase, the functionality of the whole *RNs* will be restored by the regular repair alone, in the long-term recovery stage. In this *Deliverable*, only the damage of bridge structures will be taken into account, whereas those road segments connecting them are assumed to be intact.

11.1.1 Absorption stage

The earthquake-induced functionality losses regarding various bridges of *RNs* is quantified by seismic functionality-loss functions. Mathematically, such functions provide a measure of the probability that the bridge of interest could retain a certain fraction of their pre-shock functionality, given the intensity measure of the earthquake ground motion at its geographic site, obtained from seismic attenuation models. Nonetheless, for real-world bridge structures, the quantitative relationship between the seismic damage they have incurred and the corresponding functionality loss is very complicated and case-specific (Gehl and D'Ayala 2016, Gehl and D'Ayala 2018). To address such a challenge, in this *Deliverable*, seismic fragility functions are employed to determine *Damage States (DSs)* of bridges under seismic hazard. A total of three *DSs* are considered, i.e. no damage (*DS1*), minor damage (*DS2*), and extensive damage (*DS3*). The seismic fragility model developed by Shinozuka et al. (2002) is employed to examine beam bridges, while the fragility functions published by Zampieri (2014) is used to model the arch bridges. The vulnerability of the bridge is then assessed by quantifying its remaining degree of functionality, given its *DS*. The bridge functionality loss metrics proposed by Gehl and D'Ayala (2018) is employed in this *Deliverable*. Following such metrics, bridges with *DS3* are assumed to be completely closed to any of the vehicular traffic, while those bridges with *DS2* are set to remain passable, but the travelling speed on them will be reduced to 25% of the pre-shock level. In the following, it is assumed that two operators are collaborating to restore the *RN* functionality: a rapid response operator, who might represent a *Civil Protection Agency*, tasked with leading activities in the emergency and immediate aftermath phase, represented by Agent A; and a recovery operator, representing the conventional network management agency, which will dispatch two different agents, B and C, tackling bridges with minor and severe level of seismic damage, respectively, to reflect the different level of resources needed and consequences for the network functionality.

11.1.2 Immediate aftermath of earthquake

Once the probabilistic damage states of each of the individual bridges have been determined, under particular earthquake scenario, *RNs* will then enter *IAoEs* (Figure 33). As mentioned above, the ultimate goal of rapid response throughout such a phase is to restore the traffic-carrying capacity of *RNs*, especially, the connectivity of a host of critical paths, to an acceptable level. Nevertheless, the time needed to fulfil such goals can be very case-specific. In this *Deliverable*, the time span of such a stage is set to be one month, regarding earthquake scenarios with the maximum magnitude, by which time the full functionality of the majority of those severely-damaged bridges will unlikely be restored (Decò et al. 2013), but the restoration on the connectivity of critical paths through rapid responses, can be potentially completed. A multi agent-based model is developed in this *Deliverable*, as an adaptive and inclusive modelling strategy, with regard to the interacting post-shock *rapid response* and the *regular repair* of *RNs* (Sun et al. 2019b), to investigate whether such a time frame is realistic, when applied to a real-case scenario, given the available data on repair and replacement delivery.

Previous studies have investigated the prioritization of bridge repair on the basis of various criteria (Merschman et al. 2020), nonetheless, the working assumption being that the repair phase occurs by considering one bridge at a time. In this *Deliverable*, three different *Repair Unit Agents* have been included to model the restoration of bridges, and their behaviour throughout the recovery campaign is shaped by a set of pre-defined behavioural attributes.

As shown in Figure 1, in each realization of the simulation following the *Absorption* stage, the *Agent A* delivering the post-shock *rapid-response* throughout *IAoEs*, will start the *rapid response* on the damaged bridges, without any idle period.

Figure 33 . Post-shock recovery delivered by concurrent rapid response and regular repair.

As mentioned above, *Agent a* will intervene on those severely-damaged bridges (*DS3*) only, in light of their critical impairment of accessibility to other critical services (e.g. hospitals and emergency shelters), and their potentially long-lasting bottleneck effect on the repair of other bridges with *Minor damage (DS2)*.

Essentially, it would be challenging for state-of-the-art disaster management systems to formulate the optimal rapid response sequence of repair to a *RN*, following catastrophic earthquakes. Regarding a local *RN* like the one considered in the testbed, for earthquake scenarios with high magnitude and epicentre close to its central area, approximately 16% of the bridges, i.e. 19 bridges, would be severely damaged. Accordingly, there would be 19! (=

$1.2165e+17$) permutations of possible sequences. The use of a basic optimization routine would be thus unfeasible on any real-world problem, as also recognised by Bocchini and Frangopol (2012). Hence, engineering reasoning is used in this *Deliverable* to plan rapid responses, based on the network and bridge characteristics. Technically, it will be increasingly hard to construct promptly temporary replacement bridges in the form of prefabricated ramps or spans to create bypasses, for bridges with span length greater than 50m (Yeh et al. 2015), due to local logistics and procurement delays. Specifically, Long et al. (2013) developed a system for the construction of temporary arch bridges, which can take few days for spans up to 10m. In this *Deliverable*, as a straightforward criterion for rapid response priority at system level, the bridges with *DS3* are ranked based on their span, as a measure of ease of reparability, in the ascending order.

Meanwhile, the initial number of bridges with either *DS2*, or *DS3*, will affect the rate of the delivery of *rapid response* to each of the bridge with *DS3*, throughout the *IAoE* phase, depending on its position in the *RN*, and its span. Hence, as shown in Figure 33, the start and completion time of the *rapid repair/replacement* of each bridge (out of a total of N_r ones) is defined by Equations (1-3):

$$R_{r,j} = T_{r,j} + \frac{F_{r,j}}{E_r * \omega^n} * \frac{\text{Span}(j)}{50}, \quad \text{if } \text{Span}(j) \leq 50\text{m or}$$

$$R_{r,j} = T_{r,j} + \frac{F_{r,j}}{E_r * \omega^n} * \left(\frac{\text{Span}(j)-50}{50}\right)^2, \quad \text{if } \text{Span}(j) > 50\text{m}, \quad (1)$$

with $j = 1: N_r$ and

$$T_{r,1} = SD_{r,0}/V_r \quad (2)$$

$$T_{r,j} = SD_{r,j}/V_r, \quad \text{for } j = 2: N_r \quad (3)$$

where $T_{r,1}$ is the time needed to start the rapid response associated with the first bridge, since the earthquake event. Given the *RN* topology, the travelling time between the *rapid response* centre and the first bridge (*i.e.* the severely-damaged bridge with shortest span) is determined by the length of the shortest path between the two locations (denoted as $SD_{r,0}$); V_r is the travelling speed of the *rapid response* team. The total time needed to complete the rapid response on the first bridge, denoted as $R_{r,1}$, will be therefore obtained by $T_{r,1}$ plus the required repair time as defined in (Eq. 1).

In Eq. (1), $F_{r,j}$ denotes the component functionality objective to be restored, which in the *IAoEs* is set to be the target of being accessible, with the corresponding travelling speed set to be 10% of the pre-shock level; E_r denotes the efficiency of the *rapid repair/replacement* squad, also treated as a probabilistic variable. To account for delays due to the availability of resources, need for clearance operations, and etc., as shown in Eq. (1), the efficiency parameter is reduced by a factor ω^n ($\omega < 1$), where ω is a pre-defined reduction coefficient, while $n(t, b_d,$

b_t) denotes the number of damaged bridges (with either $DS2$, or $DS3$) associated with the shortest path between the last bridge that the Agent A has delivered the rapid response (denoted as b_d), and the one it is heading to tackle (denoted as b_t). As shown in Figure 33, n will assume a new value for each rapid response loop, and will be contingent upon the amount and location of bridges repaired by the other two agents.

Furthermore, for each single bridge j , as shown in Eq. (1), the *repair/replacement time* will increase linearly with its span, denoted as $Span(j)$, when shorter than 50m, while it will increase quadratically with $Span(j)$, if longer than 50m.

The model described above therefore allows to develop a looped interdependence between *rapid repair/replacements* and *regular repairs*. The expeditious rapid response will help to allay the bottleneck effect on the regular repair, which will in turn, facilitate the rapid response itself.

11.1.3 Long-term recovery

As shown in Figure 33, following the *Absorption* phase, similar to *Agent A*, *Agent B* and *Agent C* will also be dispatched to deliver the *regular repair* on damaged bridges with $DS2$ (i.e. minor damage), and $DS3$ (i.e. severe damage), respectively. Both agents formulate their repair sequences by ranking the bridges based on their *betweenness centrality*, following the assumption that the topology of the road networks affects the efficiency of restoration. Mathematically, the betweenness centrality of bridge v is computed following Equation (4):

$$g(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{st} is the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t , and $\sigma_{st}(v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v (Brandes 2001). A ranked repair list can therefore be generated in the descending order, based on such a criterion. Both the two *Agents B* and *C* will depart from the *Repair Centre* and start to repair the first bridge on their own repair list (i.e. the bridge with the largest value of betweenness centrality, with regard to both $DS2$ and $DS3$). Similar to Equations (1) ~ (3), the repair time for each bridge with $DS2$ will be determined by the two behavioural attributes of the agent, namely, V_m and E_m , which refer to the traveling speed of the *Agent B* and its repair efficiency, respectively. Hence, for each individual bridge i with $DS2$ (the total amount of which will be denoted as N_{DS2}), the time needed to start and finish its repair will then be determined following Equations (5) ~ (7):

$$T_1 = T_0 + SD_0/V_m \quad (5)$$

$$R_i = T_i + F_{m,i}/E_m, \quad i = 1: N_{DS2} \quad (6)$$

$$T_i = R_{i-1} + SD_i/V_m, \quad i = 2: N_{DS2} \quad (7)$$

where T_1 is the time needed to reach the first bridge, since the seismic event. Similar to Eq. (2), SD_0 refers to the length of the shortest path between the *RN* repair centre and the first bridge (in the specific ranked repair list), given the *RN* topology, which is different from the pre-shock

one, and is itself a function of the repairs undertaken at any given time. Therefore, for the first bridge, the corresponding travelling time will be obtained by SD_0 divided by the attribute V_m , which again is affected by the restriction on speed on any of the bridges with $DS2$. Besides, T_0 is set to consider the time for the *Agent B* to scheme the repair plan, while preparing the necessary repair resources (Decò et al. 2013, Sun et al. 2019a). The total time required to restore the functionality of the first bridge, denoted as R_1 can therefore be obtained by T_1 plus the required repair time quantified by $F_{m,1}/E_m$. Here, $F_{m,1}$ denotes the functionality to be fully restored, for the first bridge. In this case, full restoration of functionality responds to the criteria of the bridge being passable with the pre-shock allowed speed level, i.e. means that all lanes have been restored and therefore no speed or weight restrictions are in place. The *Agent B* will proceed to restore the next bridge in the repair list, until the functionality of all bridges with $DS2$ has been fully restored. Nevertheless, it shall be highlighted that *Agent B* would likely encounter inaccessible paths, due to the existence of bridges with $DS3$. Regarding such cases, in this study, before being able to reach a particular bridge scheduled for the repair, *Agent B* is assumed to be waiting until the restoration of the accessibility of those severely-damaged bridges ($DS3$), which occlude its available path forward to such a bridge, delivered by either *Agent A* (rapid response), or *Agent C* (full repair). Finally, the *Agent C*'s behaviour will be modelled in the same way as *Agent B*, yet with different behaviour attributes, namely, V_s and E_s , respectively. However, as the complete functionality recovery (defined as stated for $DS2$ bridges) on most of the bridges with $DS3$ would only be delivered in the long-term recovery stage (Figure 33), when calculating the travelling time, the potential bottleneck effect from those bridges with $DS2$ will be considered only in the earlier phase of activity of *Agent C*, namely, during *IAoEs*.

11.1.4 Multidimensional resilience measures

In order to quantify the seismic resilience of *RNs* from both the physical and societal point of view, a total of three resilience measures are proposed in this *Deliverable*:

- a) *Functionality losses at the component level*. As already stated, the only components of *RNs* analysed in this study are the bridges. Justifiably, it is significant to first investigate the probabilistic distributions of *DSs* associated with individual bridges, particularly, those critical ones with high betweenness centrality, or those ones that are most vulnerable to seismic hazards. Besides, in this *Deliverable*, only the damage distribution obtained in the absorption stage following the main shock will be considered;
- b) *Percentage of functional bridges*, denoted as $PFB(t)$.

$$PFB(t) = \frac{\sum_i^{B_{tot}} f(i,t)}{B_{tot}}, \text{ with } f(i,t)=1, \text{ if functional; Otherwise, } 0 \quad (8)$$

As shown by Eq. (8), at any given time t , $PFB(t)$ can be examined, based on the functionality state of each individual bridge i , denoted as $f(i,t)$. The value of $f(i,t)$ is set to

be I , if the bridge has no damage or if it has been fully repaired. Otherwise, it equals to 0 . $PFB(t)$ will be tracked throughout the entirety of the recovery phase, and employed as a physical resilience measure on the system level;

c) *Normalized length of critical path*, denoted as $NLCP(t)$.

$$NLCP(t) = \frac{LCP_{orig}}{LCP(t)} \quad (9)$$

The ultimate role played by RNs is to enable the uninterrupted mobility of people. It is apparent that the traffic-carrying capacity of RNs is contingent not just upon the PFB , but also the topology of RNs . It is particularly crucial to note that the RNs ' topology itself will be time-varying, affected by the potential aftershock sequence, and the corresponding repairs and rapid responses. By the end of the *Absorption* phase, some of the road segments of RNs will be inaccessible, due to the damage or collapse of one or more bridges associated with them. From the point of view of graph theory, the RN topology then will be different from that in the pre-shock stage, as those inaccessible road segments are essentially removed from the topological model representing the RNs . Given the start and end nodes of interest, the shortest path between them may likely be substantially different from the one obtained from the intact RNs , or there might not be any accessible path anymore. However, upon the onset of the *IAoEs*, the functionality of those damaged bridges will start to be restored. Those inaccessible paths can therefore be available again, as those associated damaged bridges have been partially or fully repaired. Hence, in this *Deliverable*, the topology of the RN of interest is reanalysed after each rapid repair/replacement or regular repair has been delivered, and the shortest path between that particular pair of start and end nodes is updated (i.e. shortened, or fully restored to the original level associated with the intact RN). As shown in Eq. (9), the global dynamic behaviour of the RNs can therefore be well interpreted by the *normalized length of critical path* ($NLCP$) of interest. Here, LCP_{orig} and $LCP(t)$ denote the geographic length of that particular path, obtained from the original topology and the time-varying topology, at time point t following the earthquake hazard, respectively.

11.2 Rapid response-based recovery and resilience of testbed RN in Luchon, France

11.2.1 Configuration of the case-study RN

To gauge the contribution of post-shock rapid responses with regard to seismic resilience of RNs , the *ABM* developed hereinbefore is applied to a real-world RN across the *Luchon Valley, France*, a historic and touristic region, one of the valleys of the *Pyrenees* connecting France to Spain. Such a hierarchical RN comprises a *route nationale* ($N125$), several *route départementales*, and rural roads. Given the mountainous topography and the presence of several water courses, the RN comprises 118 bridges, of which 89 beam-type bridges, 1 truss bridge and 28 arch bridges, and connects 53 municipalities (small villages and towns), as

shown in Figure 34.

11.2.2 Scenario-based simulation following the developed ABM framework

Given the significant uncertainties regarding seismic hazards, as well as the vulnerability and recovery behaviour of *RNs*, *Monte Carlo (MC)* simulations are run to account for their collective influence on the seismic resilience of the *RN*. The simulation outcomes presented hereinafter are obtained from 2,000 *MC* simulations. For each realization, the simulation is run for a reference time of 1,800 days, to ensure the full recovery of the network and repair of all damaged bridges. As the post-shock recovery continues, the state of the *RN* is updated at each time step, set as half day, allowing the whole recovery trajectory to be tracked.

The realization of each single *MC* simulation is set to start with the generation of an earthquake scenario, characterized by the location of its epicentre and the corresponding seismic magnitude M_w . On the basis of recorded historic seismic activity across the region, three epicentres close to the central area of *Luchon*, with coordinates presented in Table 1, are considered in this case-study, as shown in Figure 34.

Table 1. Location of epicentres.

Epicentre	Longitude (W)	Latitude (N)
1	0.6	42.8
2	0.55	42.867
3	0.5	42.833

To generate ground shaking scenarios, different ground motion models have been considered as recommended by García-Fernández et al. (2019), ultimately choosing the ground motion attenuation model for a rock site proposed by Campbell and Bozorgnia (2008), applicable to earthquake scenarios with $M_w \leq 7.5$. Given the upper limit of the *SHARE* seismic source area model across the region (Woessner et al. 2013), the maximum seismic magnitude considered in this paper is set to 7.

Figure 35 shows the histogram of the *Intensity Measure* (e.g. *Peak Ground Acceleration*) at the geographic site of bridge #663 for a scenario with the epicentre No.1 and magnitude $M_w=7$, and the corresponding fragility behaviour for such a bridge. It shows that the value of the resulting *PGAs* is varying between 0.2g and 0.4g, for the majority of the realizations. It can be further found that, given its fragility function, for such a range of *PGA* values, the probability of being in *DS2* or *DS3* are low but not insignificant, from the probabilistic point of view.

The functionality losses associated with each earthquake-damaged bridge can be determined, based on its *DS* obtained from the fragility analysis. Accordingly, the trajectory of their post-shock functionality recovery, driven by the activity of those three *agents* described above, can also be tracked thereafter. To that end, in each of the simulations, the behavioural attributes of those agents will be randomly generated following the probabilistic distributions, characterized by the pre-defined parameters, presented in Table 2. Specifically, for *Agent A*,

the travelling speed (V_r) is set to follow a uniform distribution with the lower and upper limits of 15km/h and 20km/h , respectively. Such a relatively low speed is assumed, to account for the potential impact of the debris and jam on the travel, throughout the *IAoE* phase, in an implicit way. Accordingly, the lower and upper limit for the travelling speed (V_m) of *Agent B* in charge of the repair on bridges with *DS2*, who may need to ship some heavier equipment, are set to be 5km/h and 10km/h , respectively, while the travelling speed V_s of *Agent C* delivering the restoration of bridges with *DS3*, is set to be varying between 2.5km/h to 5km/h , assuming that major on-site equipment will need to be mobilised for each repair.

Figure 34 . Topology of the road network in Luchon, France.

Figure 35 Probabilistic distribution of intensity measure at one critical bridge location as sampled through the MC simulation and the corresponding fragility functions.

For each single bridge of the RN, its DS is determined by fragility analysis, based on the Intensity Measure (*IM*) of the ground motion at its geographic location, obtained from the attenuation model.

Figure 35 shows the histogram of the *Intensity Measure* (e.g. *Peak Ground Acceleration*) at the geographic site of bridge #663 for a scenario with the epicentre No.1 and magnitude $M_w=7$, and the corresponding fragility behaviour for such a bridge. It shows that the value of the resulting *PGAs* is varying between $0.2g$ and $0.4g$, for the majority of the realizations. It can be further found that, given its fragility function, for such a range of *PGA* values, the probability of being in *DS2* or *DS3* are low but not insignificant, from the probabilistic point of view.

The functionality losses associated with each earthquake-damaged bridge can be determined, based on its *DS* obtained from the fragility analysis. Accordingly, the trajectory of their post-shock functionality recovery, driven by the activity of those three *agents* described above, can also be tracked thereafter. To that end, in each of the simulations, the behavioural attributes of those agents will be randomly generated following the probabilistic distributions, characterized by the pre-defined parameters, presented in Table 2. Specifically, for *Agent A*, the travelling speed (V_r) is set to follow a uniform distribution with the lower and upper limits of 15km/h and 20km/h , respectively. Such a relatively low speed is assumed, to account for the potential impact of the debris and jam on the travel, throughout the *IAoE* phase, in an implicit way. Accordingly, the lower and upper limit for the travelling speed (V_m) of *Agent B* in charge of the repair on bridges with *DS2*, who may need to ship some heavier equipment, are set to be 5km/h and 10km/h , respectively, while the travelling speed V_s of *Agent C* delivering the restoration of bridges with *DS3*, is set to be varying between 2.5km/h to 5km/h , assuming that major on-site equipment will need to be mobilised for each repair.

In terms of *Efficiency*, for *Agent A*, E_r is set to follow a uniform distribution with lower and upper limit of $100/\text{day}$ and $200/\text{day}$, respectively. This means that the time needed to complete the rapid response for a single bridge will range from 0.5 to 1 day. However, it is noteworthy to highlight that, as shown in Eq. (3), such a time will be increasing with span length, linearly up to 50 m, and then quadratically, for spans exceeding 50m. More importantly, E_r will also be reduced by the factor ω^n ($\omega < 1$), as explained in *section 3*.

For *Agent B* and *Agent C*, their *Efficiency* parameters (denoted as E_m and E_s , respectively) are also assumed to be following uniform distributions. The corresponding lower and upper bounds of such distributions are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Behavioural attributes of the three *Agents*

Attribute	Lower	Upper	Distribution	Average recovery time
V_r (km/h)	15	20	Uniform	
E_r (%)	100	200	Uniform	0.75 day
V_m (km/h)	5	10	Uniform	

E_m (%)	5	10	Uniform	15 days
V_s (km/h)	2.5	5	Uniform	
E_s (%)	1.25	2.5	Uniform	60 days

11.2.3 Simulation results

As mentioned hereinbefore, resilience of the *RN* in *Luchon* will be investigated from the perspective of the probabilistic *DSs* of critical bridges, $PFB(t)$, and $NLCP(t)$, respectively. To that end, a graph-theory (topological) model is established to represent such a *RN*, where each individual node refers to a starting/end point, while the links among them are set to represent the corresponding road segments.

Based on that graph, the betweenness centrality of each single bridge can therefore be computed following *Eq. (4)*, which will serve as the measure of the criticality of the 118 bridges of the *RN*. However, to account for the hierarchical nature of the *RN*, with greater traffic capacity and demand on the national road and substantially lower traffic capacity on the local roads, the betweenness centrality of bridges, associated with the “regional” and “local” road systems, is scaled down by 0.1 and 0.01, respectively, while the betweenness of bridges belonging to the “main” road system is kept unchanged. Based on the scaled betweenness, two bridges with *ID* No. 663 and 676, become the two most relevant ones (Figure 34), with regard to the whole *RN* (i.e. with the highest betweenness centrality values). Indeed, they are both located on the national road connecting the central and northern regions of *Luchon*.

To determine the efficiency of the repair and the restoration of critical paths, after analysing a number of critical Origin-Destination pairs, the start and end node have been set to be the city centre and the southwest exit of the *RN*, which links the valley’s population to critical emergency facilities (see Figure 34). The shortest path between these two nodes is 11.5 km, given the topology of the intact *RN*.

Figure 36 Damage Sate of critical bridges under seismic scenarios with different magnitude.

The stochastic analysis under M_w 7 scenarios (with epicentre No.1) obtained through the 2000 MC realisations provides a probabilistic distribution of the damage states $DS2$ and $DS3$ for each of the 118 bridges, as plotted in Figure 36, which can be interpreted together with their betweenness centrality ranking to determine critical bridges across the network and the critical paths. For instance, regarding bridge #663, its likelihood of $DS2$ and $DS3$ are found to be merely 2.25% and 6.65%, respectively. It shall be noted, in light of its high betweenness centrality, the seismic robustness of this bridge is strategically valuable, as many of the paths can thereby be maintained, notwithstanding widespread damage across the RN . The analysis shows that for the specific level of magnitude chosen, the maximum credible in the region, the likelihood of $DS3$ is significantly larger than that of $DS2$ for many bridges. Among all, due to its proximity to the epicentre, bridge No. 619 turns out to be the most vulnerable one, in terms of $DS3$. It can be noted that several masonry arch bridges have high probability of being in $DS3$, and as mapped in Figure 34, they would affect both the national and regional branches of the network, and substantially affect the mobility throughout the valley and its accessibility, as for instance bridge No. 706, being on the critical path between the city centre and the exit.

The results on recovery and restoration of the chosen critical path are presented in the following considering two distinct scenarios: first, a conventional recovery process, considered as the baseline scenario, where only *Agent B* and *Agent C* are active; then a second scenario, which considers the activity of all three *Agents* and determines the gain to be had by implementing rapid repair/replacements in the *IAoE* period.

A. Baseline scenario: conventional recovery process

In Figure 37, the sensitivity of seismic resilience of the RN , with regard to different locations of the epicentre was first examined, by tracking the median of its $PFB(t)$, under scenarios with $M_w=7$. In general, the recovery trajectories are not found to be radically different from each other, despite the different location of epicentres and different initial number of non-fully functional bridges. Specifically, for the epicentres with Nos. 1, 2 and 3, the PFB value is found to be 73.7%, 76.3%, and 78.0%, respectively. In light of the same probabilistic distribution of the behaviour attributes of the agents (Table 2), the overall recovery rate of the RN is close to each other, regarding all the three epicentres. Eventually, it takes 1023 days, 962.5 days, and 840 days, respectively, for the RN to be fully recovered. Given the similarity of the resulting resilience of the RN with regard to different epicentre locations, the behaviour of the RN is further investigated, under the scenario with *Epicentre No.1* alone, which induces the most serious damage, on the systems level.

Figure 37 Median $PFB(t)$ under earthquake scenario with different epicentres.

Figure 38(a) tracks the median $PFB(t)$ of the RN, under earthquake scenario with different magnitudes. The analysis at network scale shows the sensitivity of seismic resilience of the Luchon RN to the increasing magnitudes. Specifically, its median PFB in the absorption phase drops from 90.7% to 73.7%, as the magnitude increased from 5 to 7. Similarly, the median full recovery time vary from 191 days to 2.8 years for the same range of magnitudes. It should be noted that the rate of recovery is not substantially affected by the increase in magnitude although two step changes can be seen between M_w 5.25 and M_w 5.5 and between M_w 6 and M_w 6.5, corresponding to increases in the number of bridges with $DS3$.

(a) Median resilience under scenario with different magnitudes (b) 5% and 95% quantiles under $M_w = 7$

Figure 38 $PFB(t)$ under earthquake scenario with different magnitudes.

In Figure 39(b), the quantile of 5% and 95% of the $PFB(t)$ under seismic scenario with $M_w=7$, are also presented. It should be noted that even considering the hazardous event as a given scenario, the stochasticity regarding seismic resilience of the RN is large, due to the collective impact of the uncertainty associated with seismic fragility of the bridge structures, their recoverability, and the interdependences thereof. The uncertainty of seismic fragility is measured by the PFB immediately following the shock, which is found to be ranging between 68% and 78%. On the other hand, it can be seen that the recovery paths diverge with time, and for the 5% quantile, it will take up to 4.3 years to fully repair all the seismically-damaged

bridges. Such a significant lack of resilience, notwithstanding the fairly low exceedance likelihood, underscores the sensitivity of the system to the uncertainty associated with the recovery behaviour, and the importance to define them more accurately.

Figure 39. Median number of bridges under seismic scenarios with different magnitudes.

To further examine the recovery trajectory of bridges with different DSs , Figure 39 presents the time-varying number of bridges with $DS2$ and $DS3$, respectively, under scenarios with different magnitudes. It can be found that, immediately following the seismic hazard, the number of bridges with $DS3$ will be growing from 3 to 19, as the magnitude is increased from 5 to 7, while the recovery rate remains constant throughout. For the same range of scenarios, the number of bridges with $DS2$ increases from 8 to 12. The pattern associated with their post-earthquake recovery, however, are fairly different. Notwithstanding the same behavioural attributes, the stagnancy regarding the recovery is found to be increasingly pronounced, as the magnitude increases, due to the bottleneck to recovery induced by the increase of the amount of bridges with $DS3$, which prevents reaching bridges with $DS2$ conditioned on certain branches of the network until they have been fully repaired.

In Figure 40 the $NLCP(t)$ between *City Centre* and *Exit* (Figure 34) under those different earthquake scenarios are tracked. Results show that the $NLCP$ is not substantially affected by earthquakes of magnitude lower than 5.5, so that the corresponding recovery time is almost 0, even though the number of damaged bridges is non-zero. This highlights that, although the network is highly hierarchical and has a substantially in-series layout, there is nonetheless sufficient redundancy to accommodate up to 13% of the bridges being damaged, with 5 of them seriously, without losing accessibility. However, once the magnitude reaches the threshold of 5.5, the response of the RN turns out to be substantially different, as no available path can be identified between the pair of nodes of interest anymore (thus 0, in Figure 43) following the shock. More crucially, such a loss of connectivity remains unchanged for 76.5 days. This outcome reveals that as the number of non-functional bridges increases, the system-level resilience would degrade, given its topology. For magnitudes increasing from 5.75 to 7, no accessible path can be determined between the two reference points for up to 81.5 to 109.5

days, which suggests a long-lasting functionality loss, and the associated socio-economic disruptions. It shall be noted that, as shown in Figure 34, such a particular path connects the city centre to an exit of the valley, which will thereby be employed to transport the wounded to the hospitals, to evacuate the affected inhabitants, and to ship the emergency necessities. Such a lack of societal resilience would thus pose a strategic risk to the whole community, under hazardous events, especially, in the *IAoE* phase.

Figure 40. Normalized, median *NLCP* under seismic scenarios with different magnitude.

B. Rapid Response Scenario

The simulation outcome presented above has highlighted that, the *RN* of interest will not be sufficiently resilient under strong earthquakes, particularly from the societal perspective. Therefore, the post-shock rapid responses should be leveraged as an alternative pathway to the enhancement of seismic resilience of earthquake-damaged *RNs*. However, justifiably, for the increased widespread damage inflicted to the network, the delivery of *Rapid Response* will also be increasingly encumbered. Therefore, to simulate such a dependency of the rapid response on the level of seismic damage in the *IAoE* phase, and the concurrent regular repair activity, the factor ω is employed as a multiplier of the efficiency parameter and assigned values $\omega = 0.5, 0.75, \text{ and } 1$, respectively. The higher the ω value is, the more self-reliant the *Rapid Responses* will be, and for $\omega = 1$, there is no hindrance on the activity of *Agent A*. Moreover, as described above, another parameter n , which is the exponent of ω and denotes the number of damaged bridges associated with the path to the next target bridge in the *IAoE* phase, will also be introduced to account for that dependency.

Additionally, the duration of *IAoEs* in this *paper*, as already mentioned in *Section 4.1.2*, is set to be 30 days, following the main shock.

Figure 41 examines the influence of parameter ω , on the *Rapid Response* itself. In the case of $\omega = 0.5$, the benchmark efficiency E_r will therefore be reduced by 0.5^n , so that the rapid repair/replacement is found to be delivered to only 8 bridges, by the end of the *IAoE*. The partial restoration of accessibility of the limited amount of bridges with *DS3* is thus expected to be

unable to substantially expedite the regular repair on bridges with $DS2$. In particular, as mentioned in *Section 4.1.2*, the guiding strategy of the rapid response *Agent A* is to address the restoration of the “easiest” bridges first, so as to maximise the number of passable bridges in the short term. However, such bridges might not be necessarily on those paths to be taken by the *Agent B*, whose sequence is ranked by betweenness centrality of the bridges of $DS2$.

This outcome also highlights the difficulty of delivering rapid responses in a really “rapid” way, unless the influence of the widespread damage of the RN can be mitigated through “pre-emptive” preparedness, for instance, by appropriately distributing the resources needed for post-shock rapid responses, such as enough vehicles able to carry heavy equipment and prefabricated metal ramps, across minor roads, through the mountainous valley.

As the ω value increases, the influence of regular repairs on the activity of *Agent A* is less pronounced. From Figure 41, in case of $\omega = 0.75$, all bridges with damage $DS3$ can be made passable within the rapid response timeframe of 30 days, with a single delay identified by the plateau observed. Moreover, as showed in Table 2, on average, it will take around 15 days and 60 days to fully restore one bridge with $DS2$ and $DS3$, respectively. Therefore, according to Figure 41, the rapid response has already been delivered to the majority of bridges with $DS3$ on the 15th day, which means that the corresponding bottleneck effect could be effectively lifted, before the completion of the regular repair of the first bridge with $DS2$.

Finally, for $\omega = 1$, not only the rapid response can be delivered to all the severely-damaged bridges, but also is unaffected by the existence of the other damaged bridges of the RN , as $I^n = 1$. Therefore, as shown in Figure 41, the rapid response trajectory is a straight line and the entirety of the rapid response campaign takes only 9.5 days. While this situation is clearly ideal, the fact that the average repair time is 15 days for the first bridge with $DS2$, means that there is negligible difference in terms of RN resilience associated with the two cases of $\omega = 0.75$ and 1, respectively.

Figure 41. Median number of bridges with rapid response delivered, under seismic scenarios with magnitude 7 for different values of ω .

In Figure 42, the resulting functionality trajectories of the whole *RN*, as well as the recovery path of bridges with *DS2*, under the earthquake scenarios with the magnitude of 7, associated with three different values of ω , are tracked and compared with the outcome obtained from the baseline case without *Rapid Response*.

Figure 42. Median trajectory under seismic scenarios with magnitude 7.

It can be found that, compared with the baseline case, the *Rapid Responses* is able to improve seismic resilience of the *RN*, yet by a narrow margin, when $\omega = 0.5$. In terms of the repair on bridges with *DS2*, the overall recovery rate is indeed slightly higher than that of the baseline. Nevertheless, it shall be noted that the plateau observed in Figure 39(a) can still be found, which indicates that the repair on bridges with *DS2* would still be impeded by the bottleneck effect from some bridges with *DS3*. The whole recovery campaign (on bridges with *DS2*) is thus only shortened by 17% (from 731 days to 606.5 days).

As ω reaches 0.75, however, the resulting resilience behaviour is found to be sharply enhanced. Figure 42(a) shows that the overall recovery rate substantially increases since the very beginning of *IAoE*. Compared with the baseline, it can be found that the time needed to reach 85% of the pre-shock level has been reduced by 63.5%, i.e. from 465.5 days to 170 days. The positive interaction between *Agent A* and *Agent B* is demonstrated by Figure 42(b), whereby the plateau observed in the first two cases can no longer be identified, showing that the *Agent B* is no longer hindered by damaged *DS3* bridges. Finally, it only took 166.5 days to fully repair all the bridges with *DS2*, which account for 22.78% of the time needed for the baseline case.

When the rapid response become completely “independent” ($\omega = 1$), the seismic resilience of the *RN* is not further improved, in a significant way. From Figure 42(a), it took 168.5 days to reach 85% of the pre-shock level. In terms of those bridges with *DS2*, the entirety of the recovery campaign took 164 days, signifying a 77.56% reduction, compared to the baseline.

Figure 43. Median *PFB* on “milestone” moments under earthquake scenario with magnitude of 7, given different ω values.

To further examine the influence of ω on the seismic resilience of the RN, in Figure 43, the median *PFB* on a set of “milestone” moments (which includes the 30th, 60th, 90th, 120th, 150th, and 180th day after the earthquake), have been tracked by the additional simulations with ω value increased from 0.5 to 0.75, with the step of 0.025. Overall, it can be found that, for the first two moments, *PFB* is found insensitive to different ω values, consistent with the observations from Figure 42. Therefore, although the rapid response campaign concludes on the 30th day, it is too soon for its beneficial effect to be observed, given the average rate of repair for bridges with either *DS2*, or *DS3* (Table 2). However, the resilience improvement become increasingly pronounced, from the 90th day onwards. It can be seen that increasing value of ω lead to an increase in the percentage of functional bridges. Specifically, on the 120th day, there is an increase of 5% of functional bridges between the cases with $\omega = 0.5$ and $\omega = 0.7$ (also shown in Figure 42). Such a pattern holds true and becomes more remarkable, when it comes to the response of the RN, on the 150th and 180th days, respectively. For the former, an increase in the ω from 0.55 to 0.675 yields an increase of *PFB* from 79.7% to 83.9%, in a monotonical way, while an increase from 80.5% to 85.6% of *PFB* is measured on the 180th day for the same change in the value of ω . From the perspective of risk governance, such an observation indicates that, even the slight increase of self-reliance of the rapid response unit, e.g. through the improved preparedness, could substantially improve the seismic resilience of RNs.

Figure 44. Median number of the *NLCP* under seismic scenarios with magnitude 7.

Finally, Figure 44 examines the *NLCP* of interest, regarding the four different cases. It is shown that the rapid response can significantly accelerate the restoration of the connectivity of such a path. Even for the case of $\omega = 0.5$, accessibility of the critical path can be restored 88 days earlier (21.5th day versus 109.5th day), despite the marginal contribution made by the rapid response, regarding the recovery rate of the percentage of fully functional bridges (Figure 42(a)). In particular, the corresponding period is further shortened to 4 and 3.5 days, as ω reaches 0.75 and 1, respectively. Such a reduction by up to 96.8% is strategically critical, not only to the emergency aids and evacuations, but also to the restoration on other *CISs*, which will in turn, have a knock-on effect on seismic resilience of the *RN* itself.

12 THE POST-SHOCK RECOVERY OF CISs UNDER INCOMPLETE INFORMATION

During the early recovery phase (*IAoE*), the information regarding the heatmap of the global networked *CISs* will be dynamic and evolving, depending on the information that is gradually retrieved from the field. Therefore, a *Bayesian Network (BN)* framework has been adopted as the key approach for the rapid response phase in the TURNkey project. It is extensively developed in Work Package 4 (*Physical and Systematic Vulnerability Estimation for Rapid Loss Prediction Updating*), as part of the *Rapid Earthquake Loss Prediction Model*. The following paragraphs summarize the potential use of the *BN* outcomes as inputs to the recovery and resilience models, while demonstrating its application to a road network system.

12.1 Bayesian Networks as a tool for post-event loss updating

This part has been detailed in Deliverable Report D5.2 (Phase 1): a Bayesian Network (BN) has been designed in order to update loss measures of a road network (damage states of bridges at the component level, and connectivity loss at the system level) located in the Luchon valley (TB-2), which is the same one examined in Chapter 2.

Two types of observations are fed into the BN: accelerometric measures from free-field seismic stations and damage measures from structure-mounted stations. Outputs of the BN consist in the damage probabilities of the bridges and in the probability that two locations of the network are accessible (depending on the passability of bridges). This outcome aims at improving situational awareness immediately after the earthquake occurrence, before taking rapid response actions.

12.2 Bayesian Networks as a tool for a first-order estimation of recovery efforts

Due the probabilistic nature of the outputs of Bayesian updating, such information should be mostly used to estimate the extent of the crisis and to prepare the deployment of resources in specific areas or ‘hot spots’. In order to provide more elaborate measures than binary connectivity, it is proposed here to investigate the possibility to develop a BN that may predict metrics related to the longer term, such as the total recovery time of the road network (which may be linked to resilience measures).

To this end, the global idea is to learn “empirical” relations between the damage states of bridges and complex system performance measures, by running multiple stochastic earthquake scenarios and by applying an agent-based model for road network recovery. This BN learning framework has first been investigated and implemented by Gehl et al. (2018). The main steps of the proposed approach are the following (see Figure 45):

- A large set of earthquake scenarios (e.g., 10,000 events) are generated, leading to corresponding damage maps of n bridges (i.e., damage states sampled from damage probabilities).

Figure 45. Flowchart of the proposed approach to couple the agent-based model for recovery with the Bayesian updating framework.

- For each damage scenario, an agent-based model is applied to the restoration strategies of bridges (recovery phase), based on their damage states, the availability of repair teams and the travel time (connectivity, accessibility) to reach damaged bridges. The model provides time-varying functionality loss measures, at the level of the system or of the component: evolution of the percentage of functional bridges, evolution of the connectivity, etc.
- This recovery analysis provides a “Damage State Matrix” (DSM), linking the damage states of the n bridges to various loss and resilience measures, such as the total recovery time of the road network.
- Data mining techniques (e.g., regression tree, random forest) are applied to the DSM in order to identify a subset of k bridges that have the most impact on the performance measure of interest.

- The sampled damage configurations of the k bridges are then used to “learn” simplified probabilistic relations between the damage states of bridges and the performance measure.
- These relationships are finally used to build a simplified BN, which is able to provide early estimates of performance measures that are related to recovery and resilience.

12.3 Application of the BN learning framework to the road network in TB-2

The proposed approach is applied to a road network located in the Luchon valley (Pyrenees, France), which connects 53 municipalities and which is composed of 118 bridges (considered as the vulnerable components of the system). The studied road network is extensively detailed in Work Package 4, especially in Deliverable Report D4.3 (D’Ayala et al. 2021) related to Task 4.2.

12.3.1 Generation of stochastic damage scenarios

Stochastic earthquake events are generated by sampling events from the seismogenic sources surrounding the road network. Gutenberg-Richter distribution parameters are obtained from the SHARE area source model (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2013), as detailed in Table . A minimum magnitude of 4.5 is set in order to prevent the sampling of non-damaging events. Moreover, due to the large extent of some seismogenic areas, a maximum cut-off distance of 100 km (between the epicenter location and the closest bridge) is adopted in order to prevent the sampling of remote events.

Table 3. Activity parameters for the eight seismogenic source areas surrounding the road network.

Area ID	M_{\min}	M_{\max}	a	b
ESAS465	4.5	6.8	3.1000	1.00
FRAS466	4.5	6.8	3.6500	1.00
FRAS468	4.5	6.8	2.1389	1.00
FRAS469	4.5	6.8	3.2500	1.00
ESAS470	4.5	6.8	3.0000	1.00
FRAS473	4.5	6.8	3.0000	1.00
ESAS971	4.5	6.8	1.3968	1.03
FRAS110	4.5	6.5	2.7911	1.00

For each sampled earthquake event, the Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) is computed at the location of each bridge, by using the Ground Motion Model (GMM) by Akkar & Bommer (2010). The inter- and intra-event error terms of the GMM are sampled, while accounting for the spatial correlation between the intra-event errors (Esposito and Iervolino 2011). Soil amplification factors are taken into account by applying a regional site effect map developed for the Pyrenees area (Fayjaloun et al., 2021).

Finally, fragility functions are applied to the 118 bridges, using the sampled PGA, in order to compute damage probabilities. Three damage states are considered: D1 (no damage), D2

(minor damage) and D3 (severe damage). Based on the damage probabilities, the bridge damage states are sampled in order to produce stochastic damage scenarios that correspond to the sampled earthquake events (see Figure 46).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32					
49	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1				
50	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			
51	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
52	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
53	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
54	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
55	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
56	3	3	2	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1			
57	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
58	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
59	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
60	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
61	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
62	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
63	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
64	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
65	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
66	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
68	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
69	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
70	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1

Figure 46. Extract of the generated catalogue of stochastic damage scenarios, showing the sampled damage states for bridges #1-#32 in scenarios #49-#70.

12.3.2 Computation of recovery and resilience measures with the agent-based model

For each sampled scenario of bridge damage states, the agent-based model developed by Sun et al. (2021) is applied in order to estimate various metrics in the recovery phase, such as the time-varying percentage of functional bridges, the number of bridges under repair, the evolution of the shortest path between two locations of the network, or the total duration until the whole network is restored. The agent-based model accounting for several constraints, such as the time taken to repair bridges given their damage states, and the time taken to deliver material and repair crews to the target bridge locations (while accounting for the degraded functionality of the road network). In Figure 47, the last column shows an example of a recovery metric (total recovery time of the whole network in days), which has been estimated with the agent-based model for each bridge damage scenario. This metric is selected as the performance measure of interest for the rest of the demonstration.

	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119
49	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
50	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
51	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
52	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
53	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
54	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
55	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
56	3	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	3	2	3	658
57	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
58	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
59	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
60	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
61	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12.5000
62	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
63	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	710
64	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
65	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
66	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
67	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
68	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	58
69	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
70	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	248.5000

Figure 47. Extract of the generated DSM, showing the sampled damage states for bridges #107-#118 in scenarios #49-#70, and the performance measure of interest (last column, representing the total recovery time in days).

12.3.3 Data mining on the Damage State Matrix

Various ranking and classification methods are applied to the DSM, in order to identify which components have the most influence on the distribution of the performance measures:

- **Correlation measure:** the DSM is used to assemble a correlation matrix, and the bridges that are the most correlated with the performance measure are selected.
- **Classification Tree (CT):** a decision tree is built by progressively splitting the domain space described by the states of the components, until homogeneous regions with respect to the target variable (i.e., the system performance measure of interest) are created.
- **Random Forest (RF):** the random forest classification relies on the stochastic generation of a large number of classification trees, using bootstrap sampling. The bootstrap sampling is carried out on two levels, namely (i) on the simulation outcomes (i.e., removal of some rows of the DSM) before each classification tree is built, and (ii) on the components to consider (i.e., removal of some columns of the DSM), for each decision split in the classification tree.
- **Regression Tree (RT):** a regression tree is similar to a classification tree, but it is more suited to continuous quantities.

In the present example, it is proposed to select a subset of $k = 20$ bridges. As shown in Table 4, the various ranking methods lead to different subset selections.

Table 4. Results of the ranking and classification algorithms. Selected bridges are ranked by decreasing order of influence.

Rank	Selected bridge IDs			
	Correlation	RF	RT	CT
#1	117	50	118	118
#2	116	11	117	45
#3	68	43	68	55
#4	111	7	89	46
#5	89	83	111	117
#6	118	9	116	5
#7	52	46	52	47
#8	55	45	109	1
#9	88	8	88	12
#10	108	4	66	59
#11	109	5	30	89
#12	66	21	45	4
#13	5	73	46	64
#14	46	52	96	66
#15	12	55	55	9
#16	45	1	99	108
#17	64	12	108	30
#18	59	68	44	52
#19	30	30	5	116
#20	47	109	47	111

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
160	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	3	1	2	1	3	2	2	1	2
161	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	2	1	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
162	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
163	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	3	2	3	1	3	3	3	1	2
164	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	2
165	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	1	3	1	3	1	3	3	2	1	2
166	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	3	1	3	1	3	1	3	3	3	1	3
167	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
168	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
169	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
170	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
171	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1
172	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	2	1
173	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	2	1
174	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
175	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
176	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1
177	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	2
178	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
179	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
180	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
181	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1

Figure 48. Extract of the table of unique damage configurations for the subset of 20 selected bridges (using correlation measure as ranking method), showing damage configurations #160-#181.

Then, in the DSM, only the k columns corresponding the selected subset of bridges are kept. The 10,000 sampled lines are reduced to a number m of unique damage configurations for only k bridges. For instance, when the correlation measure is used for the ranking, $m = 868$ unique damage configurations are extracted from the DSM (see Figure 48). This table of unique damage configurations constitutes the so-called learning dataset from Figure 45.

Figure 49. Distribution of the sampled recovery times for 4 specific damage configurations of the subset of bridges. The combinations [1...1] indicate the damage states of the 20 selected bridges (here, the correlation measure is used as the ranking method).

Finally, for each unique damage configuration of the subset, matching sampled configurations are extracted from the DSM (over the whole set of bridges), in order to assemble statistics of the performance measure. An example is shown in Figure 49, where the total recovery time is shown as a histogram for specific damage configurations of the subset.

12.3.4 Application of the BN to an arbitrary earthquake event

The BN framework developed in Work Package 4 (Task 4.5) is adapted to the present objective. The BN is implemented and solved in the OpenBUGS software (Lunn et al., 2009): thanks to a Markov-chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) sampling scheme, it is able to model both discrete and continuous variables.

As a result, for a given earthquake event with some field observations, the output of the MCMC sampling consists of thousands of damage combinations for the 118 bridges, depending on the length of the MCMC chains. Each of these sampled outcomes can then be associated with one of the subset damage configurations (Figure 48), and in turn with one of the distributions of the performance measure Figure 49). If no corresponding subset damage configuration can be found for a given sampled outcome, the subset size is reduced (i.e., the least influent bridge is removed from the subset, and so on), until matching damage configurations are found.

The BN is tested with a hypothetical earthquake event, of magnitude M_w 6.3 and epicenter location (lon 0.60° , lat 42.65°). It is assumed that 7 seismic stations have recorded the strong motion in the area (Table 5), and that the damage states of 5 bridges have been identified (Table 6), constituting the field observations that are fed into the BN.

Table 5. Hypothetical PGA measurements from the surrounding seismic stations.

Station ID	Longitude	Latitude	PGA [m/s^2]
#1	0.7973	43.0119	0.4093
#2	0.8181	42.7076	2.0003
#3	0.7981	42.7027	0.9828
#4	0.6014	42.7906	1.7366
#5	0.5986	42.7920	0.4001
#6	0.5977	42.7988	5.6893
#7	0.7467	42.8660	2.6933

Table 6. Hypothetical damage states on some bridges, resulting from structural monitoring.

Bridge ID	Longitude	Latitude	Damage State
#35	0.6392	42.9149	D1
#43	0.7468	42.8664	D1
#80	0.6032	42.7729	D2
#88	0.6102	42.7449	D2
#99	0.5609	42.8065	D3

The BN results for the estimation of the recovery time based on the learning procedure are detailed in Figure 50 and Figure 51, respectively regarding the prior (only the knowledge of the earthquake's characteristics) and the posterior distributions (accounting for field observations).

The results show that prior estimates are almost evenly distributed over several intervals of recovery duration, meaning that the generated damage scenarios are not very informative regarding the temporal extent of the disruption. The observations that are entered in the BN mostly paint an aggravated picture of the situation (e.g., high PGA values recorded, several damaged bridges): therefore, the posterior distribution of the recovery time evolves towards much longer durations than the prior, as expected. Moreover, it can be seen that the posterior

estimates follow a sharper distribution, showing the benefits of accounting for field observations when propagating uncertainties.

Figure 50. Estimates of the prior distribution of the recovery time, accounting only for the magnitude and epicentre location of the earthquake event, using the 4 different ranking methods.

Figure 51. Estimates of the posterior distribution of the recovery time, accounting for immediate field observations, using the 4 different ranking methods.

13 CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE

This section of the report introduces alternative approaches that will be used in the TURNkey project to model the potential effect that the use of the TURNkey Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response (*FWCR*) platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.

Section 4.1 describes how Analytical Hierarchy Process (*AHP*) modelling will be used to analyse the potential impact of the TURNkey platform on businesses, critical infrastructure and community resilience. As outlined in *Deliverable 5.2* (Phase 1), resilience will be modelled holistically and include factors regarding disaster preparedness, response and recovery. Accordingly, a hybrid model is developed that includes both the engineering and socio-ecological aspects of seismic resilience. This *Section* starts with a general introduction that describes how such a *Deliverable* builds on the work carried out under *D5.1*. It then goes on to provide an overview of *AHP* modelling and describes how the degree of inconsistency in an *AHP* hierarchy can be measured. The section concludes with an overview as to how this approach will be applied.

Section 13.2 describes how System Dynamics (*SD*) modelling will be used to analyse disaster operations during the rapid recovery phase. As discussed in *Deliverable 5.2* (Phase 1), a modelling method that incorporates a range of factors (such as data, decisions and policy) into one dynamic system, lends itself well to modelling multiple stakeholders with different objectives working towards the common goal of recovery following a destructive earthquake. Furthermore, the *SD* process is appropriate for modelling stakeholder interactions because it relies on mediated modelling. Mediated modelling helps to build consensus regarding the goal of the model in small steps, by constructing a simulation model and running scenarios to evaluate the desirability of the potential outcomes of various actions (Van den Belt, 2004). *SD* modelling will involve a combination of desk and field-based studies within the two Icelandic field sites of TURNkey in north and south Iceland, and interviews with the Icelandic TURNkey project partners.

13.1 Modelling the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquakes - methodological approach

As part of Deliverable D1.2, Jones (2020) mapped the potential impacts that the earthquake early warning and operational earthquake forecasting tools, forming the basis of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform, could have on the range of resilience factors and indicators that are used in the majority of community resilience models currently employed across the world. Deliverable D5.1 (Jones et al. 2020b) extended the review work done by both Jones (2016, 2020) and Morga et al. (2020) to identify a range of performance metrics that could be used to assess the impact that the TURNkey *FWCR* platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events. In particular, Deliverable D5.1 (Jones et al. 2020b) sought to identify the logical links between the components of the *FWCR* platform (Operational

Earthquake Forecasting, Earthquake Early Warning, and Rapid Response to Earthquakes) and earthquake resilience expressed in terms of the critical requirements derived from the end-user use cases developed in Deliverable D1.4 (Jones, 2020a) and to map these against a range of metrics derived from the latest resilience theory and toolkits (see Table 15, and Tables 17 to 22 in Deliverable D5.1 for details). Deliverable D5.1 concluded that resilience (business, critical infrastructure and community) is shaped by a combination of physical, organisational, operational, and governance factors and that the metrics contained in the UNDRR scorecards⁴,⁵ and REDi TM rating system⁶ could form the basis of models to assess the potential impacts of the TURNkey FWCR platform on business and community resilience to earthquake events. Deliverable D5.1 also concluded that, whilst none of the critical infrastructure resilience frameworks or metrics fully address the resilience issues associated with critical infrastructure organisations, an extension developed by Morga et al. (2020) in the LIQUEFACT project provided a good starting point to develop a new framework in the TURNkey project. Deliverable D5.2 will extend the work of D5.1 by considering how individual metrics can be aggregated within an AHP framework model to obtain a measure of organisation, critical infrastructure and community resilience to earthquake events.

An initial (theoretical) mapping of United Nation Disaster Risk Reduction (*UNDRR*) scorecard against the *FWCR* platform can be found in Deliverable D5.1. This mapping will be validated during the participatory action research (*PAR*) (currently underway in TURNkey Work Package 2) and this Deliverable. The decision to use the *UNDRR* scorecard as the basis for assessing community resilience to earthquake events is also consistent with the work of Burton et al. (2017) who developed and validated a scorecard methodology similar to the *UNDRR* Scorecard, and with the work of Morga et al. (2020) who customised the *UNDRR* scorecard for earthquake induced liquefaction disaster events in the LIQUEFACT project.

Building on these premises, the extensive review conducted in D5.1 for organisational resilience and the critical review of relevant literature relating to infrastructure resilience and community resilience models reported in section 2.5 of this document, this section will:

- discuss the role of the *AHP* as the basis for evaluating the potential impact that the TURNkey *FWCR* platform could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience;
- present hypothetical examples showing how *AHP* models can be applied to business, critical infrastructure organisations and the wider community;
- outline the next steps in the development of the *AHP* models as part of the 3rd *APR* cycle.

The work presented in this section should be considered as a work in progress which will be amended and modified throughout the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified through the participatory action research programme.

⁴ Available at www.undrr.org/publication/disaster-resilience-scorecard-cities

⁵ Available at www.preventionweb.net/files/69845_undrrbuildingscorecardfinalv1.3.pdf

⁶ Available at www.arup.com/perspectives/publications/research/section/redi-rating-system

13.1.1 Modelling Resilience to Earthquake Events using the AHP/ANP

Many researchers (Alshehri et al. 2015, Bruneau et al. 2003, Cimellaro et al. 2010, Cutter 2013, Dojutrek et al. 2016, Linkov et al. 2006, Orencio and Fujii 2012, Morga et al. 2020, Prior 2015, Xu et al. 2020, Zhong et al. 2020) have identified the need to apply multi-criteria methods that support the integration of both quantitative and qualitative data into integrated models of resilience to disaster events. Whilst the approaches adopted by each author vary, more recent studies (Xu et al. 2020, Zhong et al. 2020) have tended to develop hierarchical models of the system under consideration (in terms of the system factors) that affect resilience and then apply prioritisation techniques (e.g. the analytic hierarchy/network process) to evaluate the impact that changes to factors in the hierarchy have on system resilience.

The *AHP* (Saaty 1990) is a method for resolving a complex decision-making problem into a hierarchy of a primary goal (community resilience) and component levels (e.g. the *UNDRR* Essentials) comprising sub-components (e.g. areas) and subjects/issues (metrics). Priorities are then established at the subject/issues, sub-component and component levels through pairwise comparison. By evaluating the impact that different potential solutions have on each metric the relative importance of the subject/issue can be calculated at the sub-component level; the importance of each sub-component can be calculated at the component level; and the importance of each component can be calculated against the primary goal. Saaty (1990) extended the AHP approach to accommodate a more complicated modelling arrangement in which a number of inter-related hierarchies co-exist within a system. To model these multiple hierarchies, and to account for feedback between the hierarchies Saaty (*ibid*) developed the analytic network process (*ANP*) (Saaty 1996). The *ANP* follows the same principles as the *AHP* method.

The *AHP* and the *ANP* were developed by Thomas Saaty (1990, 1996) as a selection and prioritisation methodology which allows decision makers to evaluate the impact of alternate interventions on complex problems by evaluating individual impacts that interventions have at different levels in a hierarchy (Figure 52).

Figure 52. The Analytical Hierarchy Process.

The *AHP* structures a system in terms of its goal; the criteria/sub-criteria (components and elements) layers represent the various objectives pertinent to that goal, expressed as children of the objectives, grandchildren of the objectives, great-grandchildren of the objectives etc; and the bottom layer of the hierarchy contains all the alternative approaches to the resolution of the problem.

Once the fundamental hierarchy has been established, the relative importance of the objectives in achieving the goal are determined through pair-wise comparisons. Each objective is compared against the others in the objective layer to determine each objective's importance in achieving the goal (e.g. the relative importance of C1, C2 ... Cn in achieving the primary goal; the relative importance of C11, C12, ... C1n in achieving objective C1). Comparisons are repeated in this way for every layer of the hierarchy.

Comparisons are made using a 1-9 numeric scale that translates qualitative statements into numeric scores (Table 7) expressed as a priority vector.

Table 7. Pairwise comparison scoring system (source: Saaty 1990)

Qualitative Statement	Numeric score
Equal importance	1
Moderate importance of one over another	3
Strong essential importance	5
Very strong or demonstrated importance	7
Extreme importance	9
Intermediate values	2, 4, 6, 8
Use of reciprocal is for inverse comparisons	

The calculation of the priority vector for a typical 3 criteria model is demonstrated in Saaty (1990) and repeated here.

Firstly, we need to establish the relative importance of the 3 criteria to each other. In this example, criteria C2 is considered to be between equally and moderately more important than criteria C1 so a numeric score of 2 is assigned. Criteria C3 is considered to be between moderately and strongly more important than criteria C1 so a numeric score of 4 is assigned. Criteria C3 is considered to be between equally and moderately more important than criteria C2 so a score of 2 is assigned (Table 8).

Table 8. Priority scores

	C1	C2	C3
C1	1	1/2	1/4
C2	2	1	1/2
C3	4	2	1
Column Total	7	3.5	1.75

The priority scores are normalised by dividing each entry in each column by the sum of the entries in the column. The overall relative priorities across the three criteria are calculated by summing the scores in each row and dividing by the number entries in each row Table 9.

Table 9. Normalised matrix and priority score

	C1	C2	C3	Priority Vector
C1	0.1428	0.1428	0.1428	0.1428
C2	0.2857	0.2857	0.2857	0.2857
C3	0.5714	0.5714	0.5714	0.5714

In this example, because all the pairwise comparisons used to construct the priority matrix are internally consistent, we can conclude that C1 accounts for 14.28% of the final goal, C2 accounts for 28.57% of the final goal and C3 accounts for 57.14% of the final goal.

However, internal consistency cannot always be guaranteed so Saaty (1990) provides a mechanism to check the level of inconsistency within any set of pairwise comparisons.

When the matrix is consistent the sum of entries in each row provides a measure of the dominance of one element over the other's in achieving the goal and the sum of the entries in each column tells us how much one element is dominated by the others. For consistent matrices the elements in the columns should be the reciprocal of the elements in the rows; and both should be equal to 1.0. Further, the product of the column sums and normalised row sums should equal n (the number of entities). However, when the matrices are inconsistent these relationships do not hold. If the matrices are inconsistent then the product sum is greater than 1.0 and dividing the difference by n gives us a measure of the inconsistency.

Saaty (1990) presents a numeric methodology for calculating the level of inconsistency by raising the judgement matrix by large powers (e.g. by squaring it, then squaring it again etc.)

and calculating the normalised vector until the point at which the difference between iterations is within acceptable accuracy limits. At which point the normalised vector represents the principal eigenvector of the matrix whose associated eigenvalue λ_{max} can be used to calculate inconsistency of judgements.

Repeating the previous example (again extracted from Saaty 1990) for an inconsistent matrix (Tables 10 and 11) gives

Table 10. Inconsistent judgment matrix

	C1	C2	C3
C1	1	1/2	1/4
C2	2	1	1/4
C3	4	4	1
Column Total	7	5.5	1.5

Table 11. Normalised matrix and priority score

	C1	C2	C3	Priority Vector (PV)
C1	0.1429	0.0909	0.1667	0.1334
C2	0.2857	0.1818	0.1667	0.2114
C3	0.5714	0.7273	0.6667	0.6551

As can be seen by comparing Table 9 and Table 11 the priority vector has changed. We can compare the degree of change to that which would be expected if the judgements were all randomly generated by multiplying the first column of the inconsistent judgement matrix (Table 12) by the relative priority of C1 (0.1334), multiplying the 2nd column by the relative priority of C2 (0.2114), and the 3rd column by the relative priority of C3 (0.6551) and summing the entities in each row (Table 12).

Table 12. Totalling the entries

	C1	C2	C3	Row Totals
C1	0.1334	0.1057	0.1638	0.4029
C2	0.2668	0.2114	0.1638	0.642
C3	0.5336	0.8456	0.6551	2.034

If we now divide the column of row totals (Table 12) by the corresponding entry in the priority vector (Table 5 and average the entries in the final column (Table 13) we get an approximation of $\lambda_{max} = 3.054$.

Table 13. Determining λ_{max}

Row Total (RT)	Priority Vector (PV)	RT/PV
0.4029	0.1334	3.0202
0.642	0.2114	3.0369
2.034	0.6551	3.1049

The consistency index (CI) where $n = 3$ can then be calculated by $(\lambda_{\max} - n)/n-1 = (3.054 - 3)/2 = 0.027$ which can be compared with the random value of CI for $n=3$ of 0.52 (obtained by Saaty from a sample of 500 matrices) to obtain the consistency ratio $(0.027/0.52) = 0.052$ which is better than the 10% normal accepted limit.

Finally, a sensitivity analysis should be carried out by varying the priorities of each criterion to determine their influence on the goal and stability of the decision to be tested.

Whilst *AHP* has many advantages, including its ability to measure both tangible and intangible criteria (Saaty and Sagir 2009), to measure the consistency and stability of a decision, to be used alongside other processes such as goal programming (Sarkis and Sundarraj, 2001) it also has a number of weaknesses including:

- the possibility of rank reversal;
- it is an additive complete aggregation tool which can allow good scores to compensate for bad scores;
- as the hierarchy is made up of objectives and various levels of sub-objectives the amount of pairwise decisions to be made can be quite extensive, and
- the process can become quite time consuming (Macharis et al. 2004);
- the 9-point scale can be problematic as a decision maker may not be able to determine the difference between the values during the pairwise process. Hajkowicz et al. (2000) reduced the 9 point scale to a 3 point scale to overcome this problem, requiring the decision maker to determine if one criterion was more, less or equal important than the other.

Saaty (1996) developed the *Analytic Network Process (ANP)* as a generalised version of *AHP* to accommodate the modelling of complex problems where interaction and interdependency are better described in an influence network of clusters and nodes rather than a simple one-dimensional hierarchy of criteria. By adopting a multi-dimensional approach, *ANP* not only considers the relative importance of criteria to determine the impact that alternative solutions can have on achieving the goal, but also models the interaction between alternatives allowing for feedback to support future (as opposed to present) goals.

Whilst *ANP* uses the same basic pairwise comparison for establishing priorities between criteria, it is not structured as a top-to bottom hierarchy but as an interconnected network of clusters of elements where elements in one cluster are connected to elements in another cluster (outer dependence) or to elements in the same cluster (inner dependence). Outer dependence describes the influence that elements in one cluster have on elements in another cluster with respect to a control criterion (note: control criterion are multiple outcomes from the model, e.g. improved resilience to earthquake events). Inner dependence describes the influence of elements within a cluster on each other. By considering outer and inner dependency *ANP* allows us to reflect the views of different stakeholders and to model the interdependency between them (Figure 53).

Figure 53. Feedback network with components having inner and outer dependences among their elements (Source: Saaty 1996).

In relation to Figure 53, the arrows between *clusters* indicates the outer dependence of elements in C_i on the elements in C_j with respect to a common property; while the loop-in a *cluster* indicates inner dependence of the elements in that *cluster* with respect to a common property. By way of comparison, a hierarchy can be considered as a one-directional network in which the levels in the hierarchy correspond to the clusters in a network

The process of decision making requires us to analyse a decision according to its *benefits*, *opportunities*, *costs* and *risks*. *Benefits* (B) are the positive outcomes that would result from taking the decision; *Opportunities* (O) are the potentially positive outcomes that can result in the future from taking the decision; *Costs* (C) are the negative outgoings that would result from taking the decision; and *Risks* (R) are the potential negative outgoings that can result from taking the decision. The *BOCR* are known as the ‘four merits’.

In developing an *ANP* model the pairwise comparison matrices are entered into a super matrix in which steady-state priorities are sought (note: in complex problems not all super matrices will converge). Whilst *ANP* modelling is inherently complicated and mathematically demanding, software solutions have been developed (e.g. <http://www.superdecisions.com> <http://www.transparentchoice.com/>) to guide the user through the modelling process. In addition, Saaty and Sagor (2006) identified 12 steps to develop an *ANP* model. These are:

13. Describe the decision problems objectives, criteria/sub criteria, actors and their objectives and possible outcomes. Give details of influences that determine how that decision is made.
14. Determine the control criteria/sub criteria in the 4 decision control hierarchies (benefits, opportunities, costs and risks) of the decision and obtain priorities from paired comparison matrices.
15. Determine the most general network of clusters (or components) and their elements that apply to all control criteria.

16. For each control criterion/sub criterion, determine the clusters of the general feedback system with their elements and connect them according to their outer and inner dependence influences.
17. Determine the approach to follow in the analysis of each cluster or element, influencing other clusters and elements with respect to a criterion, or being influenced by other clusters and elements.
18. For each control criterion, construct a super matrix.
19. Perform pairwise comparisons on the elements within the clusters themselves according to their influence on each element in another cluster they are connected to (outer dependence) or on elements in their own cluster (inner dependence).
20. Perform pairwise comparisons on the clusters as they influence each cluster to which they are connected with respect to the given control criterion.
21. Compute the limit priorities of the stochastic super matrix according to whether it is irreducible or reducible.
22. Synthesise the limiting priorities by weighting each idealised limit vector by the weight of each control criterion and adding the resulting vectors for each of the 4 control criteria (the benefits, opportunities, costs and risks, i.e. the 4 (*BOCR*) merits).
23. Determine strategic criteria and their priorities to rate the 4 *BOCR* merits one at a time. Normalise the 4 ratings and use them to calculate the overall synthesis by subtracting the costs and risks from the sum of the benefits and opportunities.
24. Perform a sensitivity analysis on the final outcome.

Inconsistency is one of the fundamental problems encountered by those using *AHP/ANP* pairwise comparisons in decision-making. Inconsistency occurs when the internal mathematical logic linking the relative importance of one criterion to another fails. By way of example, consider that you are comparing 3 criteria (A, B and C). Suppose you answer (using Saaty's 9 point judgement scale) that A is 3B (i.e. A is moderately more important than B) and that B is 2C (i.e. B is slightly less than moderately more important than C). Using mathematical logic then A must = 6C (i.e. A is between strongly and very strongly more important than C). The problem is in *AHP* we don't ask people to use mathematical logic but to use qualitative statements that are then converted using Saaty's 9-point judgement scale. This approach inevitably introduces the risk of inconsistency, either because:

- people by nature make inconsistent judgements;
- people don't have enough information to make consistent judgements;
- the use of Saaty's discrete scale doesn't provide a consistent direct numerical comparison either because there is no direct comparison score in the scale (e.g. suppose you score $A=2B$ and $A=3C$ then for consistency $B=1.5C$ but we do not have a 1.5 numeric score on Saaty's scale) or because the logic numeric score greater than that allowed on the scale (e.g. suppose

you score $A=3B$ and $B=4C$ for consistency $A=12C$ but we do not have a 12 numeric score on Saaty's scale). Whilst the problem of inconsistency is well known; so are the steps that can be taken to reduce inconsistency within an *AHP* model. The following guidance is provided by Opydo (2020) for reducing inconsistency:

- keep the number of components in any branch/level of the hierarchy to as few as possible, and always less than 9;
- don't compare components that exhibit large differences in priority (if one or more components dominate the branch/level of the hierarchy then they are probably in the wrong level;
- when eliciting qualitative scores from people, encourage them to use the lower end of Saaty's scale. The elicitation of pairwise comparisons requires a degree of expertise and practice on behalf of the facilitator;
- avoid obvious contradictions in pairwise comparisons by using such contradictions to explore the underlying relationships upon which people are basing their judgements (i.e. question the logic of their qualitative scoring).

It is worth noting that inconsistency in itself is not a problem; but the degree of inconsistency can be. In real world situations some level of inconsistency is to be expected (in fact a perfectly consistent *AHP* model should raise concerns about its validity amongst researchers/users).

As described above, the degree of inconsistency in an *AHP* hierarchy can be measured by its consistency ratio. Saaty (1990) developed a methodology for comparing the level of inconsistency within an *AHP* model to that which would be expected from a randomly generated model having the same number of components. Saaty (1990) suggested that a consistency ratio of less than 10% should be acceptable for the majority of applications (although lower values can be used if required).

As outlined, the *AHP/ANP* approach described in this section will be used to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey *FWCR* platform on community resilience. *AHP* will be used to develop hierarchy models for the impact that TURNkey *FWCR* could have on business, critical infrastructure and community resilience against the criteria discussed in D5.1. The potential of *ANP* to develop a *BOCR* model of the impact that TURNkey could have will be undertaken as part of the final stage of the participatory action research programme in WP6 and WP7.

13.2 Developing an *AHP* model of organisational resilience

TURNkey Deliverable D5.1 critiqued a range of physical, operational and organisational factors that affect the resilience of business (and critical infrastructure) organisations to disaster events, and reviewed how these factors were represented in resilience scorecards and models for the management of disaster related risk.

In considering the management of disaster related risk, D5.1 drew on the work of Gibson and Tarrant (2010) who highlighted the need to consider resilience as a dynamic outcome comprising a combination of factors that vary with context and not as a process management system that can be applied at a single point in time. This approach, in essence, is similar to that adopted by the Sendai Framework for disaster risk reduction (UNDRR 2015) which places emphasis for resilience on managing disaster risk rather than managing the disaster event (as the Kyoto Framework did, UNFCCC 1997). In seeking to manage disaster risk, models need to consider resilience as a multidimensional concept viewed from complementary perspectives (physical, operational, corporate) that reflect different organisational context (e.g. antecedent resilience, vulnerability and exposure of different functional units within the organisation) and risk management strategies, which in turn need to integrate disaster management and business continuity planning for both hard (physical) and soft (human and financial) organisational elements to identify the organisation's resilience capability.

D5.1 also drew on the work of Lee et al. (2013), who viewed an organisation's resilience capabilities in terms of its resilience strengths and weaknesses that should be managed as part of a journey towards becoming more resilient (Lee et al. 2013). To support an organisation along their journey Lee et al. (ibid) identified situational awareness; management of key vulnerabilities; and adaptive capacity, expressed through a series of indicators (criteria), as key attributes of a resilience strategy that could be used to understand the complex multidisciplinary sociotechnical phenomena (as they perceived organisational resilience to be) that underpins an organisation's resilience improvement strategy (Relative Overall Resilience model). An indicator (criteria) based approach understanding organisational resilience also forms the basis of the REDiTM (Almufti et al. 2014) rating system for resilience-based earthquake building design and UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings (2020). Although the REDiTM (ibid) rating system was primarily developed to inform technical design standards (physical resilience), it also considers the role of operational and corporate resilience in informing design decisions. From a physical resilience perspective REDiTM seeks to minimise earthquake damage to structural and non-structural systems through earthquake resistant design or a better understanding of structural behaviour in response to an earthquake to minimise business disruption (downtime). From an operational and corporate perspective REDiTM recognises the importance of contingency planning for reducing repair times and minimising the effect of disruption to utilities needed to support business function and to reduce the impact of losses (logistics and financial) on business function. Although the REDiTM rating system is intended as a design aid the authors would argue that the principles underpinning it are compatible with a retrospective analysis of organisational resilience.

The UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings (2020) was developed to support the implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction by providing a framework to help building owners, operators and managers understand the resilience of their built assets and to the impact that their organisation has on

wider community resilience. The Scorecard comes in 2 versions, a summary scorecard comprising 33 assessment areas and a detailed scorecard comprising 116 assessment areas. Both versions of the scorecard group the assessment areas into one of 10 essentials that address governance, planning and preparation, and response and recovery actions. Each assessment area has a 0-5 indicative performance measurement scale, accompanied by qualitative statements about what would typically be expected at each level of performance. The Scorecard assumes that each of the assessment areas is of equal importance to overall building resilience; thus, no weightings are applied to the resilience calculations. If an assessment area does not apply to the building being assessed, it is left blank (in the data gathering spreadsheets) so as not to appear in the final resilience score. The authors would suggest that the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings represents the most up-to-date and comprehensive metric-based approach to assessing organisational resilience.

Finally, Deliverable D5.1 argued that organisational resilience is shaped by a combination of physical, operational, and corporate factors that can be effectively modelled as a 2 level hierarchy (Figure 54) where the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform can be assessed on each branch of the hierarchy (physical, operational and corporate resilience and on overall organisation resilience by assigning metric scores to the level 2 criteria (using a similar methodology to that in the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings) and by applying weightings to the metric scores at both level 1 and level 2 of the hierarchy to reflect organisational and situational specific context.

The generic hierarchy model outlined in Figure 54 was derived by synthesising the key factors that affect organisational resilience. In synthesising the factors consideration was given to the scope and complexity of the factors and to the ability of an organisation to make a qualitative judgement as to the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on earthquake risk management. During the consolidation process consideration was given to potential double scoring of the factors (e.g. factors associated with damage prevention replicate to some extent factors associated with contingency planning and continuity planning. Furthermore, contingency planning and continuity planning could effectively be argued to be the same activity). Also, during the consolidation process factors which were assigned to levels 3 and 4 were removed from the model, but retained as part of the justification for why the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have an impact on the level 2 criteria (e.g. when assessing the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform on damage control, production, contents - consolidated to production resilience in the AHP model - consideration would be given to the impact TURNkey could have on vulnerability, auto control, repair time through the use of warning systems, and post-earthquake inspection and mobilisation. Safety was considered a part of contingency planning and risk). The final AHP Organisational Resilience Model is shown in Figure 55. Note, although the model has been developed through reference to the latest disaster resilience literature any criteria in the model that are not directly relevant to an organisation (e.g. a virtual organisation may not have structural assets) can be removed.

Similarly, any criterion relevant to the organisation but not included in the model can be added. The model will be further refined during the validation of the TURNkey FWCR Platform with end-user organisations in Task 6.5 and during the development of the business case for TURNkey in Task 7.3.

Figure 54. Consolidated factors from UNDRR scorecard, REDiTM scorecard and Lee et al (2013).

Figure 55. Organisational Resilience Hierarchy Model (derived from The REDi™ Rating Scheme (Almufti et al. 2014), the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings (UNDRR, 2020) and Lee et. al. (2013))

13.2.1 Excel spreadsheet of the organisational resilience AHP model

The AHP model of organisational resilience to an earthquake was translated into an Excel spreadsheet to allow different modelling scenarios to be evaluated against a range of pairwise comparisons. The accuracy of the Excel model was tested using data extracted from Saaty (p84-p94, 3rd edition, 5th printing). The Excel model accurately reproduced the results presented by Saaty (ibid) using the approximate AHP methodology.

The spreadsheet model was built in 2 stages. Firstly, a spreadsheet model was built for each branch of the hierarchy (i.e. physical resilience, operational resilience, and corporate resilience). These 3 models were then combined in the 2nd stage model to assess the overall resilience to an earthquake. Two versions were developed of the organisational resilience model; one in which the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform on the level 2 criteria was modelled using pairwise comparison, and a second where the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform on the level 2 criteria was modelled using absolute scores. Both approaches are presented for comparison purposes. All pairwise comparisons were made using Saaty's 9-point scale (1 – Equal Importance, 3 – Moderate Importance, 5 – Strong Importance, 7 – Very Strong Importance, 9 – Extreme Importance, with scores of 2, 4, 6 and 8 used for intermediate values). Reciprocal values were used when a criterion was LESS important). A 6-point scale (1- no impact, 2 – very low impact, 3 – low impact, 4 – moderate impact, 5 – high impact, 6 – very high impact) was used for absolute scoring in an ideal (normalised) mode (see Saaty pp141 for more details).

To demonstrate the development process, a simplified model is presented here using hypothetical data. The impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform has on each leg of the hierarchy is evaluated using both pairwise and absolute scoring methods.

13.2.1.1 Overall Organisational Resilience Using Pairwise Scores

Physical Resilience Branch of the Model

The goal of the model is to minimise downtime as a consequence of damage to physical systems (structural systems, non-structural systems and production systems).

Using the pairwise comparisons:

- structural resilience is considered to be moderately more important than non-structural resilience.
- structural resilience is considered to be moderately more important than production resilience.
- non-structural resilience is considered to be equally - moderately more important than production resilience.

Result in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

	Structural	Non-structural	Production
Structural	1.0000	3.0000	3.0000
Non-structural	0.3333	1.0000	2.0000
Production	0.3333	0.5000	1.0000

The normalised comparison matrix produces the following priority vector (for future reference PV1):

	Priority Vector
Structural	0.5889
Non-structural	0.2519
Production	0.1593

A consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.0270 which gives a consistency ratio of 0.0518, which is less than the 10% consistency threshold (0.52 for n=3) identified by Saaty (1990). As such, the pairwise comparisons used in the model are considered to be internally consistent.

A pairwise comparison of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform could have on each of the bottom level criteria (i.e. structural systems, non-structural systems, production systems) produces three (2x2) comparison matrices:

- TURNkey would have an equal impact on structural resilience.
- TURNkey would have an equal-moderate impact on non-structural resilience.
- TURNkey would have a moderate impact on production resilience.

With associated priority vectors (for future reference PV2):

	Priority Vector (structural resilience)	Priority Vector (non-structural resilience)	Priority Vector (production resilience)
With TURNkey	0.5000	0.6667	0.7500
Without TURNkey	0.5000	0.3333	0.2500

Combining the product of the priority vectors from the normalised comparison matrix (PV1) with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors (PV2) produces a relative resilience score of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on an organisation's physical resilience.

	Resilience Score
With TURNkey	0.5818
Without TURNkey	0.4182

Thus, for the hypothetical test data used to validate the spreadsheet model, the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a positive impact on an organisation's physical resilience, although the absolute improvement cannot be determined from this model.

Operational Resilience Branch of the Model

A similar model was developed for operational resilience where the goal of the model was to minimise disruption.

Using the pairwise comparisons:

- contingency planning/risk management (subsequently referred to as contingency planning) is considered to be moderately more important than supply chain/external relationships (subsequently referred to as supply chain).
- contingency planning/risk management is considered to be equally-moderately more important than the disaster management and recovery (subsequently referred to as disaster management).
- Supply chain is considered to be equally as important as disaster management.

Result in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

	Contingency Planning	Supply Chain	Disaster Response
Contingency Planning	1.0000	3.0000	2.0000
Supply Chain	0.3333	1.0000	1.0000
Disaster Response	0.5000	1.0000	1.0000

The normalised comparison matrix produces the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Contingency Planning	0.5485
Supply Chain	0.2106
Disaster Response	0.2409

A consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.0092, which gives a consistency ratio of 0.0176, which is less than the 10% consistency threshold (0.52 for n=3) identified by Saaty (1990). As such, the pairwise comparisons used in model are considered to be internally consistent.

A pairwise comparison of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform has on each of the bottom level criteria (i.e. contingency planning, supply chain, disaster response) produces three comparison matrices:

- TURNkey would have a strong impact on contingency planning.
- TURNkey would have an equal-moderate impact on supply chains.
- TURNkey would have a moderate impact on disaster management.

With associated TURNkey priority vectors:

	Priority Vector (contingency planning)	Priority Vector (supply chain)	Priority Vector (disaster management)
With TURNkey	0.8333	0.6667	0.7500
Without TURNkey	0.1667	0.3333	0.2500

Combining the product of the priority vectors from the normalised comparison matrix with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors produces a relative score of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on an organisation's operational resilience.

	Resilience Score
With TURNkey	0.7782
Without TURNkey	0.2218

Again, the model would suggest that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have a positive impact on an organisation's operational resilience, and although the absolute improvement cannot be determined from this model, it would appear that the impact on organisational resilience would be more pronounced than the impact on physical resilience.

Corporate Resilience Branch of the Model

A third model was developed for corporate resilience where the goal of the model was to minimise losses.

Using the pairwise comparisons:

- financial resilience is considered to be strongly more important than and adaptive capacity.
- financial resilience is considered to be moderately more important than corporate image.
- adaptive capacity is considered to be equally as important as corporate image.

Result in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

	Financial resilience	Adaptive capacity	Corporate image
Financial resilience	1.0000	5.0000	3.0000
Adaptive capacity	0.2000	1.0000	1.0000
Corporate image	0.3333	1.0000	1.0000

The normalised comparison matrix produces the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Financial resilience	0.6555
Adaptive capacity	0.1578
Corporate image	0.1867

A consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.0146 which gives a consistency ratio of 0.0281 is less than the 10% consistency threshold (0.52 for n=3) identified by Saaty (1990). As such the pairwise comparisons used in model are considered to be internally consistent.

A pairwise comparison of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform has on each of the bottom level criteria (i.e. financial resilience, adaptive capacity, corporate image) produces three comparison matrices:

- TURNkey would have a moderate impact on financial resilience.
- TURNkey would have an equal impact on adaptive capacity.
- TURNkey would have a equal-moderate impact on corporate image.

With associated TURNkey priority vectors:

	Priority Vector (financial resilience)	Priority Vector (adaptive capacity)	Priority Vector (corporate image)
With TURNkey	0.7500	0.5000	0.6667
Without TURNkey	0.2500	0.5000	0.3333

Combining the product of the priority vectors from the normalised comparison matrix with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors produces a relative score of the impact that TURNkey could have on an organisation's corporate resilience.

	Resilience Score
With TURNkey	0.6950
Without TURNkey	0.3050

Again, the model would suggest that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have a positive impact on an organisation's corporate resilience, and although the absolute improvement cannot be determined from this model, it would appear that the impact on corporate resilience would be more pronounced than the impact on physical resilience, but slightly less pronounced than on operational resilience.

Overall Organisational Resilience

The final stage in the organisational AHP model is to integrate the level 2 scores with the pairwise ratings for the level 1 criteria where the goal was to improve overall organisational resilience to an earthquake.

Using the pairwise comparisons for level 1 criteria:

- physical resilience is considered to be strongly LESS important than operational resilience.
- physical resilience is considered to be equally-moderately LESS important than corporate resilience.
- operational resilience is considered to be moderately-strongly MORE important than corporate resilience

Results in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

	Physical resilience	Operational resilience	Corporate resilience
Physical resilience	1.0000	0.2000	0.5000
Operational resilience	5.0000	1.0000	4.0000

Corporate resilience	0.2000	0.2500	1.0000
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The normalised comparison matrix produces the following priority vector (for future reference PV3).

	Priority Vector
Physical resilience	0.1179
Operational resilience	0.6806
Corporate resilience	0.2014

A consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.0124, which gives a consistency ratio of 0.0238, which is less than the 10% consistency threshold (0.52 for $n=3$) identified by Saaty (1990). As such, the pairwise comparisons used in model are considered to be internally consistent.

Weighting factors for sub-criteria of physical resilience, operational resilience and corporate resilience are calculated by multiplying the priority vector for the level 1 criteria against the priority matrices for the level 2 (sub-criteria) (e.g. the priority vector for the sub-criteria associated with the physical resilience criteria (PV1) is multiplied by the priority vector value for the physical resilience criteria (0.1179 from PV3). The process is repeated for operational and corporate resilience criteria to obtain the impact weighting factor matrix, which represents the relative impact of each of the sub-criteria on the primary model goal: to improve organisational resilience to an earthquake.

The impact weighting factor matrix is:

	Physical Resilience	Operational Resilience	Corporate Resilience
Sub- criteria 1	0.0695	0.3733	0.1320
Sub- criteria 2	0.0297	0.1433	0.0318
Sub- criteria 3	0.0188	0.1640	0.0376

The impact of TURNkey on the goal is then calculated by the sum product of the impact weighting factor matrix and the priority vectors for each sub-criteria, with and without TURNkey.

This produces an overall organisational resilience score:

	Organisational Resilience
With TURNkey	0.7382
Without TURNkey	0.2618

This suggests that use of the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a positive impact on the organisation's overall resilience to an earthquake.

13.2.1.2 Overall Organisational Resilience Using Absolute Scores

An alternative method for assessing the impact of alternatives on an AHP hierarchy can be obtained by scoring the absolute impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the level 2 sub-criteria. The first part of the modelling (establishing the pairwise comparison of the criteria and sub-criteria) is exactly the same as the process described above. Where the absolute approach differs is in how it scores the effect that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the level 2 sub-criteria.

The first stage in applying an absolute scoring method is to develop a qualitative scale that can be used to assess the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on all of the level 2 sub-criteria. In this example a 6-point impact scale has been used.

A comparison intensity matrix and priority vector is developed for each branch of the AHP hierarchy model (i.e. physical resilience branch, operational resilience branch, and corporate resilience branch). Whilst individual comparison intensities and priority vectors can be developed for each branch, in this example a common comparison intensity matrix and priority vector has been developed in which the relative importance of TURNkey FWCR Platform is consistent across all sub-criteria.

The comparison intensity matrix for a 6 point impact scale is:

	Very high impact	High impact	Moderate impact	Low impact	Very low impact	No impact
Very high impact	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00
High impact	0.5	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00
Moderate impact	0.33	0.5	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00
Low impact	0.25	0.33	0.5	1.00	2.00	3.00
Very low impact	0.2	0.25	0.33	0.5	1.00	2.00
No Impact	0.17	0.2	0.25	0.33	0.5	1.00

The associated priority vector is (for future reference PV4):

	Priority vector
Very high impact	0.38
High impact	0.25
Moderate impact	0.16
Low impact	0.10
Very low impact	0.07
No impact	0.04

The priority vector is now used to assess the impact that TURNkey has on each of the sub-criteria in the model. For example, for the physical resilience branch of the AHP model, the priority vector (PV1) is multiplied by the weighting factor associated with the level of impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each of the sub-criteria. For example, if TURNkey was expected to have a very low impact on structural resilience, the priority vector score (0.5889) from PV1 would be multiplied by the very low impact vector score (0.07) from PV4. Similarly, if TURNkey was expected to have a moderate impact on non-structural resilience, the priority vector score associated with none structural resilience (0.2519) from PV1 would be multiplied by the moderate impact vector score (0.16) from PV4. The same process is applied to the final sub-criteria (production resilience) and the three scores combined to provide an assessment of the overall impact that TURNkey could have on the physical resilience branch of the overall organisational resilience hierarchy. Assuming that TURNkey would have a very low impact on all sub-criteria of the physical resilience branch would result in an overall score of 0.07 (which is consistent with the priority vector given in PV4).

Similarly, assuming that TURNkey would have a very high impact on all sub-criteria of the physical resilience branch would result in an overall score of 0.38 (which is again consistent with the priority vector given in PV4).

To extend the range of the impact scale, Saaty developed an alternative methodology for applying an absolute scoring regime by normalising the priority vector associated with the absolute scoring scale. Using the example above, and redistributing the ‘No impact’ score across the other impact levels (i.e. effectively setting a ‘No impact’ score to zero whilst maintaining the consistency of the ratio scale – the scale still sums to 1.00) results in the normalised ‘Ideal Mode⁷’ providing a normalised scoring scale between very low impact to very high impact and effectively ensuring that any sub-criteria on which the TURNkey FWCR Platform has no impact does not contribute to the overall impact score at either the criteria or overall goal levels.

The normalised priority vector for this example is (for future reference PV5):

	Priority Vector (Ideal Mode)
Very high impact	1.00
High impact	0.66
Moderate impact	0.42
Low impact	0.27
Very low impact	0.17
No impact	0.00

Finally, by applying the absolute (Ideal Mode) approach to all 3 branches of the organisational hierarchy model and evaluating the sum product of the impact scores and top-level pairwise comparisons (PV3) yields scores for the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each branch of the hierarchy and on overall organisational resilience to an earthquake.

Using as close an impact criteria as we can to the pairwise impact with and without TURNkey presented previously gives a low impact (0.24) on physical resilience, a high-moderate (0.52) impact on operational resilience and on corporate resilience. Overall, the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a moderate-high (0.46) impact on organisational resilience. These results are similar to those obtained using the pairwise methodology presented previously.

13.2.2 Modelling the potential impact of TURNkey FWCR platform of a hypothetical small business organisation

The example given above used hypothetical data that bore little or no resemblance to a real situation. The following example applies the absolute version of the AHP organisational resilience model to a hypothetical organisation drawn from a combination of organisations studied during the first two phases of the participatory action research programme to develop the end-user use-cases.

Whilst the data used is still hypothetical, it does more closely match the potential application of the TURNkey FWCR Platform to a typical small manufacturing business operating in a known

⁷ See Saaty (1990) pp 137 for more details of the Ideal mode

earthquake zone. Note: the data used does not represent any one organisation or location, but is an amalgam of data drawn across a range of organisations and locations.

13.2.2.1 Scenario: A typical small manufacturing organisation

A small manufacturing business producing a range of components for the automotive industry is reviewing its business continuity and resilience plans (including its disaster management plans) in response to recent increased seismic activity in its locality. The organisation has commissioned a local risk consultancy organisation to assess their current vulnerability and resilience to an earthquake event and assess whether the use of the TURNkey FWCR platform could improve their resilience to an earthquake. The risk consultancy organisation applied the absolute version of the AHP organisational resilience model to the manufacturing business.

The manufacturing business is located in a concrete frame building that was built in the 1950s and is not currently satisfying local seismic design codes. The building is structurally sound and in a reasonable state of general repair. The building accommodates a number of production units that produce a range of metal components for the local automotive industry. The building also accommodates general office space and associated support spaces (e.g. storage facilities, meeting rooms, restrooms, kitchens etc).

The risk consultancy organisation organised a one-day meeting with representatives of the manufacturing business to identify the relative importance of the criteria and sub-criteria in the AHP organisational resilience model and assess the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform could have on the resilience of the business. The impact that TURNkey could have was evaluated against a severe and a moderate earthquake scenario.

Overall goal the AHP model

To evaluate the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform could have on organisational resilience.

Pairwise comparison of top level criteria

Initial discussions between the risk consultants and the manufacturing business explored the relative importance of physical, operational and corporate resilience to the overall resilience of the business in terms of disruption to production (downtime). During these discussions, a consensus was reached that physical resilience of either the building or production systems would have the most impact on production. This said, the organisation believed that effective management of its operations immediately before, during and after an earthquake could minimise the length of disruption. The organisation believed that its corporate resilience was its lowest priority: it had a mature and stable customer base that they believed would return once production had been re-established and had good relationships with the local community. The one aspect of corporate resilience that was the weakest was their ability to adapt their production systems in the short-term (this would require relocating to alternative production facilities which was not currently part of their contingency planning). For these reasons the business rated:

- physical resilience as moderately-strongly more important than operational resilience.

- physical resilience as strongly more important than corporate resilience.
- operational resilience as equally-moderately more important than corporate resilience

The judgements were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.024) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Physical resilience	0.6806
Operational resilience	0.2014
Corporate resilience	0.1179

Pairwise comparison of Physical Resilience sub-criteria

Whilst the building the organisation occupied was in a good state of repair, it was not compatible with modern earthquake design. As such it was considered to be structurally vulnerable to a strong earthquake (resulting in structural damage that would need to be repaired before the building could be reoccupied) but only non-structurally vulnerable to a moderate earthquake (building could be occupied once minor repairs and clean-up operations had been completed). Whilst some production line facilities were considered to be vulnerable to ground shaking, the impact could be minimised if the equipment was placed in a 'safe-mode' before ground shaking occurred. For these reasons the business rated:

- structural resilience as moderately-strongly more important than non-structural resilience.
- structural resilience as moderately more important than production resilience.
- non-structural resilience as equally as important as production resilience.

The judgments were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.009) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Structural	0.6327
Non-structural	0.1749
Production	0.1924

Pairwise comparison of Operational Resilience sub-criteria

The organisation had contingency and risk management plans in place to deal with natural disasters (including earthquakes). Whilst these plans did not include the provision of alternative back-up facilities, they did include the ability for the organisation to carry a reasonable inventory of raw materials needed for production and spare parts to maintain production equipment. As such, the business thought that it could minimise the impact of short-term supply chain disruptions and it could manage its external relationships with its long-standing customers. The organisation also had internal resources (e.g. internal maintenance teams, short-term backup power supplies) to help it recover from the immediate aftermath of an earthquake. For these reasons the business rated:

- contingency planning/risk management as moderately-strongly more important than supply chain/external relationships;

- contingency planning/risk management as equally-moderately more important than the disaster management and recovery;
- supply chain/external relationships as moderately less important than disaster management.

The judgments were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.018) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Contingency Planning	0.5571
Supply Chain	0.1226
Disaster Response	0.3202

Pairwise comparison of Corporate Resilience sub-criteria

The organisation had been in existence for many years and was in a strong and stable financial position (it had significant liquid assets at its disposal). The organisation also had a good local market for its products and they did not believe that their customers could find alternative suppliers in the short-term. As such, they believed that if they effectively managed their customer relationships they should not lose too many customers, and may even gain more customers in the long-term. Customer relationship management was important to the organisation, which they perceived to be a fundamental part of their ‘responsible business’ corporate image. With regards to adaptive capacity, the organisation felt that it had both the human and financial reserves to adapt to any medium-and long-term changes in the market. For these reasons the business rated:

- financial resilience to be equally as important as adaptive capacity;
- financial resilience to be moderately less important than corporate image;
- adaptive capacity to be strongly less important as corporate image.

The judgments were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.028) and resulted in following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Financial resilience	0.1867
Adaptive capacity	0.1578
Corporate image	0.6555

With the pairwise comparisons established across the AHP model, the business organisation considered the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each sub-criteria. Potential impact was assessed by considering the end user use-cases developed to support the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform (see deliverables D1.4 and D2.6). Impact was scored using the 6 point Ideal Mode absolute scale. The impact score along with the justification for that score was recorded for future reference (Table 14).

Table 14. Impact of the TURNkey FWCR platform at the sub criteria level

Sub-criteria	Impact score	Justification
Structural resilience	Low (0.27)	Whilst TURNkey could not reduce the direct structural damage caused by an earthquake, an early warning would allow volatile distribution systems (e.g. gas supply) to be shut

		down thus minimising the potential for secondary explosion damage.
Non-structural resilience	moderate (0.42)	A forecast of heightened risk of ground shaking would initiate protective actions (e.g. temporary reinforcement, isolation of service distribution networks minimising secondary non-structural damage – water damage)
Production resilience	High (0.66)	Advanced warning of a potential earthquake, through a heightened risk forecast or as an early warning alert, could trigger the placing of vulnerable systems into a 'safe-mode'. This would reduce repair and disruption time.
Contingency planning / risk management	High (0.66)	A forecast of heightened risk of ground shaking would allow early activation of contingency plans to ensure that all health and safety systems were fully checked and functional. An earthquake alert would allow employees located in dangerous areas to evacuate or take other safety precautions. Together these would reduce risk of death or serious injury to employees.
Supply chain / external relationships	Moderate (0.42)	Forecast of heightened risk would allow production schedules to be modified to minimise internal disruption and smooth post-earthquake supply to customers thus reducing potential loss of customers and income.
Disaster response/recovery	High (0.66)	Forecast of heightened risk would allow disaster response and recovery teams to be placed on standby, thus minimising response time if an earthquake occurred. Temporary relocation of warehousing items to ground level would minimise potential damage to components needed to support production repair. Early deployment of backup systems (e.g. power generators and fuel supplies) would allow recovery to continue even if local/regional power infrastructure was disrupted. A return to full production levels ahead of competitors could result in new customers.
Financial resilience	None (0)	No immediate impact of TURNkey on the financial resilience of the business could be identified (potential loss of income from customers is covered in the supply chain/external relationships sub- criteria).
Adaptive capacity	None (0)	No immediate impact of TURNkey on adaptive capacity could be identified (potential medium term increase in customer base as a consequence of a more rapid recovery than immediate competitors is covered in the disaster response/recovery sub- criteria).
Corporate image (CSR)	Moderate (0.42)	Forecast of a heightened risk would allow detailed discussions with customers and the supply chain, allowing for better expectations management. Internal communication with employees would help reduce anxiety and mental stress. TURNkey could support enhanced training amongst employees.

Applying the above impact scores to the organisational hierarchy model suggests that the greatest impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the organisation would be on improved operational resilience (score of 0.63 or a high impact). TURNkey would have a lower impact on physical resilience (0.37 or a moderate impact) and an even lower impact on corporate resilience (0.28 or a low impact). TURNkey would be expected to have a moderate (0.41) impact on overall organisational resilience.

Given the above, the business organisation decided to investigate the potential impact that TURNkey could have on operational resilience in more detail before deciding on whether to invest time and effort in integrating the TURNkey system into their disaster management/business continuity and resilience plans.

The model was re-run for a moderate earthquake scenario. In this case, because the impacts of the earthquake on the physical resilience were considered to be less, the relative importance of physical resilience (compared to both operational and corporate resilience) on the overall organisational resilience was thought to be less. The relative importance between operational and corporate resilience on organisational resilience under a moderate earthquake scenario remained unchanged. The revised pairwise comparisons for the Level 1 criterion are:

- physical resilience as moderately more important than operational resilience.
- physical resilience as moderately-strongly more important than corporate resilience.
- operational resilience as equally-moderately more important than corporate resilience

Because the impact of a moderate earthquake on structural resilience would be lower the relative importance of structural resilience (compared to non-structural resilience and production resilience) was also perceived to be lower. However, due to the low likelihood of damage to production resilience the relative importance of non-structural resilience was perceived to be slightly more important than production resilience. The revised pairwise comparisons for physical resilience sub-criteria are:

- structural resilience as moderately less important than non-structural resilience.
- structural resilience as moderately less important than production resilience.
- non-structural resilience as equally-moderately more important than production resilience.

Whilst the severity of a moderate earthquake would have an impact on Operational and Corporate resilience sub-criteria, it was not believed that it would change the fundamental relative importance of the sub-criteria to each other. As such, the same pairwise comparisons we used for the moderate earthquake scenario as for the severe earthquake scenario.

Where differences were expected was in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the sub-criteria. The potential for TURNkey to affect the physical resilience was considered lower (very low impact on structural resilience; low impact on non-structural resilience; and a low impact on production resilience); as was the potential for TURNkey to affect operational resilience (moderate impact on contingency planning/risk management; very low impact on supply chain/external relationships; and a moderate impact on disaster response/recovery). TURNkey was expected to have a similar impact on corporate resilience as for the severe earthquake scenario (no impact on financial resilience; no impact on adaptive capacity; and a low impact on corporate image).

Running the model with the above would suggest that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a low impact on physical resilience (0.26); a moderate impact on operational resilience (0.39); and a very low impact on corporate resilience (0.18). Overall the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a low (0.28) impact on overall organisational resilience.

Finally, comparing the severe and moderate earthquake scenarios suggests that the expected impacts that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have is lower across all aspects of organisational resilience; the relative impact on physical operational and corporate resilience are nevertheless ranked in the same order as for the severe earthquake scenario, suggesting that the overall model is stable.

13.2.2.2 Sensitivity analysis

The final stage of the AHP modelling process is to assess the sensitivity of the model to changes in the pairwise comparisons and absolute scores given to the impact of the alternative solutions (in this case the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the sub-criteria).

Changes to the impact of pairwise importance weightings of the top-level criteria were made by calculating a base case scenario assuming that each of the top level criteria were of equal importance and then comparing this with analyses where each top level criteria was considered progressively more important (1 = equal importance; 3 = moderate importance; 5 = strong importance; 7 = very strong importance; 9 = extreme importance). The pairwise importance weightings of the sub-criteria were kept constant (i.e. the same as for the example presented above) as were the expected impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the sub-criteria.

The results of this analysis against the most severe and moderate earthquake scenarios for the example given above are shown in Table 15. Internal consistency was maintained in all the analyses. For the base case (top level criteria all of equal importance) TURNkey would be expected to have a moderate impact on overall organisational resilience (0.43) for the most severe earthquake scenario and a low impact (0.26) for the moderate earthquake scenario. For both earthquake scenarios, increasing the dominance of physical resilience and corporate resilience criteria resulted in a reduction in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have, whilst increasing the dominance of the operational resilience criteria resulted in an increase in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have, on overall organisational resilience. These findings were not unexpected given that the operational resilience branch of the hierarchy was dominant in the hypothetical scenario example.

Table 15. Impact of changing top level criteria weightings on overall organisational resilience

	Base Case	Moderate	Strong	Very Strong	Extreme
Severe earthquake scenario					
Physical resilience	0.43	0.40	0.39	0.39	0.39
Operational resilience	0.43	0.51	0.54	0.56	0.57
Corporate resilience	0.43	0.37	0.34	0.33	0.32
Moderate earthquake scenario					
Physical resilience	0.26	0.25	0.24	0.24	0.23
Operational resilience	0.26	0.32	0.34	0.35	0.36
Corporate resilience	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.20

Table 16 shows the effect of varying the pairwise comparisons of the sub-criteria of each branch of the organisational resilience hierarchy in turn and calculating the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each branch of the hierarchy, as well as on overall organisational resilience. The relative importance of the top-level criteria and the potential impact of TURNkey on each sub-criteria were the same as those used in the hypothetical scenario example. Internal consistency was maintained in all the analyses. A base case for each branch of the hierarchy was calculated by setting equal importance to all of the sub-criteria in the branch and keeping the relative importance of the sub-criteria in the other branches the same as the hypothetical scenario example. As the trends and patterns were the same for both the severe and moderate scenarios only the results of the severe earthquake scenario are shown in Table 16.

In Table 16 column 2 indicates which sub-criteria was dominant in the analysis. Columns 3-7 indicate the branch resilience score for different levels of dominance given to the sub-criteria. For example, the highlighted row of Table 16 should be read as follows. The row is part of the Physical Resilience branch of the hierarchy. Structural resilience is the dominant sub-criteria. The base resilience score (assuming all sub-criteria in this branch are equally important) is 0.45 - and the overall organisational resilience score is 0.47. The resilience scores (both for the branch and overall organisation) changes as the level of dominance changes (e.g., branch resilience score of 0.38 and overall resilience score of 0.42 for moderate level of dominance; branch resilience score of 0.35 and overall resilience score of 0.40 for strong level of dominance etc.).

Changing the relative dominance of the physical resilience branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on physical resilience from 0.32 (moderate-low) to 0.60 (high) and from 0.38 (moderate) to 0.57 (high-moderate) on overall organisational resilience. The relative dominance of production resilience is again expected given the high potential impact that TURNkey FWCR Platform is predicted to have on production resilience in the hypothetical scenario example.

Changing the relative dominance of the operational resilience branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on operational resilience from 0.47 (moderate) to 0.63 (high) and from 0.38 (moderate) to 0.41 (moderate) on overall organisational resilience. The relative dominance of contingency planning/RM and disaster response/recovery is again expected given the high potential impact that TURNkey FWCR Platform is predicted to have on these sub-criteria in the hypothetical scenario example.

Changing the relative dominance of the corporate resilience branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on corporate resilience from 0.04 (none) to 0.35 (moderate-low) and from 0.38 (moderate) to 0.42 (moderate) on overall organisational resilience. The relative dominance of corporate image/CSR is again expected given that TURNkey FWCR Platform is predicted to have no impact on either the financial resilience or adaptive capacity sub-criteria in the hypothetical scenario example.

Taken together, the sensitivity analysis at the sub-criteria level would again suggest that the model is stable, providing a range results which are compatible with modelling input data.

Table 16. Impact of varying the dominant sub-criteria on branch and overall resilience

Hierarchy Branch	Dominant sub-criteria	Level of Dominance and (Overall Organisational Resilience Score)				
		Base Score	Moderate	Strong	Very Strong	Extreme
Physical Resilience	Structural Resilience	0.45 (0.47)	0.38 (0.42)	0.35 (0.40)	0.33 (0.38)	0.32 (0.38)
Physical Resilience	Non-Structural Resilience	0.45 (0.47)	0.44 (0.46)	0.43 (0.45)	0.43 (0.45)	0.43 (0.45)
Physical Resilience	Production Resilience	0.45 (0.47)	0.53 (0.52)	0.57 (0.55)	0.59 (0.56)	0.60 (0.57)
Operational Resilience	Contingency Planning / RM	0.58 (0.40)	0.61 (0.41)	0.62 (0.41)	0.63 (0.41)	0.63 (0.41)
Operational Resilience	Supply Chain / ER	0.58 (0.40)	0.52 (0.39)	0.49 (0.38)	0.47 (0.38)	0.47 (0.38)
Operational Resilience	Disaster Response / Recovery	0.58 (0.40)	0.61 (0.41)	0.62 (0.41)	0.63 (0.41)	0.63 (0.41)
Corporate Resilience	Financial Resilience	0.14 (0.40)	0.08 (0.39)	0.06 (0.39)	0.05 (0.38)	0.04 (0.38)
Corporate Resilience	Adaptive Capacity	0.14 (0.40)	0.08 (0.39)	0.06 (0.39)	0.05 (0.38)	0.04 (0.38)
Corporate Resilience	Corporate Image (CSR)	0.14 (0.40)	0.25 (0.41)	0.30 (0.41)	0.33 (0.42)	0.35 (0.42)

The final aspect of sensitivity that needs to be considered is the sensitivity of the hierarchy model to the assumptions made about the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform on the sub-criteria. Table 17 shows the results of a series of sensitivity analyses against the original hypothetical scenario example (column 2). In column 3, the relative impact that TURNkey FWCR Platform is expected to have on each sub-criteria is increased by one level (e.g. if in the original example the impact was expected to be low, in the modified example this has been raised to moderate). In columns 4 – 9 the effects of setting all of the sub-criteria in a branch to low, moderate or high in turn are modelled.

Increasing the impact by one division that the TURNkey FWCR Platform is expected to have on the sub-criteria significantly increases the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy and on overall organisational resilience. Further, the degree of change caused by this increase is substantial, suggesting that care needs to be taken when assigning impact scores. The effect of changing the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform is expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy also causes substantial changes in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform will be expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy, and on overall organisational resilience. This said, the range of potential impacts of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on overall organisation is narrower (0.35 to 0.56) than that associated with individual branches (0.27 to 0.66) and as such the model would again appear to be stable.

Table 17. Results of a series of sensitivity analyses against original hypothetical scenario example

Sub-criteria	Ex	Ex+1	Impact Scenarios
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Structural Impact	L	M	L	L	M	M	H	H
Non-structural Impact	M	H	L	L	M	M	H	H
Production Impact	H	VH	L	L	M	M	H	H
Contingency Planning/RM	H	VH	M	H	L	H	L	M
Supply Chain/ER	M	H	M	H	L	H	L	M
Disaster Response/Recovery	H	VH	M	H	L	H	L	M
Financial Resilience	N	VL	H	M	H	L	M	L
Adaptive Capacity	N	VL	H	M	H	L	M	L
Corporate Image (CSR)	M	H	H	M	H	L	M	L
Physical Resilience	0.37	0.57	0.27	0.27	0.42	0.42	0.66	0.66
Operational Resilience	0.63	0.96	0.42	0.66	0.27	0.66	0.27	0.42
Corporate Resilience	0.28	0.49	0.66	0.42	0.66	0.27	0.42	0.27
Overall Resilience	0.41	0.64	0.35	0.37	0.42	0.45	0.55	0.56

The analysis presented in this section demonstrates how AHP can potentially be applied to assessing the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on organisational resilience. The AHP model will be further refined once the final version of the TURNkey FWCR Platform is available during the 3rd PAR cycle.

13.3 Developing an AHP model of critical infrastructure resilience

TURNkey FWCR platform aims to provide management support to critical infrastructures owners and operators to increase the preparedness, trigger pre-event actions and help the management of post-events response and communication with first responders.

Critical infrastructures, as highlighted in Deliverable 4.3, are composed by soft and hard components. This distinction is clearly presented by some other authors (Muller G., 2012). On the other hand, some studies focused on community resilience to disasters define the infrastructure resilience as dependent only on its physical asset (Sharifi and Yamagata (2016); UNDRR (2017)).

Deliverable 1.2 and Deliverable 5.1 have already presented the definition of resilience, but they did not include a clear difference between preparedness and mitigation, which are two different aspects of resilience (Tarhan et al., (2016); Ranghieri and Ishiwatari, (2014)). Whilst mitigation looks to activities that reduce the damages consequent to a disaster, preparedness includes all activities to plan the emergency response to a disaster. According to these definitions OEF and EEW are mitigation actions for the hard elements of CIs, while they are preparedness or mitigation actions for the soft components of the CIs. The RRE is always a preparedness action.

The assessment of CIs resilience is often decomposed into a resilience assessment of their dimensions. Some studies identified three dimensions of CI resilience: organizational; technological; and societal (ResiLENS, 2016). Other studies defined four dimensions of the CI resilience: organizational; technical; economic; and social (Bruneau et al. (2003); Labaka et al. (2016)). Morga and Jones (2019) presented a framework to assess the CI resilience to soil liquefaction disasters that

includes three dimensions: organization and management; technical systems; and operational delivery systems. Here a CI resilience model with three dimensions or first level indicators of the AHP model is presented: physical and operative; organizational; and financial (Figure 56). The physical and operative dimension includes three second level indicators already used in other studies (Prior 2014), ResiLENS (2016) and Morga and Jones (2019)): integrity of structural systems, integrity of non-structural systems (often called services of the built asset), and lack of disruption of the supply chain or interdependence from any other CI. The CI physical and operative resilience quantifies the mitigation of losses and the reduction of the CI downtime. It is influenced by OEF and EEW functions of the TURNkey FWCR platform. The organizational resilience measures the CI preparedness to earthquakes, and it is influenced by RRE functions of TURNkey FWCR platform. The second level indicators of the organizational resilience are contingency planning and Risk Management (RM) analysis; information management and internal communication, which are already identified as CI resilience indicator by Lubaka et al. (2016) and by Morga and Jones (2019); and external communication, which also includes the communications with the earthquake alert provider and the first responders (Lubaka et al. (2016); Tahrán et al. (2016); Ranghieri and Ishiwatari (2014)). Finally, the financial resilience measures the loss mitigation and is influenced by OEF functions of TURNkey FWCR platform: earthquake forecast can trigger an inventory of the spare functional components of the CI and a review of the repair plan. Therefore, the second level indicators of the financial resilience of the CI resilience model proposed are redundancy (or spare part availability) and repair plan; financial resilience resources (Labaka et al. (2016); Morga and Jones (2019)); and availability of public funds for quick recovery (Ranghieri and Ishiwatari (2014)).

Figure 56. AHP model of CI resilience to earthquakes

13.3.1 Analytical Hierarchic Process of assess Critical Infrastructure resilience

The AHP CI resilience model was evaluated using hypothetical data to determine the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the resilience of a CI organisation. Firstly, the values of the second level indicators are assessed in pairs and the values are then combined through the first level indicators, which are also assessed in pairs, to calculate the overall CI resilience. The assessment of the resilience is carried out twice: the first time for a CI not using the TURNkey FWCR Platform and the second time for the CI using the TURNkey FWCR Platform. Saaty's 9-levels scale is applied for the pairwise assessment of the second and first level indicators (1 – Equal Importance, 3 – Moderate Importance, 5 – Strong Importance, 7 – Very Strong Importance, 9 – Extreme Importance, with scores of 2, 4, 6 and 8 used for intermediate values).

Hypothetical data are used in the following subsections to demonstrate the methodology and test its effectiveness. Firstly, the estimation of second level indicators grouped according to the first level indicators is presented and then the assessment of the CI overall resilience is presented.

13.3.1.1 Physical and operative resilience of Critical Infrastructures

The physical and operative resilience of CIs measures the CI losses mitigation and reduction of the CI downtime. The propositions of the AHP pairwise comparisons for the physical and operative resilience of CI are assumed to be:

- structural resilience is strongly-very strongly more important than non-structural resilience; the non-structural systems functionality is dependent on the structural systems.
- structural resilience is very strongly-extremely more important than supply chain and interdependences; in fact, no operation can occur without functioning structural systems.
- non-structural resilience is equally-moderately more important than supply chain and interdependences; despite the available supplies the CI cannot operate when its non-structural systems do not work.

The following pairwise comparison matrix results from these propositions:

	Structural	Non-structural	Supply chain / interdependences
Structural	1.0000	6.0000	8.0000
Non-structural	0.1667	1.0000	2.0000
Supply chain / interdependences	0.1250	0.5000	1.0000

The normalised pairwise comparison matrix produces the following priority vector

	Priority Vector
Structural	0.7671
Non-structural	0.1481

Supply chain / interdependences	0.0848
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The consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.009, which gives a consistency ratio of 0.017 (1.7%). It is less than the 10% consistency threshold indicated by Saaty (1990). Therefore, the pairwise comparison are internally consistent.

The assessment of the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on the second level indicators of the physical and operative CI resilience defines three (2x2) pairwise comparison matrices based on the following propositions:

- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have an equal impact on structural resilience, as an enhancement of the structural vulnerability of CI is possible only through physical strengthening.
- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a moderate impact on non-structural resilience, as some systems could be shut down automatically after an EEW.
- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have an equal-moderate impact on production resilience, as the supply chain and interdependency cannot be modified after an OEF or EEW, but stocks of critical supplies can be checked and replenished after an OEF.

These propositions are defined by taking into account the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have on the end user use-cases presented in Deliverable 1.4 and Deliverable 2.6.

From the pairwise comparison matrix the following the associated priority vectors are calculated.

	Priority Vector (structural systems)	Priority Vector (non-structural systems)	Priority Vector (supply chain / interdependences)
With TURNkey	0.5000	0.7500	0.6667
Without TURNkey	0.5000	0.2500	0.3333

Combining the product of the normalised comparison matrix with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors produces a relative resilience score of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform has on the CI physical and operative resilience (Table 18).

Table 18. Score of the CI physical and operative resilience.

	Score of physical and operative resilience
With TURNkey	0.5511
Without TURNkey	0.4489

Table 18 shows that the overall impact of TURNkey FWCR platform on the physical and operative resilience of a CI is very low for this hypothetical case as the difference between the two scores is only 10%.

13.3.1.2 Organisational resilience of Critical Infrastructures

The organizational resilience of CIs measure the preparedness to seismic events. The pairwise comparison propositions for the CI organizational resilience are assumed to be:

- contingency planning and risk management (RM) is strongly more important than external communication. Without contingency planning and risk management communications from outside the CI, such as an EEW, can be ineffective in reducing losses and CI communications with external entities after the event, such as first responders, can be difficult and confused.
- contingency planning and RM is moderately more important than information management and internal communication. The RM plan indicates how the information should flow within the CI to prepare for the seismic event, e.g. the RM plan can indicate who orders the shut off of sections of the CI non-structural systems (e.g. the valves of a gas pipeline) and who organises the repair in case of damage.
- information management and internal communication is equally-moderately more important than external communication. The OEF and EEW trigger actions in the CI, but without internal communication those actions are not performed.

These comparison propositions produce the following pairwise comparison matrix.

	Contingency planning/RM	External communication	Information management / internal communication
Contingency planning/RM	1.0000	5.0000	3.0000
External communication	0.2000	1.0000	0.5000
Information management / internal communication	0.3333	2.0000	1.0000

The normalized comparison matrix produces the following priority vector:

	Priority Vector
Contingency planning/RM	0.6479
External communication	0.1222
Information management / internal communication	0.2298

The consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.0018, which gives a consistency ratio of 0.0036 (3.6%), which is less than the 10% consistency threshold indicated by Saaty (1990). Therefore the pairwise comparisons are internally consistent.

The assessment of the impact of the TURNkey FWCR platform on the second level indicators of the CI organisational resilience defines three (2x2) comparison matrices based on the following propositions:

- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a strong impact on contingency planning and RM. The RM plan would be different with or without the implementation of TURNkey FWCR platform. If the CI uses the platform its RM plan will include actions to take in case EEW alerts are issued and communications to send to first responders after a seismic event.
- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a strong impact on external communication. In fact, it is a tool to manage part of the CIs external communication.
- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have a moderate impact on the information management and CI internal communications. The EEW obtained from outside the CI through the platform must be integrated with legacy systems to trigger planned actions.

These propositions are defined considering the TURNkey FWCR platform end user use-cases presented in Deliverable 1.4 and Deliverable 2.6.

From the pairwise comparison matrix the following priority vectors are calculated.

	Priority Vector (contingency planning/RM)	Priority Vector (external communication)	Priority Vector (information management / internal communication)
With TURNkey	0.8333	0.8333	0.7500
Without TURNkey	0.1667	0.1667	0.2500

Combining the product of the normalised comparison matrix with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors produces a relative resilience score of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform has on the CI organisational resilience (Table 19).

Table 19. Score of the CI organizational resilience.

	Score of organizational resilience
With TURNkey	0.8141
Without TURNkey	0.1858

Table 19 shows the overall impact of TURNkey FWCR platform on the CI organisational resilience is quite high for these set of hypothetical data. The relative score of organisational resilience of the CI with TURNkey FWCR platform is around six times that without the platform.

13.3.1.3 Financial resilience of Critical Infrastructure

The CI financial resilience leads to mitigation of losses. The pairwise comparison propositions for the financial resilience of CIs are assumed to be:

- Financial resilience resources is moderately more important than availability of public funds. Although it is proved that most of the recovery actions of CI after a seismic event are paid for by

public funds (Ranghieri and Ishiwatari (2014)) they are not always as quickly available as the funds put aside by the CI for recovery (including insurance).

- Redundancy built before the seismic event and repair plans are moderately-strongly more important than financial resilience resources. Lack of redundancy increases the probability of damage and downtime and the need of funds for repair. Moreover, redundancy strengthens the financial resilience of the CI because it could resume operations quickly after the seismic shake even if experiences a partial reduction of income and profit.
- Redundancy built before the seismic event and repair plans are strongly-very strongly more important than public funds. Lack of redundancy increases the probability of CI complete failure and downtime and increases the need of funds for repairs.

These comparison propositions produce the following pairwise comparison matrix.

	Financial resilience resources	Public funds	Redundancy and repair plan
Financial resilience resources	1.0000	3.0000	0.2500
Public funds	0.3333	1.0000	0.1667
Redundancy and repair plan	4.0000	6.0000	1.0000

The normalized comparison matrix produces the following priority vector:

	Priority Vector
Financial resilience resources	0.2213
Public funds	0.0933
Redundancy and repair plan	0.6852

The consistency check produces a consistency index of 0.027, which gives a consistency ratio of 0.05 which is below the 10% threshold calculated by Saaty (1990) so the pairwise comparisons are internally consistent.

The assessment of the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on the second level indicators of the financial resilience of CI defines three (2x2) comparison matrices based on the following propositions.

- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have an equal-moderate impact on financial resilience resources. The platform can reduce the financial resources that the CI puts aside for repair of some non-structural elements and missed service provision to clients.
- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have an equal impact on public funds as minor repairs that can be avoided using the platform are not covered by public funds.

- TURNkey FWCR Platform would have an equal-moderately more impact on redundancy and repair plans as redundancy should be implemented where OEF and EEW are available to the CI and the repair plan should be prepared despite OEF and EEW.

These propositions are defined considering the TURNkey FWCR platform end user use-cases presented in Deliverable 1.4 and Deliverable 2.6.

From the pairwise comparison matrix the following the associated priority vectors are calculated.

	Priority Vector (financial resilience resources)	Priority Vector (public funds)	Priority Vector (redundancy and repair plan)
With TURNkey	0.6667	0.5000	0.6667
Without TURNkey	0.3333	0.5000	0.3333

Combining the product of the normalised comparison matrix with the priority vectors from the TURNkey priority vectors produces a relative resilience score of the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform has on the CI financial resilience is calculated (Table 20).

Table 20. Score of the financial resilience of a CI.

	Score of financial resilience
With TURNkey	0.6511
Without TURNkey	0.3489

Table 20 shows a moderate overall impact of TURNkey FWCR platform on the CI financial resilience for the set of hypothetical data used in the calculation. The relative score of financial resilience of the CI with TURNkey FWRC platform is twice the relative score without the platform.

13.3.1.4 Overall CI resilience

The first level CI resilience indicators are then put together to calculate the overall CI resilience to earthquakes. For this purpose, the following pairwise comparison propositions of the first level indicators are formulated.

- physical and operative resilience is moderately-strongly more important than organizational resilience. Without the undamaged physical assets any communication with outside the CI or internal to CI is meaningless.
- physical and operative resilience is moderately more important than financial resilience. While private and public funds can be used to repair the damaged CI, the repairing process takes time and reduces the CI income (and profit in case of a privately-owned CI).
- financial resilience is equally-moderately more important than organizational resilience. Communications from outside the CI include the EEW that can influence the repair plans and the amount of financial resilience resources the CI plan to put aside.

These comparison propositions are summarized in the following pairwise comparison matrix:

	Physical and operative resilience	Organisational resilience	Financial resilience
Physical and operative resilience	1.0000	4.0000	3.0000
Organizational resilience	0.2500	1.0000	0.5000
Financial resilience	0.3333	2.0000	1.0000

The normalized comparison matrix produces the following priority vector:

	Priority Vector
Physical and operative resilience	0.6232
Organizational resilience	0.1373
Financial resilience	0.2395

The consistency index is 0.0092. It produces a consistency ratio of 0.017 (1.7%), which is less than the 10% consistency threshold identified by Saaty (1990). Therefore, the pairwise comparisons of the first level CI resilience indicators are internally consistent.

The normalized priority matrix of the CI second level resilience indicators are multiplied by the respective normalized priority vector element of the first level CI resilience indicators to calculate the matrix of the relative impact of each second level indicator on the CI overall resilience:

	Physical and operative resilience	Organizational resilience	Financial resilience
Indicator 1	0.4781	0.0889	0.0530
Indicator 2	0.0922	0.0167	0.0223
Indicator 3	0.0528	0.0315	0.1641

Finally, the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform is assessed for the overall CI resilience (Table 21):

Table 21. Score of the overall CI resilience

	CI Resilience
With TURNkey	0.6111
Without TURNkey	0.3889

The values in Table 21 indicate that the score of the CI overall resilience is double when TURNkey FWRC platform is implemented than when it is not.

13.3.2 Modelling the potential impact of TURNkey FWCR platform of a hypothetical Critical Infrastructure organisation

In this section a scenario analysis is presented for a specific CI. Although the data used in the analysis are still hypothetical and not based on a real case study, the analysis and the comments are oriented to investigate the resilience and functionality of that specific CI in a seismic prone area.

4.2.1.1. Scenario: A localized Critical Infrastructure

The regional administration is evaluating the potential benefit of the use of the TURNkey FWCR Platform to improve the resilience to earthquake of a hospital with A&E and two operating theatres located in an earthquake prone area. The hospital is composed of a 10 storey building built in year 2000 a.C. and a warehouse where supplies are stored. The hospital is not identified as a primary emergency health care facility in case of earthquake. However, the hospital should have unchanged functionality level soon after a moderate seismic event.

The appraisal of the effectiveness of the TURNkey FWCR Platform to improve the resilience of the hospital is carried out through a questionnaire administered to senior and middle managers.

13.3.2.1 Pairwise comparison of the first level resilience indicators

The hospital is public therefore it receives public funds. It is composed of one building designed using the standard for the construction in seismic area EN1998 and a small warehouse in the parking area where health care supplies are stored. The emergency electric generator needs maintenance. The staff are not trained to respond to a seismic event, but the senior managers know how to implement the emergency and contingency plan. For these reasons the outcome of the questionnaire is summarized using the following comparison propositions:

- physical and operative resilience is moderately more important than organizational resilience.
- physical and operative resilience is very strongly more important than financial resilience.
- organizational resilience is moderately-strongly more important than financial resilience.

Table 22 shows the normalized priority vector of the hospital overall resilience based on these propositions.

Table 22. Normalized priority vector of the hospital overall resilience

	Priority Vector
Physical and operative resilience	0.66
Organizational resilience	0.26
Financial resilience	0.08

13.3.2.2 Pairwise comparison of the physical and operative resilience indicators

The hospital building and its warehouse are designed and built according to EN1998, the current European standard for structures in seismic area. The hospital has an emergency electric generator that can produce electricity for 12 hours to power all hospital services and functions except for the heating and cooling systems. The water tank can store water needed for any process usually occurring in the hospital in a 24 hour period. The hospital has no redundant connection to aqueduct, drainage and power line. The inventory and replenishment of stocks occurs once a month.

Due to these conditions the questionnaire outcome is summarized with the following comparison propositions:

- structural resilience is strongly more important than non-structural resilience.
- structural resilience is strongly more important than supply chain and interdependences.
- non-structural resilience is equally-moderately more important than supply chain and interdependences.

Table 23 shows the normalized priority vector of the physical and operative resilience of the hospital based on these propositions.

Table 23. Normalized priority vector of the hospital physical and operative resilience

	Priority Vector
Structural	0.70
Non-structural	0.18
Supply chain / interdependences	0.12

13.3.2.3 Pairwise comparison of the organizational resilience indicators

The hospital has an updated contingency plan than includes an operation plan in case of earthquake. It is known by the senior manager but the staff have not been trained to respond to seismic events. The hospital is served by only one phone line. For this reason, the outcome of the questionnaire is summarized with the following comparison propositions:

- contingency planning and RM are strongly more important than external communication
- contingency planning and RM is moderately more important than information management and internal communication.
- external communication is equally important than information management and internal communication.

Table 24 shows the normalized priority vector of the hospital organizational resilience based on these propositions.

Table 24. Normalized priority vector of the hospital organizational resilience

	Priority Vector
Contingency planning / RM	0.65
External communication	0.16
Information management / internal communication	0.19

13.3.2.4 Pairwise comparison of the financial resilience indicators

The hospital is public, therefore it is funded by public money. It is not served by any redundant interdependent CI and the replenishment of stocks occurs once per month. It does not provide any service to paying patients. For these reasons the outcome of the questionnaire administered to senior and middle managers is summarized by the following comparison propositions:

- public funds are extremely more important than financial resilience resources.
- redundancy and repair plan are extremely more important than financial resilience resources.
- public funds are equally-moderately more important than redundancy and repair plan.

Table 25 shows the normalized priority vector of the hospital financial based on these propositions.

Table 25. Normalized priority vector of the hospital financial resilience

	Priority Vector
Financial resilience resources	0.05
Public funds	0.58
Redundancy and repair plan	0.37

The use of the TURNkey FWCR Platform would impact the priority of each second level indicator. This impact is assessed considering the propositions presented in the hypothetical case of the application of the AHP to the CI resilience to earthquake. Those propositions were obtained from the analysis of the end user use-cases presented in Deliverable 1.4 and Deliverable 2.6. Table 26 presents the normalized impact score of each second level indicators on the overall resilience of the hospital in case TURNkey FWCR Platform is used or not.

Table 26. Normalized impact score of the second level resilience indicators on the overall resilience of the hospital

Sub-criteria or second level indicator	Normalized impact score with TURNkey FWCR platform	Normalized impact score without TURNkey FWCR platform	Justification
Structural systems	0.17	0.30	The overall resilience of the hospital is strongly dependent on the resilience of the physical asset of the system. However, the physical asset resilience will play a less important role in the overall resilience of the hospital when TURNkey FWCR platform is implemented.

Non-structural systems	0.25	0.15	The overall resilience of the hospital is strongly dependent on the resilience of the non-structural systems. TURNkey FWCR platform will increase the resilience of the non-structural systems on the overall resilience of the hospital.
Supply chain / independencies	0.23	0.20	The overall resilience of the hospital is strongly influenced by the resilience of the supply chains and interdependent CIs. TURNkey FWCR platform will have a minor effect on the importance of supply chain and interdependences in the overall resilience of the hospital
Contingency planning / RM	0.09	0.08	The overall resilience of the hospital is moderately influenced by the resilience due to existence of contingency and RM plan. TURNkey FWCR platform will have almost no effect on the importance of existence of contingency and Risk Management plan on the overall resilience of the hospital.
External communication	0.09	0.08	The overall resilience of the hospital is moderately influenced by the resilience due to external communication. TURNkey FWCR platform will have almost no effect on the importance of external communication on the overall resilience of the hospital. This result, which appears to be the most surprising one, is justified by fact that the hospital is not a primary health care facility in case of earthquake, so the communication from the hospital toward outside might be limited.
Information management / internal communication	0.08	0.11	The overall resilience of the hospital is moderately influenced by the resilience of information flow in it (internal communications). TURNkey FWCR platform will have a minor effect on the importance of internal communication in the overall resilience of the hospital
Financial resilience resources	0.03	0.02	The overall resilience of the hospital is very little influenced by the resilience due to existence of financial resilience resources. TURNkey CR platform will have almost no effect on the importance of existence of financial resilience resources on the overall resilience of the hospital.
Public funds	0.02	0.03	The overall resilience of the hospital is very little influenced by the resilience due to availability of public funds. TURNkey FWCR platform will have almost no effect on availability of public funds in the overall resilience of the hospital.
Redundancy and repair plan	0.03	0.02	The overall resilience of the hospital is very little influenced by the resilience due to existence of redundancy and repair plan. TURNkey FWCR

			platform will have almost no effect on existence of redundancy and repair plan in the overall resilience of the hospital.
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Finally, Table 27 shows the impact score of TURNkey FWCR platform on the hospital overall resilience.

Table 27. Score of the overall CI resilience

	Hospital Resilience
With TURNkey	0.6322
Without TURNkey	0.3678

The values of Table 27 indicates that the overall resilience of the hospital using TURNkey FWCR Platform is 1.7189 times higher (almost twice) than the overall resilience of the hospital not using the TURNkey FWCR platform ($0.6322/0.3678=1.7189$).

13.3.2.5 Sensitivity analysis of the AHP model for Critical Infrastructures resilience to earthquake.

A sensitivity analysis is carried out to estimate the factors that are mostly influenced by TURNkey FWCR platform. The CIs resilience model solved with AHP presented in the previous sub-sections is composed of three first level indicators (or criteria) and nine second level indicators (or sub-criteria). The double selection options (with TURNkey FWCR platform and without TURNkey FWCR platform) are added to the twelve indicators. The large number of variables would make the sensitivity analysis computationally time consuming producing some unrealistic results. For this reason the number of variables selected for the sensitivity analysis are less than the total number of variables in the AHP model for CIs. The selection of the indicators to take into account in the sensitivity analysis is based on the results of the scenario analysis presented above. The variables with the highest impact score are analysed in the sensitivity analysis: non-structural systems; supply chain/independencies; and structural systems. Three further second level indicators are analysed in the sensitivity analysis: contingency planning/RM; external communication; and information management/internal communication. Indeed, OEF, EEW and RRE involve an information exchange and management and should be included in the RM and contingency plan. The values of the weight of the first level indicators criteria of the hierarchic model will be taken from the hypothetical scenario. Finally, the importance of the implementation of TURNkey FWCR platform for each second level indicators is the same of the scenario analysis because they are obtained from the analysis of the user use-cases presented in Deliverable 1.4 and Deliverable 2.6. In the sensitivity analysis only one variable is changed at a time while all the other variables keep the values indicated in the calculation carried out in the previous sub-sections presenting the scenario analysis.

In the sensitivity analysis the pairwise value is varied from 1/9 to 9 following Saaty (1990) 9-levels scale. The values used for the varying variable are 1/9, 1/7, 1/5, 1/3, 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9. For the sensitivity analysis the consistency ratio is calculated and those solutions that are internally inconsistent are ignored. The consistency ratios of the sensitivity analysis are shown in Table 28.

Only options with consistency ratio lower than 5% (note: this is a more rigorous threshold than previously used in this section but it is consistent with Satty's approach) are considered internally consistent and therefore taken into account. In Table 28 they are in bold.

Table 28. Consistency ratio of the sensitivity analysis

Comparison / pairwise value	1/9	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	3	5	7	9
Structural systems compared to Non-structural system	1.28	1.03	0.76	0.46	0.09	0.00	0.05	0.12	0.19
Structural systems compared to Supply chain	2.79	2.38	1.93	1.40	0.61	0.16	0.05	0.01	0.00
Non-structural systems compared to Supply chain / interdependences	0.57	0.44	0.30	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.30	0.44	0.57
Contingency planning / RM compared to External communication	1.42	1.15	0.87	0.55	0.13	0.00	0.03	0.08	0.13
Contingency planning / RM compared to Information management / Internal communication	1.96	1.63	1.27	0.86	0.29	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.04
External communication compared to Information management / Internal communication	0.32	0.23	0.13	0.04	0.03	0.29	0.53	0.73	0.90

From Table 28 it is clear that the only option for the pairwise comparison of Non-structural systems with Supply chain / interdependences is that they have equal importance (which is in accordance with the proposition presented before in scenario analysis).

Tables 29 and 30 present further results of the sensitivity analysis: the values in bold are those with consistency ratio within the limit to guarantee internal consistency. Table 29 shows the values of the resilience score of the hospital adopting the TURNkey FWCR platform. Among the values with internal consistency, the highest value is 0.64. It comes from the proposition "Structural systems are moderately more important than Non-structural system". The value corresponds to a variation of 0.28 of the overall resilience score where the TURNkey FWCR platform is used (overall resilience with TURNkey FWCR Platform minus overall resilience without TURNkey FWCR platform) as shown in Table 30. This indicates that the use of the TURNkey FWCR platform would have high impact on the reduction of losses and minimization of downtime in cases where the non-structural systems are considered important for the functionality of the hospital and the EEW functions of the TURNkey FWCR platform trigger automatic or manual shut off systems. Table 29 shows also a higher improvement of the overall resilience of the hospital in case Contingency planning/RM is from strongly to extremely more important than Information management/Internal communication. This indicates that the TURNkey FWCR platform OEF and EEW should trigger either automatic actions,

like shut off of non-structural systems, or decision taken from or actions carried out by senior manager or teams specialized in disaster managements. This is in line with findings presented in Deliverable 1.2.

Table 29. Hospital overall resilience with TURNkey FWCR platform

Comparison / pairwise value	1/9	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	3	5	7	9
Structural systems compared to Non-structural system	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.69	0.67	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.63
Structural systems compared to Supply chain	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.67	0.66	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.62
Non-structural systems compared to Supply chain / interdependences	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.65
Contingency planning / RM compared to External communication	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63
Contingency planning / RM compared to Information management / Internal communication	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63
External communication compared to Information management / Internal communication	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63

Table 30. Improvement of the hospital overall resilience with TURNkey FWCR platform

Comparison / pairwise value	1/9	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	3	5	7	9
Structural systems compared to Non-structural system	0.40	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.33	0.28	0.26	0.26	0.25
Structural systems compared to Supply chain	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.35	0.32	0.28	0.26	0.26	0.25
Non-structural systems compared to Supply chain / interdependences	0.27	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.30
Contingency planning / RM compared to External communication	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26
Contingency planning / RM compared to Information management / Internal communication	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.27
External communication compared to Information management / Internal communication	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27

13.4 Developing an AHP model of community resilience

Deliverable D5.1 argued that community resilience can be assessed by using the criteria reported in Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities. In 2015, the UNISDR (UNISDR, 2015) developed “The Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities” as an assessment method to allow cities to better understand how resilient they are to natural and man-made disasters. The Scorecard was developed from the “Ten Essential” for Making Cities Resilient in support of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030. The “Ten Essentials” seek to provide a better understanding of:

- the disaster risks a city might face;
- how to mitigate the risks; and
- how to respond to disasters in a way that seeks to minimise loss of life, livelihoods, property, infrastructure, economic activity, and the environment.

The “Ten Essentials” are grouped into three sections (Figure 57). Essentials 1-3 address corporate/governance and financial issues; Essentials 4-8 address planning and disaster preparation; and Essentials 9-10 address disaster response and post-disaster recovery. The Scorecard was developed to enable cities to establish a baseline measurement of their antecedent level of disaster resilience for each “Essential” and to identify opportunities for investment and action (mitigation interventions) to improve their disaster resilience over time.

The UNDRR’s “Ten Essentials” for Disaster Risk Reduction				
Essential 1: Organise for Resilience	Essential 2: Identify, Understand and Use Current and Future Risk Scenarios	Essential 3: Strengthen Financial Capacity for Resilience	Essential 4: Pursue Resilient Urban Development	Essential 5: Safeguard Natural Buffers
Essential 6: Strengthen Institutional Capacity for Resilience	Essential 7: Increase Social and Cultural Resilience	Essential 8: Increase Infrastructure Resilience	Essential 9: Ensure Effective Disaster Response	Essential 10: Expedite Recovery and Build Back Better
= Governance		= Integrated Planning and Preparation		= Response / Recovery

Figure 57. The UNDRR “Ten Essentials” for Disaster Risk Reduction

The UNISDR Scorecard consists of 118 disaster resilience evaluation criteria (see Table 17 in Deliverable D5.1) grouped by subject/issue, details of the item being measured, a qualitative or quantitative statement of an indicative measurement, an indicative measurement scale (from 0 to 5, where 5 is best practice), and comments to help those applying the item being measured. Each item is assessed against two risk scenarios; a “most probable” scenario and a “most severe” scenario. These scenarios are defined by each city in response to its assumed hazard threat level. Improving community resilience to earthquake events relies on the complex relationships and interconnectivity

that exist between different community stakeholder groups (citizens, businesses, community groups, emergency services, critical infrastructure providers, politicians etc.) (Jones et al. 2021). Therefore, the UN scorecard is a unique tool, which requires a multi-stakeholder dialogue to be completed. This allows stakeholder with backgrounds in city governance; integrated planning and response planning to bring their unique perspective and contribution the improvement of a city resilience.

Based on the results of the first two action research cycles (reported in D2.6) and the results of the use-cases (reported in D1.3), it is proposed that community resilience can be shaped by a combination of factors related to City Governance; Integrated Planning; Response Planning. These can be effectively modelled as a 2 level hierarchy (Figure 58) where the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform can be assessed for each branch of the hierarchy and for overall community resilience by assigning metric scores to the level 2 criteria (using a similar methodology to that in the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities) and by applying weightings to the metric scores at both level 1 and level 2 of the hierarchy to reflect local context.

Figure 58. Consolidated AHP model of community resilience to earthquakes

The AHP Community Resilience model was tested using a similar approach to that previously described for the AHP organisational model (i.e. against test examples presented in Saaty 1996).

13.4.1 Community Resilience Hypothetical example

The following example applies the absolute version of the AHP to a community resilience model that uses the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities (as a proxy for community resilience - see D5.1 for more details) to a hypothetical city drawn from a combination of civic protection and emergency responders during the participatory action research programme to develop the end-user use-cases. Whilst the data used is hypothetical it demonstrates how the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on a typical city located in a known earthquake zone could be evaluated. Note: the scenario used does not represent any one city or location but is an amalgam derived from the end-user use cases.

Scenario: A typical city scenario

A medium-sized city is assessing its local disaster risk reduction strategy (resilience action plans) for earthquakes. The City has decided to adopt the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities to assist it with the assessment. The City is located in an earthquake prone area and the chances of having one or more magnitude 6 or larger earthquakes in the next 50 years are considered to be fairly high, based on historical earthquake records and geologic evidence of numerous active faults that have produced earthquakes in the recent geologic past.

The City has a population of circa 100,000 inhabitants. The population is young with an average age of 35 and a strong sense of community and belonging is present among citizens. The city presents a mostly service-based economy with a limited number of industries. It is a relatively modern city with a large proportion of its infrastructure and building stock built in recent year accordingly to Seismic Building Codes. However, the absence of industries, especially in the area of food manufacturing & processing, makes the city strongly reliant on its road infrastructure; in addition, the city is rapidly growing, and the current infrastructures are not considered resilient enough to sustain this fast development.

The City has commissioned a local risk consultancy organisation to assess their current vulnerability and resilience to a moderate and severe earthquake event and assess whether the use of the TURNkey FWCR platform could improve their resilience to an earthquake. The risk consultancy organisation applied the absolute version of the AHP to model the City through the application of the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities.

The risk consultancy organisation organised a one-day workshop with the different community stakeholder groups (citizens, businesses, community groups, emergency services, critical infrastructure providers, politicians etc.) to identify the relative importance of the criteria and sub-criteria in the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities and to build the customised AHP community resilience model and assess the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform could have on the resilience of the city. The impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have was evaluated using the generic use-cases developed by the TURNkey project against a severe earthquake scenario using a normalised version of a 6-point impact scale.

Pairwise comparison of top-level criteria

Initial discussions between city stakeholders, civil protection, community representatives, business organisations and academic institutions explored the relative importance of the governance, planning and response branches of the UNDRR to the overall resilience of the city in relation to disaster risk reduction criteria in the UNDRR Scorecard. During these discussions, a consensus was reached that governance criteria would have the most impact, and planning criteria the least impact on city resilience to an earthquake. The city stakeholders included in the one-day workshop believed that effective city governance, prior an earthquake could minimise the impact of disruption. Stakeholders recognised the city needed to put in place a more effective organizational structure and identify the necessary processes to understand and act on reducing disaster risks. They also realised that the first step to improve their planning and response was to develop a clear risk scenario able to identify hazards, exposures and vulnerabilities to a most severe (“worst-case”) scenario. Integrated planning was believed to be the second most important area as the city is growing at a fast pace and the current infrastructure system is already stretched to address the daily needs of the community.

- Governance is considered to be moderately-strongly more important than Planning
- Governance is considered to be moderately more important than Response
- Planning is considered to be moderately less important than Response

The judgements were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.071) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Governance	0.6080
Planning	0.1199
Response	0.2721

Pairwise comparison of City Governance sub-criteria

As the City is growing at a fast pace, it was believed the exposure and vulnerability are rapidly changing; therefore, identifying the most severe scenario and making use of the knowledge from risk scenarios in decisions on resilience improvement is extremely important. The city has a good understanding of the direct and indirect costs of disasters, and the relative impact of investment in prevention rather than incurring more significant costs during recovery. A ring-fenced capital budget has been assigned for any major works found to be necessary to improve resilience, including risk management allocations in operating budget as required to maintain the required state of resilience over time. They also believed that they had put in place a reasonable organizational structure and identified the necessary processes to understand and act on reducing risks associated to earthquake hazard. However, it was recognised that there was a need to further strengthen local-level institutional and co-ordination capacity; and build alliances and networks. For these reasons the City rated:

- Organise for Resilience moderately less important than Risk Assessments
- Organise for Resilience strongly more important than Financial Capacity
- Risk Assessment very strongly more important than Financial Capacity.

The judgments were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.063) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Organise for Resilience	0.2828
Risk Assessment	0.6463
Financial Capacity	0.0738

Pairwise comparison of planning sub-criteria

Given that the City was relatively modern, most of the buildings, neighbourhoods and infrastructure were built according to the most recent seismic building codes and there are no informal settlements. In addition, there is no major polluting infrastructure (e.g. chemical processing industries) on the city territory and in the county where the city is located; therefore, the potential impact of an earthquake on the natural buffers was considered limited. The City has been designed around small neighbourhoods, which has supported the creation of social connectedness and neighbourhood cohesion. In addition, the population is relatively young with strong virtual and physical community networks. In the last few years, the city has started identifying the specific nature of each vulnerability and map against the respective institutions; also, building local capacities by employing people with experience in earthquake disaster resilience and strengthening participation in disaster management and resilience improvement. However, it was recognised that there are still large issues that need to be addressed especially in terms of: engagement with private sectors and insurance companies; consistency of data and disaster risk information among the stakeholders; and professional training focussed on risk and resilience. Even if the city infrastructures have been designed in accordance to seismic building codes, concerns were expressed regarding a potential loss of service due to an earthquake. This was a particular concern due to the fact the city infrastructures are already struggling to provide effective service in daily circumstances due to the fast development of the city. Therefore, assessing the capacity and adequacy of critical infrastructure, strengthening/retrofitting vulnerable infrastructure; and recognising the relevance of priority services and operations during and after an earthquake were considered a high priority. For these reasons the City rated:

- Resilient Development Equally as important as Safeguard Natural Buffers
- Resilient Development Moderately less important than Strengthen Institutional Capacity
- Resilient Development Equally-Moderately less important than Strengthen Societal capacity
- Resilient Development Strongly less important than Increase Infrastructure Resilience
- Safeguard Natural Buffers Moderately less important than Strengthen Institutional Capacity
- Safeguard Natural Buffers Equally-Moderately less important than Strengthen Societal Capacity
- Safeguard Natural Buffers Strongly less as important than Increase Infrastructure Resilience
- Strengthen Institutional Capacity Equally-Moderately more important than Strengthen Societal capacity
- Strengthen Institutional Capacity less important than Increase Infrastructure Resilience

- Strengthen Societal Capacity Moderately less important than Increase Infrastructure Resilience

The judgments were internally consistent (consistency ratio 0.038) and resulted in the following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Resilient Development	0.0776
Safeguard Natural Buffers	0.0776
Strengthen Institutional Capacity	0.2057
Strengthen Societal Capacity	0.1437
Increase Infrastructure Resilience	0.4954

Pairwise comparison of response sub-criteria

The City has recognised that there is still a lot of work to do to ensure effective disaster response: preparedness plans were created several years before but not updated to consider the changes in the city; the city does not have an earthquake early warning system; the city's emergency response services needs to be upgraded. Whilst recovery and build back better are considered important, they are not considered to be as important as an effective disaster response. For these reasons the City rated:

- Disaster Response moderately more important than Recovery and Build Back Better.

As there are only two sub-criteria, internal consistency is guaranteed and resulted in following priority vector.

	Priority Vector
Effective Disaster Response	0.7500
Recovery and Build Back Better	0.2500

With the pairwise comparisons established across the AHP model, the city stakeholders considered the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each sub-criteria. Potential impact was assessed by considering how the end user use-cases developed to support the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform (see deliverables D1.3 and D2.6) could be applied to the city. Impact was scored using the 6-point Ideal Mode absolute scale (as this was similar in principle to the scoring scale used in the UNDRR scorecard). The impact score along with the justification for that score was recorded for future reference (Table 31).

Table 31. Impact of the TURNkey FWCR platform at the sub criteria level

Sub-criteria	Impact score	Justification (how TURNkey helps community resilience and recovery)
Organise for Resilience	Moderate (0.42)	Turnkey has a moderate impact on organising for resilience as it does not inform organizational structure; however, through its role in understanding risk it can support identifying the necessary processes to understand and act on reducing disaster risks.

Risk Scenarios	High (0.66)	The impact of TURNkey on risk scenarios was considered high as it allows stakeholders to build different scenarios setting out city-wide exposure and vulnerability from different potential earthquakes and do a proper risk assessment. It can also support with damage and loss estimation and provides integrated hazard maps.
Financial Capacity	Low (0.27)	TURNkey can indirectly help understand the economic impact of disasters and the need for investment in resilience. However, assigning a ring-fenced capital budget for any major works found to be necessary to improve resilience is a political decision, which lies outside the scope of TURNkey. In addition, it is acknowledged that some of the criteria such as, creating incentives for homeowners, low-income families, communities, businesses and public sector to invest in reducing the risks they face and applying or generating insurance coverage for lives, livelihoods, city and private assets is out of the City's responsibility as that depends on national policies.
Resilient Development	None (0.00)	Decisions to make the built environment more resilient, lie outside the scope of TURNkey and rely on risk-aware planning, design and implementation and on the development and implementation of appropriate building codes.
Safeguard Natural Buffers	None (0.00)	Decisions to safeguard natural buffers and to enhance the protective functions offered by natural ecosystems lie outside the scope of TURNkey and rely on the identification, protection and monitoring of critical ecosystem services that confer a disaster resilience benefit.
Strengthen Institutional Capacity	Low (0.27)	Decisions to provide all institutions relevant to a city's resilience with the capabilities and skills they need to discharge their roles lies outside the scope of TURNkey. However, TURNkey can indirectly support this by providing a single integrated set of resilience data that a city can share with other organizations involved with the city's resilience.
Strengthen Societal Capacity	Very low (0.17)	TURNkey can support private sector and employers to develop solid business continuity plans (through the use of the AHP organisational resilience model). However, in its current form TURNkey does not inform citizens or communities or "grass roots" organizations. Therefore, its impact on societal capacity was considered very low.
Increase Infrastructure Resilience	Moderate (0.42)	The impact of TURNkey on Increasing Infrastructure Resilience was considered Moderate as it can support critical infrastructure organisations cope with earthquakes (through the use of the AHP critical resilience model).
Effective Disaster Response	High (0.66)	TURNkey has a direct impact on disaster response as it will provide an effective and reliable early warning system for earthquakes. However, when used to inform, the risk scenario can also have an indirect beneficial effect on: event response plan; staffing/responder needs; food, shelter, staple goods and fuel supply. In addition, being primarily a frontline communication tool can have an indirect impact on interoperability and inter-agency working immediately following an earthquake.
Recovery and Build Back Better	Low (0.27)	TURNkey, when used to inform risk scenarios, can have an indirect impact on pre-disaster planning. This said, TURNkey does not have a direct impact on recovery planning or the decisions to build back better.

Applying the above impact scores to the community resilience hierarchy model suggests that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have a high-moderate (0.53) impact on overall community resilience; with the greatest impacts being on the governance and response criteria (0.56 – moderate-high for both) and the lowest impact being on the planning criteria (0.29 - low).

With respect to the governance sub-criteria, the greatest impact would be on risk assessment (0.42 – moderate) followed by organise for resilience (0.12 – very low). The TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have no impact on financial capacity (0.02).

With respect to response sub-criteria, The TURNkey FWCR Platform would have the greatest impact on effective disaster response (0.49 – moderate) through the early warning function and on coordination and immediate recovery through information provided by the real-time dashboard. The TURNkey FWCR Platform would have very low-no (0.07) impact on longer term recovery or build back better.

With respect to the planning sub-criteria, the TURNkey FWCR Platform would have the greatest impact on increased infrastructure resilience (0.21 – low-very low) if critical infrastructure organisations used the TURNkey FWCR Platform to aid their disaster management and business continuity planning. The TURNkey FWCR Platform could have a small impact on strengthening institutional capacity, again providing business organisations have used it as part of their business continuity and resilience planning. The TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have no impact on resilient development, safeguard natural buffers or strengthen societal capacity.

In this hypothetical example - because approximately 70% of the overall impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on overall community resilience is through its contribution to risk assessment and effective disaster response - the city decided to commission the consultants to do a detailed investigation of how the Platform could be integrated into their disaster management and resilience planning processes and develop business models that could be used as the basis of a cost-benefit analysis. The business models and cost-benefit analysis form part of the work in Task 7.3 (to be undertaken in early 2022).

The community resilience scorecard will be revised during the final validation stage of the TURNKey FWCR platform (T6.5).

Community Resilience - Sensitivity analysis

The final stage of the AHP modelling process is to assess the sensitivity of the model to changes in the pairwise comparisons and absolute scores given to the impact of the alternative solutions (in this case the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the sub-criteria).

Changes to the impact of pairwise importance weightings of the top-level criteria were made by calculating a base case scenario assuming that all the top level criteria were of equal importance and then comparing this with analyses where each top level criteria was considered progressively more important using the important scale defined by Saaty (1 = equal importance; 3 = moderate importance; 5 = strong importance; 7 = very strong importance; 9 = extreme importance). The pairwise importance weightings of the sub-criteria were kept constant. The impact that TURNkey could have on the sub-criteria were the same as those used in the hypothetical scenario (above).

The results of this analysis for the example given above are shown in Table 32. Internal consistency was maintained in all the analyses. For the base case (top level criteria all of equal

importance) TURNkey would be expected to have a moderate-low impact on overall community resilience (0.36). Increasing the dominance of governance and response criteria resulted in an increase in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have, whilst increasing the dominance of the planning criteria resulted in decrease in the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform would be expected to have on community resilience. These findings are to be expected given that the expected impact of TURNkey FWCR on the governance and response branch sub-criteria are dominant in the hypothetical AHP model; which in turn suggests that the model is stable and that the relative importance of planning criteria would not be a major contributory factor in the decision of a city or region to use the TURNkey FWCR Platform.

Table 32. Impact of changing top level criteria weightings on overall community resilience

	Base Case	Moderate	Strong	Very Strong	Extreme
Governance	0.36	0.40	0.41	0.42	0.43
Planning	0.36	0.29	0.25	0.24	0.22
Response	0.36	0.40	0.42	0.43	0.44

Table 33 shows the effect of varying the pairwise comparisons of the sub-criteria of each branch of the community resilience hierarchy in turn and calculating the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on each branch of the hierarchy, as well as on overall community resilience. The relative importance of the top-level criteria and the potential impact of TURNkey on each sub-criteria were the same as those in the hypothetical example. Internal consistency was maintained in all the analyses. In Table 33 column 2 indicates which sub-criteria was dominant in the analysis. Columns 3-7 indicate the branch resilience score and overall community resilience score for different levels of dominance given to the sub-criteria. For example the highlighted row of Table 33 should be read as follows. The row is part of the Governance branch of the hierarchy. Risk assessment is the dominant sub-criteria. The base resilience score assuming all sub-criteria in this branch are equally important is 0.45 and the overall community resilience score is 0.46. The resilience scores (both for the branch and overall community resilience) change as the level of dominance changes (e.g., branch resilience score of 0.53 and overall resilience score of 0.51 for moderate level of dominance; branch resilience score of 0.57 and overall resilience score of 0.53 for strong level of dominance etc.).

Changing the relative dominance of the governance branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on governance from 0.32 (moderate-low) to 0.60 (high) and from 0.38 (moderate) to 0.55 (high) on overall community resilience. The relative dominance of risk assessment is expected given the high potential impact that TURNkey FWCR Platform is predicted to have on risk assessment in the sensitivity example.

Changing the relative dominance of the planning branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on planning from 0.07 (very low-none) to 0.33 (low-moderate) and from 0.50 (moderate) to 0.53 (moderate) on overall community resilience. The relatively low dominance of resilient

development, natural buffer and societal capacity sub-criteria is again expected given that TURNkey is predicted to have no or very little impact on these sub-criteria in the scenario example. The closeness in dominance of the other the sub-criteria (institutional capacity and infrastructure resilience) is also expected given the impacts that TURNkey is predicted to have on these sub-criteria in the scenario example. The relative closeness of the impacts on overall community resilience is also expected given the relative low scores given to the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on the sub-criteria and the relatively low importance of planning amongst the top level criteria.

Whilst changing the relative dominance of the response branch sub-criteria is somewhat trivial (as there are only two sub-criteria) it is presented here for completeness. Changing the relative dominance of the response branch sub-criteria resulted in a range of potential impacts on response from 0.31 (moderate-low) to 0.62 (high) and from 0.46 (moderate) to 0.54 (high-moderate) on overall organisational resilience.

Taken together, the sensitivity analysis at the sub-criteria level would again suggest that the model is stable and providing a range results which are compatible with modelling input criteria.

Table 33. Impact of varying the dominant sub-criteria on branch and overall resilience

Hierarchy Branch	Dominant sub-criteria	Level of Dominance and (Overall Organisational Resilience Score)				
		Base Score	Moderate	Strong	Very Strong	Extreme
Governance	Organise for resilience	0.45 (0.46)	0.44 (0.45)	0.43 (0.45)	0.43 (0.45)	0.43 (0.45)
Governance	Risk assessment	0.45 (0.46)	0.53 (0.51)	0.57 (0.53)	0.59 (0.54)	0.60 (0.55)
Governance	Financial capacity	0.45 (0.46)	0.38 (0.42)	0.35 (0.40)	0.33 (0.39)	0.32 (0.38)
Planning	Resilient development	0.17 (0.51)	0.12 (0.51)	0.10 (0.51)	0.08 (0.50)	0.07 (0.50)
Planning	Natural buffers	0.17 (0.51)	0.12 (0.51)	0.10 (0.51)	0.08 (0.50)	0.07 (0.50)
Planning	Institutional capacity	0.17 (0.51)	0.20 (0.52)	0.22 (0.52)	0.23 (0.52)	0.23 (0.52)
Planning	Societal capacity	0.17 (0.51)	0.17 (0.51)	0.17 (0.51)	0.17 (0.51)	0.17 (0.51)
Planning	Infrastructure resilience	0.17 (0.51)	0.24 (0.52)	0.28 (0.53)	0.31 (0.53)	0.33 (0.53)
Response	Disaster response	0.46 (0.50)	0.56 (0.53)	0.59 (0.54)	0.61 (0.54)	0.62 (0.54)
Response	Recovery and build back better	0.46 (0.50)	0.37 (0.48)	0.33 (0.47)	0.32 (0.46)	0.31 (0.46)

The final aspect of sensitivity that needs to be considered is the sensitivity of the hierarchy model to the assumptions made about the impact of TURNkey FWCR Platform on the sub-criteria. Table 34 shows the results of a series of sensitivity analysis against the hypothetical community resilience scenario example (column 2). In column 3 the relative impact that TURNkey is expected to have on each sub-criteria is increased by one level (e.g. if in the original example the impact was expected to

be low, in the modified example this has been raised to moderate). In columns 4 – 9 the effects of setting all of the sub- criteria in a branch to very low, moderate or very high in turn are modelled. Pairwise comparisons are the same as those used in the hypothetical example.

Increasing the impact by one division that the TURNkey FWCR Platform is expected to have on the sub-criteria significantly increases the potential impact that Platform would be expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy and on overall community resilience. Further, the degree of change caused by this increase is substantial, suggesting that care needs to be taken when assigning impact scores. The effect of changing the impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform is expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy also causes substantial changes in the potential impact of Platform will be expected to have on each branch of the hierarchy, and on overall community resilience. This said, the range of potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on overall community resilience is narrower (0.34 to 0.74) than that associated with individual branches (0.17 to 1.00) and as such the model would appear to be stable.

Table 34. Results of a series of sensitivity analyses against original hypothetical scenario example

Sub-criteria	Ex	Ex+1	Impact Scenarios					
			VL	VL	M	M	VH	VH
Organise for Resilience	M	H	VL	VL	M	M	VH	VH
Risk Scenarios	H	VH	VL	VL	M	M	VH	VH
Financial Capacity	L	M	VL	VL	M	M	VH	VH
Resilient Development	N	L	M	VH	VL	VH	VL	M
Safeguard Natural Buffers	N	L	M	VH	VL	VH	VL	M
Strengthen Institutional Capacity	L	M	M	VH	VL	VH	VL	M
Strengthen Societal Capacity	VL	L	M	VH	VL	VH	VL	M
Increase Infrastructure Resilience	M	H	M	VH	VL	VH	VL	M
Effective Disaster Response	H	VH	VH	M	VH	VL	M	VL
Recovery and Build Back Better	L	M	VH	M	VH	VL	M	VL
Criteria								
Governance	0.56	0.86	0.17	0.17	0.42	0.42	1.00	1.00
Planning	0.29	0.49	0.42	1.00	0.17	1.00	0.17	0.42
Response	0.56	0.86	1.00	0.42	1.00	0.17	0.42	0.17
Overall Resilience	0.53	0.81	0.43	0.34	0.55	0.42	0.74	0.71

The analysis presented in this section demonstrate how AHP can potentially be applied to assessing the impact that the TURNkey FWCR platform could have on community resilience. The AHP model will be further refined once the final version of the turnkey FWCR Platform is available as part of the 3rd PAR cycle.

13.5 Summary and Next steps

This section has presented a number of alternative approaches based on the application of AHP to assess the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on business organisation, critical infrastructure and community resilience. The section has presented 3 hierarchy models derived from literature and described how these models can form the basis to develop a range of business models (Task 7.3) that can demonstrate the potential benefits that applying the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have. AHP is a modelling approach that uses expert judgement to make subjective decisions on the relative importance of a hierarchy of criteria and sub-criteria to an overall goal (primary objective). This methodology has been applied to three potential TURNkey FWCR Platform end-user stakeholder groups.

Section 4.2 demonstrates how the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on business organisation resilience can be assessed using a 2 level hierarchy model and both a pairwise and absolute scoring scale to assess the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on an organisation's physical, operational and corporate resilience, and overall organisational resilience. A hypothetical scenario of a small manufacturing organisation was used to demonstrate how the AHP organisational resilience model could be applied in practice. The hypothetical scenario example also demonstrated how sensitivity analysis could be applied to the AHP model to establish a range of potential impacts.

Section 4.3 demonstrates how the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on a critical infrastructure organisation can be assessed, again using a 2 level hierarchy, that whilst similar to that used for business organisations, differed in terms of the criteria used to assess resilience. Again this section demonstrated how a pairwise comparison (with or without the use of the TURNkey FWCR Platform) could be used to assess the potential impact that the TURNkey FWCR Platform could have on the resilience of a critical infrastructure organisation. Again, a hypothetical scenario was used to demonstrate how the modelling approach could be applied to a typical hospital. Section 4.3 also demonstrated an alternative approach to sensitivity analysis where a range of consistent potential pairwise comparisons were identified as part of the modelling process.

Section 4.4 demonstrates how the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on community resilience can be assessed. The community resilience model was based on a 2 level hierarchical representation of the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities, which whilst similar to the hierarchies used in Sections 8.2 and 8.3 differed in the number of sub-criteria associated with each branch of the model. The community resilience model also used a hypothetical scenario of a small city to demonstrate how the impact of the TURNkey FWCR Platform on community resilience could be assessed using an absolute scoring approach to assess the potential Platform could have on organising for resilience, risk planning, financial capacity, resilient development, safeguarding natural buffers, strengthening institutional capacity, strengthening societal capacity, increasing infrastructure resilience, effective disaster response and recovery and build back better. Again the example demonstrated how the AHP model could be applied in practice.

Whilst the three hypothetical examples presented in the section do not represent any specific organisation (business or critical infrastructure) or city they have been compiled from an amalgamation of data that was collected by the authors through the first 2 PAR cycles. As such, whilst they are hypothetical, the authors believe that they are representative of the type of potential uses of a future TURNkey FWCR Platform. The models presented in this section will be further tested and refined with specific end-user stakeholders during the 3rd (and final) PAR cycle where the AHP models will be integrated with ANP models to evaluate the benefits, opportunity, costs and risk (BOCR) merits of specific stakeholder organisations or communities using the TURNkey FWCR Platform. This work is currently underway in Tasks 6.5 and 7.3.

14 EARTHQUAKE RECOVERY AND RELIEF SIMULATION MODEL

14.1 Introduction

14.1.1 Research objective

Following damaging earthquakes, homeowners, the construction and insurance industries, municipalities, disaster recovery donors, and other relevant stakeholders, embark on a journey to repair, demolish, and rebuild buildings. While repairs and reconstruction are going on, those who have lost their homes need to find, or be provided with, temporary housing. Temporary solutions may be costly and, therefore, from the perspective of the homeless, it is beneficial that the repair and reconstruction process takes as short a time as possible.

Those involved in the repair and reconstruction are typically not involved in providing temporary housing and therefore do not view recovery from the perspective of speed (with the exception of the homeowners themselves, who have a foot in both worlds). Speeding up the recovery requires additional resources, which may be costly, or simply not the responsibility of a recovery stakeholder. Stakeholders could even be resistant to interventions to speed up the recovery, for example contractors may not want more contractors, as it will decrease job opportunities per contractor. Therefore, a management system is needed to help guide stakeholders to balance their efforts between short-duration and cost-demanding recovery.

A management system is a set of objectives and associated procedures to reach an organizational goal (ISO, 2013). Consequentially, a disaster-related management system is the set of objectives and procedures needed to reach a disaster-related goal. Herein, a disaster-related goal is based on the definition of disaster provided by UNDRR (2009) where a disaster is “a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society involving widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses and impacts, which exceeds the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources”. A disaster-related goal is the inverse of disaster, i.e., a disaster-related goal is having a society that is not experiencing disruption. Thorvaldsdóttir (2016) provides a set of eight disaster-related objectives and 53 associated basic procedures (outlined in D5.1) addressing pre-disaster (risk), during disaster (impact, life-saving, relief, and recovery operations), and post disaster (learning and implementation) perspectives. To be part of such a management system stakeholders adapt their procedures to the disaster-related procedures and create additional procedures as necessary.

Of the eight objectives, three provide a basis for a recovery and relief management system: 1) impact operations: to gain control of damaging/impact processes, 2) recovery operations: to bring the society to normalcy (same as before or new), and 3) relief operations: to provide temporary relief until normalcy is reached. Specific elements of the recovery process (or any process) can be guided by an objective for a narrower context, such as, for example in the context of housing, recovery can

be defined as complete when all the buildings are functional. The term total reconstruction and repair time can be used to measure housing recovery.

Efforts balancing short-duration and cost-demanding recovery will require an adaptive management system that is able to change its policies based on feedback from the progress and test changes to policies before implementing them. System Dynamics (SD) is a computerized simulation approach for policy design and analysis. Using an SD model of the recovery process during the recovery process to show a joint (i.e., includes the perspectives of all stakeholders) estimated recovery timeline will help stakeholders understand whether the recovery and relief processes are having the desired effect. Such a collaborative management system will allow stakeholders to be aware of each other's needs and activities, and is likely to encourage regular stakeholder communications for collaborative planning and decision making for coordinated activities towards the common goals and objectives. An important question not addressed here is who is responsible for such a system.

A planning process is deciding who does what, when, where, and how, based on given procedures and policies. A housing recovery and relief planning process will start with information about the amount and type of damages the built environment has sustained. The TURNkey platform is designed to provide real-time loss estimates that can be used as a starting point for the iterative planning process. The TURNkey platform output therefore provides input data for the SD model within the context of rapid response community resilience.

A basic housing recovery and relief simulation model is presented herein to demonstrate the fundamental aspects of a SD model that could allow stakeholders to have an adaptive recovery and relief management system. The model herein focuses on project backlog among the stakeholders, which cause delays in the recovery process leading to increased cost in the relief activities. The model was based on conditions in the south Iceland test-bed, which was hit by damaging earthquakes on June 17th and 21st, 2000 and May 29th, 2008. Interviews were conducted with construction, financing, and welfare stakeholder, where information for future work was also collected.

14.1.2 System Dynamics Approach

System Dynamics is a methodology to understand the behaviour and dynamics of complex systems over time (Forrester 1998, Goh and Love 2012). Jay W. Forrester, an electrical and computer engineer at Massachusetts Institute of Technology applied his background in computer sciences and engineering to the development of computer modelling and analysis of social systems leading to the field of system dynamics. System dynamics arose from seeking a better understanding of management (Forrester 1998). Forrester developed a structure for system dynamics using a four-tiered structural hierarchy (Richardson 2011):

5. Closed system boundary (i.e., dynamic behaviour arises internally)
6. Feedback loops as the basic structural elements within the boundary
7. Level (state) variables representing accumulations within the feedback loops
8. Rate (flow) variables representing activity within the feedback loops.

The modelling process is divided into five iterative stages (Figure 59). First of all, problem definition, which was discussed in the previous section.

Figure 59 . System Dynamics iterative modelling process

The second step is system conceptualization. It is the most creative part of the modelling process requiring careful consideration (Luna-Reyes 2003). Conceptualization defines the purpose of the model, the model boundary and identifies key variables, describes the behaviour of the key variables, and presents the basic feedback loops of the system. The conceptualization includes the development of two diagrams, a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) and a Stock and Flow Diagram (SFD). The Figure 60 shows a CLD of the basic mechanism of a company (Albin 1997), showing key variables and their causal relationships. The (+) and (-) indicate whether the variables both increase or decrease (+) or move in the opposite direction (-). Figure 60 also shows the corresponding SFD, the prerequisite to building equations in the System Dynamics software.

Figure 60. Example of a Casual Loop Diagram and an associated Stock and Flow Diagram: The basic mechanism of a company, i.e., influence factors on inventory and profit (Albin 1997).

Figure 63. The Stella software modelling page.

Figure 64. SUSTAIN project interface

14.1.3 Disaster-related Management System Procedures used in study

The disaster-related objectives and procedures used herein are those relevant to impact, relief and recovery objectives from Thorvaldsdóttir (2006). Impact procedures are listed in the table below. The first impact procedure in the table includes obtaining information about the damages and is key procedure for planning recovery and relief. The remaining impact procedures (actions to avoid the need to rescue, actions to avoid the need to repair and reconstruct, and actions to stop damaging

processes that have started) can be critical elements of the recovery/relief process, but were not included in this study.

Table 35. Impact Procedures

1.	Monitor natural processes and damaging processes, diagnose current situation and forecast possible turn of events, and convert existing impact contingency plan into an operations plan.
2.	Protect population to avoid the need for rescue operations through warnings, directives, closing off areas, and evacuations, to the greatest extent possible.
3.	Protect property by redirecting natural processes, such as sandbagging, digging diversion trenches, cooling lava and control of reservoir spillways.
4.	Halt or reduce on-going damaging process by intervening, such as stopping leaking gas lines, putting out fires, and avoiding potential explosions.

The basic procedures for recovery and relief are listed in the table below. The four recovery procedures are planning, restoration (including repairs and reconstruction), reform process, re-establishment of livelihoods and rehabilitation of people. An adaptive system will use the information from the latter three to update the plans in the first. The model herein is limited to the first (planning) and second (reconstructing the physical environment) procedure. The relief procedures are structured in the same way. The first procedure is about planning, and the remaining procedures are implementation activities that provide information on how to change the plan and adapt to the progress. The model focuses on the first (planning) and second (shelter, i.e., temporary housing.) procedure.

Table 36. Recovery and Relief Procedures

	Recovery	Relief
1.	Perform a situation assessment to get an overview and convert contingency plan to an operations plan.	Perform needs assessments to get an overview and convert relief contingency plan to an operations plan.
2.	Restoration processes: remove rubble and clean up the affected area, reunite family members and bury the deceased, fully restore services and reconstruct the physical environment.	Sustain life and provide temporary relief through providing for basic needs, such as shelter, water, food, cooking facilities, heat, clothing, fuel, physical and mental health, and financial assistance.
3.	Reform processes: renew urban planning and revise building codes.	Make temporary repairs to homes, roads and bridges, etc. [SEP]
4.	Re-establish livelihoods, and support the physical and mental rehabilitation of people, their hope and eagerness for the future.	Make temporary repairs for temporary renewals of services, such as intermittent power supply. [SEP]
5.	-	Perform support operations, such as crowd control and closing off of hazardous areas.

14.1.4 Literature

A literature survey for the key words: system dynamics, disaster, housing, and recovery revealed five studies in this area. Kumar et al. (2015) analyze the impacts of a disaster on labor for housing recovery and rebuilding of a devastated region using a SD model. The model describes the behavior of labor

in the housing restoration process and provides insights on the interactions between the labor force and the housing inventory. Dias et al (2020) also use a SD model to analyse the problem of housing recovery from the demand and supply perspective and provides significant insights for policymakers into how the production of permanent housing depends upon the uncertainties and feedback effects of material and labor. Hwang et al. (2015) seek to understand overall recovery efforts in the whole region from a holistic perspective. They use the 2011 earthquake of Tohoku they to analyze the effectiveness of governmental plans. Sutley et al. (2018) also address a holistic approach to further the understanding of the dynamic processes and interdependencies of housing recovery. The impetus for their work is that inequalities in housing recovery could be addressed more effectively if interconnected factors and dynamic processes that slow down recovery for some are better understood. Finally, Chang-Richards et al. (2018) point out that while some progress has been made in the literature towards modelling and understanding community recovery, or some facets of it, there is little attention to the physical dimension of reconstruction, and how its progression affects the recovery of other social and economic sectors. In their research, they set out a system dynamics methodology for representing post-earthquake reconstruction process using experience of Christchurch.

These studies address demand surge of labour and material, the effectiveness of plans, inequalities, and the stages of construction. A useful characteristic of SD models is that models that have a common element and are on the step time scale can be connected. For example, the model herein on project backlog and project management from the perspective of insurance agencies, building and safety departments, welfare departments, design engineers, and contractors, might be strengthened by incorporating information about demand surge, plan effectiveness and construction processes, and vice versa. Therefore, it can be easy to build on each others work.

Functional Recovery is a post-earthquake state in which capacity is sufficiently maintained or restored to support pre-earthquake functionality. This definition requires buildings and infrastructure systems to be designed not only for safety (shall not collapse) but also for resiliency. Functional Recovery as defined by EERI considers interdependencies between at least five physical systems that comprise the built environment: Buildings, new and existing, serving all occupancies and uses; Water and wastewater systems; Energy systems; Communication systems; and Transportation systems. Functional Recovery is therefore not only reconstruction of the built environment and the restoration of the services that they provide, but takes into account that the reconstruction and restoration should be performed from the perspective of the community as a whole, not the individual systems. In that way Functional Recovery is a system recovery of a complex system. Functional recovery is closely related to community resilience, in part because of the unavoidable interdependencies between buildings and lifeline infrastructure systems. Guidelines for improving the built environment for post-earthquake reoccupancy and functional recovery time have been provided by FEMA (2021). Hwang et al. (2015) emphasize the importance rapid functional recovery. Functional recovery is the larger context that the model herein is placed.

14.2 Conceptualization of a Recovery and Relief Management System

14.2.1 Premise

Armed with the problem statement outlined in the study purpose, the model premise was defined as follows:

1. Buildings are damaged during an earthquake.
2. People report damage to their insurance company.
3. The insurance companies report the claim to the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund.
4. The Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund sends out assessors, who estimate the payment for the damages and pays the homeowner.
5. After payment is received, the homeowner hires a design engineer to design repairs based on the amount from the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund.
6. When drawings are ready the homeowner or the engineer, applies for repair/building permits to the Building and Safety department.
7. After the permit is obtained, the homeowner hires a contractor to repair the building.
8. The Welfare Department provides the household with temporary support (relief) while they cannot live in the house.
9. Hiring extra municipality staff can expedite recovery and relief processes.
10. After the repairs are complete the homeowner moves back into the home.

The above was the basis for a stakeholder interview plan, both for whom to interview and what to ask. Some interviewees suggested other interviewees. The aim of the interviews was to collect information about normal and disaster procedures, and issues about accumulations, delays, and feedback. Initial interview questions were what factors are important to the given context? What are the main procedures? What are the average completion rates? How do you receive feedback? What is the typical behaviour of the system in a timeline? Where are delays and why?

The initial plan was to use the information from the stakeholders to replicate the recovery and relief during the response to the 2008 earthquake in south Iceland. It became apparent that this would not be possible as information about the entire recovery process does not exist. Laws in place in 2008 allowed insurance claims to be paid once an agreement between the insurance agency and owner had been agreed without a follow up on whether the money was used to repair the buildings or not. Not all damages were reported by the homeowner to the Building and Safety department. Not all damaged buildings were repaired. Not all repaired buildings were repaired by professionals. Therefore, as the damages and repairs are not known, it is not possible to calculate the recovery timeline. Considerable discontent surfaced among stakeholders about this process, which led to a review of the state law. As a result the law for the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund were changed in 2018. The current law states that they claims are paid based on proof of repair.

As information about the lack of available recovery data surfaced during the interviews, the study aim changed from modelling the 2008 process to providing a proof of concept of a housing recovery and relief simulation model, and collecting information for future modelling work.

14.2.2 Stakeholders

The following positions were interviewed. Information in parenthesis is type of stakeholder and the number of stakeholders involved.

1. Building contractor (private). (1)
2. Engineer damage assessor (private). (1)
3. Engineer in repair design (private). (1)
4. Engineer in demolition management (private). (1)
5. Engineer in insurance loss estimation (governmental). (1)
6. Engineer in Building and Safety Department (municipality). (3)
7. Admin staff in Building and Safety Department (municipality). (1)
8. Housing Relief Team (municipality). (1)
9. Mayor (municipality). (2)
10. Fire Fighter (municipality). (2)

All of the stakeholders are from the south Iceland testbed, except for two. One was from a national agency and the other was from the north Iceland testbed where there is a high earthquake risk. The contribution of the Husavík test bed was to verify that information about recovery and relief timelines would be useful to them, which they confirmed. Knowing that this information would be used to increase the understanding of their partners in the north strengthened the importance of the study for the stakeholders in the south. Therefore, the contribution of the Husavik test-bed partners was significant.

Various other stakeholders are involved in the recovery process who are not included in the current model. For example, the decision to hire extra municipality staff requires a decision and budget from the municipality, making the local government (town council) a stakeholder. Another example is infrastructure services. If people do not have access to their homes, or if utility services are not functioning, then people cannot live in them.

14.2.3 Causal Loop Diagram

A basic Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) for the recovery process is presented in the Figure 65. The CLD consists of two connected balancing loops. The first (B1, blue links) addresses number of buildings damaged and stakeholder activities and reads as follows: An earthquake produces damages to buildings, the bigger the earthquake the more buildings are damaged; Increased number of damaged buildings leads to increased number of insurance claims, leading to increased number of engineer projects, which leads to an increased number of building repair permits, which lead to an increased

requirement of repair crews, which leads to increased number of repaired buildings, which decreases the number of damaged buildings. From this loop the recovery time can be estimated through the insurance process delays, the time it takes to acquire a design engineer, building permit processing delays and the time it takes to get a repair crew, as shown by the pink links.

The second balancing loop (B2, green links) centres around the recovery timeline and municipality budget expenditure, and reads as follows: The longer the recovery, the longer the relief time will be due to households being evacuated from their homes; This leads to additional relief cost and increased budget spending; increased budget spending allows for more staff to be hired, more available staff can be used to reduce the delay of the building permit process, which will reduce the recovery time.

A key aspect of the CLD is the accumulation of delays. Each of the stakeholders has a process to implement their work when approached by a single homeowner whose home has been damaged. Each has a capacity to process such a request in a known average amount of time, i.e., their normal processing rate, including both the delay to start the processing and the processing time. Under normal circumstances there is a balance between the demand of repair and the supply of Design Engineers and Contractors. Meaning that on a normal day, if your home is damaged, you are not likely to acquire these resources instantly, there will be some wait, and it can be estimated. The question herein is how much longer the wait becomes when many of your neighbours are requiring the same services of the same resources at the same time. A queue will develop around the service provider and the homeowners need to wait for their request to be processed. The second key aspect in the CLD is municipality expenditure (relief cost, additional staff) verses their financial gain if the municipality implements a policy to shorten the delays. The question is therefore how to balance between time and expenditure.

Figure 65. Causal Loop Diagram for a Reconstruction and Relief Process

14.2.4 Stock and Flow Diagram

The stock and flow diagram for the repairs created for the SD simulation model is presented in the Figure 66. It represents the timeline for the causal links in the Figure 65 that are in pink and blue. It has five stocks: damaged buildings, claims processed, engineer drawings, permits, and construction. When all damaged buildings have gone through all of the stocks the recovery is complete.

The model was quantified to the level that it could demonstrate how a system dynamics models can be used for understanding the earthquake damage repair system and for policy design and analysis, but does not represent a realistic scenario. The cost model (below) was not completed (representing the green links in the CLD) but was identified as future work. The figures below show key aspects important to such a model.

Figure 66. Stock and Flow Diagram for Earthquake Recovery Simulation

Figure 67. Initial steps of a Stock and Flow Diagram for Relief Cost.

14.3 Model Activation Information-Earthquake Damage Data

14.3.1 Damage Data

The exogenous variable that drives the model (obtained from the first impact procedure previously discussed) is number of buildings damaged in the earthquake. This happens instantly during an earthquake, if progressive damage and aftershocks are not considered. In real life, all building owners do not report information about damaged buildings to insurance companies at once. Data on reporting rate can be collected from insurance companies. Whether detailed information on the reporting rate is relevant will depend on the modelling time step. If the model time step is months, then the importance of acquiring reporting rate is likely to be negligible.

The number of reported damages to residential buildings damages in an Icelandic earthquake can be estimated using Loss Estimation data from Icelandic earthquake data. In the summer of 2000, two significant earthquakes hit the South-Iceland Lowland causing considerable damage. The first earthquake hit the South-Lowland in Iceland at 15:41 local time (GMT) on 17 June 2000, the National Independence Day of Iceland. The second damaging earthquake occurred three and a half days later, on 21 June at 00:47 local time, 17 km west of the first earthquake. The June 17 earthquake had a moment Magnitude $M_w=6.5$, the hypocentre was at 6.3 km depth, and occurred on an 18 km long fault; The June 21 earthquake also had a moment Magnitude $M_w=6.5$, the hypocentre was located at 5.1 km depth, and occurred on a 16 km long fault (Sigbjornsson 2001, Thorarinsson et al. 2001).

Based on recordings from the Iceland Strong Ground Motion Network, maintained by the Earthquake Engineering Research Institute of the University of Iceland in Selfoss, the highest recorded peak ground acceleration recorded on June 17 was 65% g and on June 21 was 84% g (Thorarinsson et al. 2001). The majority of structures experienced below 47% g. Despite the fact that none of the buildings collapsed in the earthquakes, a significant amount of structural and non-structural damage was reported to, and reimbursed by, the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund.

The data driving the model will change with the recovery timeline. The data will become more accurate, from estimations to real data. For example, prior to an earthquake, damages can be based on loss estimation data. Immediately after an earthquake real-time earthquake data can be used to get improved estimated damage data. This data can be updated as the verified damage data comes in. Then, as information about the recovery progress becomes available the recovery parameters can be updated accordingly. Aftershocks can be taken into account.

14.3.2 Damage Ratio

The Damage Ratio (number of damaged buildings/number of total buildings) is likely to be one of the first pieces of data available about the damages, and provides information about the scope of the damage for initial planning. For example, the Damage Ratio is an indication of how many insurance claims there are likely to be and from that an estimate of the percentage of how many subsequent building-permits will need to be processed. Having immediate information allows the Building and Safety Department to estimate its backlog, plan activities, set up a monitoring scheme and call for

extra resources in advance of serious delays. Damage Ratio information from previous earthquakes in Iceland by Bessason et al. is presented in Figure 68.

Figure 68. Damage Ratio information from Bessason et al. 2020. Left: Number of building sustaining a given PGA range. Right: Percentage buildings seeing No Loss (no damages to building), Loss (some damages to building), and Total loss (building destroyed).

14.3.3 Damage Probability Matrices

Due to the fact that rates of claim processing, engineering design completion, permit processing, and construction/repair can vary based on the level of damage, the SD model can produce more accurate results if the data about the number of buildings is broken down by categories in the form of Damage States. Information of how many buildings is in each Damage State is an indication of the temporary housing needs because buildings with minor damage are not likely to be evacuated or lead to temporary housing demands. The Welfare department could use such estimates to estimate their own

workload and plan their activities, set up a monitoring scheme, and call for extra resources in advance of serious delays.

Damage Probability Matrices (DPMs) are available for the Iceland test-beds developed from the 2000, 2008 and joint 2000 and 2008 based on datasets from the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund database. The first DPMs to be produced from the 2000 dataset were produced in the EU FORESIGHT project (Thorvaldsdottir 2016). An example of DPMs in FORESIGHT for Single Family Dwellings for brick, concrete and timber is presented in the Figure 69.

9.0 MATERIAL by PGA (3864 Total buildings)

DPM 9.1: Brick, Single Family Dwellings
429 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	92,5	86,4	41,0
2-slight	0-1	0.5	0,0	2,3	1,6
3-light	1-10	5	6,0	7,0	27,9
4-moderate	10-30	20	1,5	2,0	11,5
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,0	1,3	4,9
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,0	1,0	13,1

DPM 9.2: Concrete, Single Family Dwellings
1914 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	93,8	90,7	43,1
2-slight	0-1	0.5	1,5	2,0	3,4
3-light	1-10	5	3,7	6,6	38,4
4-moderate	10-30	20	0,5	0,7	8,8
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,2	0,0	3,7
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,2	0,1	2,7

DPM 9.3: Wood, Single Family Dwellings
1521 Buildings

Damage States	Damage Factor Range (%)	Central Damage Factor (%)	Frequency of Damage (%)		
			0-10% g	10-20% g	20-47% g
1- none	0	0	93,6	96,4	63,7
2-slight	0-1	0.5	1,1	0,5	6,0
3-light	1-10	5	4,5	2,0	20,7
4-moderate	10-30	20	0,0	0,9	6,0
5-heavy	30-60	45	0,4	0,2	2,0
6-major and destroyed	60-100	80	0,4	0,0	1,6

Figure 69. Example of DPM from EU-FORESIGHT project

Recent work produced by Besson et al. (2020) produced fragility curves based a new vulnerability model for the three building types, presented in the Figure 70, from which DPMs can be extracted.

The following is the definition of the Damage States (DS) used by Bessason et al.

- DS0 – minor, loss less than 1% of replacement value,
- DS1 – slight, loss less than 1-5 % of replacement value,
- DS2 – moderate, loss less than 5-20 % of replacement value,
- DS3 – substantial, loss less than 20-50% of replacement value

Figure 70 . Fragility curves from Bessason et al. (2020)

While the DPMs and Damage ratios are all constructed from the damage data from recent South Iceland earthquakes, the construction and design of buildings are similar in the north and south and the DPMs easily apply to the north of Iceland.

14.4 Model Formulation Information - Stakeholder Interviews

The following information was collected from stakeholders during the TURNkey interviews. It demonstrates the wealth of information that needs to be considered when developing a SD recovery and relief simulation model. This information will be used in future development of the model.

14.4.1 Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund

Source of funding for damage repairs is a fundamental component of earthquake recovery. Natural catastrophe insurance is a statutory insurance policy that compensates for direct damages to insured property caused by volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, landslides, avalanches and floods. This means that all building owners in Iceland pay by law a natural disaster premium towards earthquakes, floods, volcanic eruptions, and avalanches through their fire insurance premiums (which is mandatory). If contents are insured against fire, whether through special contents insurance or composite contents insurance, which includes fire-related compensation and is classified as property insurance, then they are also covered for natural catastrophes. The natural catastrophe insurance amount is the same as the fire insurance (the home owner gets the same value whether their house is damaged in a fire or an earthquake).

The Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund (NTI) (<https://www.nti.is/en/>) is the public institution whose role it is to insure major valuables against natural catastrophes. NTI operates under the auspices of the Ministry of Finance and Economic Affairs and its activities are based on special legislation on the Natural Catastrophe Insurance of Iceland. All real estate and movables are insured by one of the insurance companies in Iceland on behalf of NTI.

The structure of NTI's operations is based on flexibility. The scope of operations varies greatly from year to year as loss events require extensive human resources. Normally, 4-5 full-time employees work at the agency, but when events occur, projects are either outsourced or people are hired for temporary work. As of 2019, NTI has contracts with four engineering companies which will allow NTI to process claims faster. Field loss assessment is in the hands of experts who work on the basis of contract agreements for NTI. The assessors are independent and impartial in their work for NTI and confirm their qualifications for each loss assessment and their independence towards the claimant and NTI, to ensure their impartiality with the loss assessment. According to the agreement, the NTI can hire 25 engineers the first month and addition 35 the second month. Engineers work in teams of two people, therefore NTI hires max 30 teams. NTI has guidelines on how to expand their staff size. An example is provided in the Figure 71 for how the NTI would expand their workforce for an event that had 10,000 claims. Claim process completion time here is 3 years with 60 assessors and 30 assessor teams.

NTI also has procedures for handling claims. The claimants report a claim, and the claims are registered by NTI who sends it to an assessment team. The assessment teams go to the field, assess the building and provide an estimate to the NTI. The NTI compiles a report that includes the intended payment and sends to the claimant, who then has an opportunity to comment on the process and payment. NTI then processes the comments and makes a decision on the payment, and pays the claimant.

Figure 71. Expected timeline for 10,000 damaged buildings. Left X axis: Staff members per month. Right X-axis: Percent claims closed. Y axis: Months. Functions: Móttaka: registration; Matsmenn: Assessor Teams; presenting to building owner and finalizing decision; Greiðsluferlill: Payment process; Hlutfall lokið: Percent claims closed; and Hlutfull tilkynnta: Percent claims reported.

Figure 72. Standard Working Procedures for Natural Catastrophe Fund (NTI). Rows represent work by (from top to bottom): building owner, NTI service personnel, NTI building assessor, NTI director, NTI cashier,

NTI quality assurance personnel). The columns represented by arrows (from left to right) are: Registration, Damage Estimate, Information presented to Building Owner, Decision, Payment, and Paperwork Closure.

There are three types of insured damages relevant to this study:

- Under deductible, and therefore not registered, and no insurance payment.
- Over deductible, non-structural damage, insurance payment, but does not require engineering design or building permit.
- Over deductible, structural damage, requires engineering design or building permit.

Processing time could be days up till years. This depends on whether:

- Assessments are simple and estimates are agreed upon quickly by homeowner and NTI.
- Estimate are disputed by homeowner.
- The assessment process is complicated.
- The homeowner decides to take the case to court.

Completion date could be delayed due to:

- Owners reporting late
- Damages were not known til later

New procedures since 2018

- The Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund will notify the Building and Safety Department of any structural or piping damage (health and safety) as soon as the assessors have sent in the assessment report (i.e., before the claim is settled). This will allow the Department to start their procedures.
- The Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund will pay the owners based on a work plan that has been approved by the Building and Safety Department.

Policies and procedures on how to implement the new law are currently being discussed by the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund staff. A fully functional Recovery and Relief Simulation Model would help stakeholders to understand the impact of possible policies and allow those who work with, or for, the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund to understand how they will be impacted by the new procedures, and in turn can evaluate their own policies and procedures.

14.4.2 Assessment Engineers

Assessment engineers are contracted by the Natural Catastrophe Insurance Fund and trained by them. The process is as follows: homeowners report damages to their insurance company; insurance companies report to NTI; NTI sends the claim to the assessment coordinator; Assessment coordinator

sends out assessment teams to write up a repair estimate and send to the coordinator; the coordinator reviews all estimates and addresses any uncertainties. In 2008, the estimates were sent to the homeowners, however, new rules dictate that the estimates are sent to the NTI, who in turn contacts the home owners. The NTI work with the homeowners until an agreement is reached, a contract is signed, and the claim is paid. People could send in claims for 10 years after the earthquake.

The coordinator will receive a number of claims at the same time. The order of priority will depend on the on the description of damage in the claim. The assessment mission plan is based on the number of claims (most in the beginning) and the number of assessment teams. Key factors in determining priorities are:

- First, assess single buildings. Prioritize structural and pipeline damages (safety & health issues) over cosmetic damage.
- Then area based assessments, e.g., all buildings in the same street.
- New neighbourhoods are addressed last.

The time it takes to complete an estimation depends on, for example:

- Duration until the the assessments starts.
 - Will depend on when the claim was sent.
 - Priority of claim.
- Assessment process of a building, is typically 2-4 weeks. Assessment process depends on the ability to understand the cause of damage, such as,
 - Ease of assessing estimates.
 - Small amount of damage takes a short time.
 - Destroyed buildings takes a short time (example one day).
 - Uncertainties of origin of damage.
 - Was this from actually damages from the 2008 earthquake or the 2000 earthquake?
 - Was this damage due to damage from the 2000 earthquake not being repaired?
 - Cost-benefit of repairs.
 - It is clearly earthquake damage, but is it worth repairing? E.g., slight tilt, no structural damage, very costly to repair.
- Additional delays to finishing a claim can be due to:
 - Reassessment needed due to new damage being uncovered during repair.
 - Disputes over,
 - Engineer claimed amount was not enough.
 - Contractor claimed amount was not enough.

- Court cases.

An rough estimate of how long assessments took due to the 2008 earthquake:

- 70-80% processed before 1 month
- 20% took a few months
- Some damages, e.g. pipeline damage, did not appear until after 1 year, when insects appeared.
- Some took/are taking many years (and some are still on-going) due to court cases disputing claims.

Assessment projects caused delays in normal projects among engineering companies working on assessments. Therefore, the planning of assessment mission also took into account other work of the Engineering firm. The firm always kept a small number of staff members working on normal projects. As priority of the claims decreased, normal work could be given increased priority. To avoid long delays, a general rule was set by the coordinator that a claim should never be with an assessment team longer than 4 weeks (a decision made around 2012-2014, exact date not recalled).

14.4.3 Design Engineers

When structural components of a building are damaged, the repairs must be designed by a chartered engineer. The payment from the NTI is intended to include the cost of the engineer. A customer needs to wait approximately 1.5 months to obtain engineering services. It takes from 0.5 to 3 months to design earthquake repairs. For example, Damage State 1 could be 0.5 month, Damage State 2 could be 1 month, Damage State 3 could be 2 months and Damage State 4 could be 3 months. The engineer provides the owner with a bid. If the bid does not alignment with the assessor's estimate, the homeowner can take the engineering offer to the NTI and request a reevaluation. One reason for the offer being lower than the estimate could be that the owners neglect to show the assessors all the damages. In regards to repairs, drawings should exist, so designing repairs should not take as long as the original design work.

14.4.4 Building and Safety Departments

The Municipality Building Engineer, head of the Building and Safety Department, authorises permits to commence building construction. A building permit requires the names of the contractors responsible for the construction coordination, the names of contractors responsible for construction components, such as piping, electricity, painting, heating, etc., and architectural and engineering drawings for each construction component, created by certified professionals. In recent years, changes have been made on what type of construction requires a permit and what simply needs to be notified to the Building and Safety Department. Future modelling work needs to take into account current regulations.

It usually takes 7-14 days to process a permit request. Sometimes delays occur due to insufficient documentation, and the processing time can take 14 – 30 days. The department can process the applications to the rate that no backlog is hardly ever noted.

Buildings that were demolished were fully monitored by the Building and Safety department. No buildings collapsed during the 2008 earthquake, but about 50 buildings were so badly damaged that they were torn down. The conditions of the foundations were investigated during the demolition process. In all cases, the foundations were found to be inadequate in that the foundation did not reach to a rock foundation.

In addition to processing repair and reconstruction permits, The Building and Safety department staff spent considerable time tending to structural, non-structural, and content damage in municipality buildings. It was estimated that the latter was more a cause of stress than the former.

14.4.5 Demolition Engineers

Engineers are contracted for demolition projects after the decision to demolish a building has been confirmed. The process for demolitions due to the 2008 earthquake was as follows: The municipality hired an engineering company to manage demolition contracts; The engineering company put together a bidding package for each building; the bidding packages are made available to contractors; interested contractors sent in their bids to the engineering company; the engineering company chose a contractor for each building and signed them on; contractor starts demolition; and contractor completes demolition.

A total of 51 buildings were demolished. Of those, 26 were in the the same municipality, which was the maximum number of families that a municipality welfare department needed to deal with. Two of the buildings did not have complete data. The total delay time in months and years are listed in the table below for the 24 buildings, and also shown graphically. The shortest time to complete a demolition is 5.5 months from the earthquake, and the longest was 3.1 years. Note that the demolition process is taking place along side continued damaged assessments and repair for other buildings, placing a demand on engineering and construction companies.

Delays in start time can be due to lack of access to contractors. Delays in demolition occurred due to abest in buildings, archiological findings or expected findings, and anthrax due to rotting animals. Delays could also occur due to a request from the owner. Some of the structures demolished were garages or farm buildings, and therefore low-priority buildings.

#	Total delay (months)	Total delay (years)
1	5,5	0,5
2	6,0	0,5
3	8,5	0,7
4	10,0	0,8
5	10,0	0,8
6	10,0	0,8
7	11,0	0,9
8	12,5	1,0
9	13,5	1,1

19	13,5	1,1
11	14,0	1,2
12	14,0	1,2
13	15,5	1,3
14	16,0	1,3
15	19,5	1,6
16	21,0	1,8
17	22,0	1,8
18	24,0	2,0
19	24,5	2,0
20	26,5	2,2
21	30,0	2,5
22	31,0	2,6
23	35,0	2,9
24	37,5	3,1

Figure 73. Dates of 24 demolitions

Total demolition duration shown in the above graph can be grouped into three delays. First, based on the time it took to confirm that the building was to be demolished (1st delay). Second, the time it took to acquire demolition contractors (2nd delay). Third, completing the demolition (3rd delay). The Figure 74 shows the delays for each building. The earthquake occurred at time 0. The graph shows that the time it takes to demolish the buildings is relatively short, 0,5 - 1 month, except in one case (#13) where it took 10 months.

The graph shows a variation between the time of receiving a confirmation for demolition (1st delay) and allowing a contractor to start the demolition. (2nd delay). When comparing the delays we see that the first and last demolition both took 0.5 months, the first was completed after 5.5 months, the last after 3 years. The graph also shows that not many demolitions were taking place at the same time, 5 at the most.

Figure 74. Demolition dates. 1st delay: Decision to demolish. 2nd delay: Finding a contractor. 3rd delay: Demolish time.

System dynamics modelling seeks break down trends into its components and the understand the effects of single components. Therefore, the data in the Figure 74is reordered in the Figure 75 based on confirmation time (1st delay). Figure 75shows exponential growth in the 1st delay.

Figure 75. Demolition dates order based on length of 1st delay. 1st delay: Decision to demolish. 2nd delay: Finding a contractor. 3rd delay: Demolish time.

14.4.6 Contractor Crews

Based on the interviews it takes on average about 3 months to get a contractor to start building a house. That is likely to be an underestimate. Delays will be based on the number of buildings need to be built in relation to the number of contractor crews available (one contractor company can work on multiple worksites).

Experience has shown that contractors are willing to reprioritize their projects in order to repair homes that have been damaged in an earthquake, at least to the extent to make them habitable, for humanitarian reasons (helping people in need). Contractors thus contribute to the relief process and become decision makers in the recovery and relief process.

14.4.7 Mayors

The mayors were responsible for overall coordination of municipality staff. Specific activities included:

- Meetings with the NTI about sharing information on damaged buildings with the Building and Safety Department.
- Contract with Engineering Company to support owners in reviewing estimates from the Natural Catastrophe Insurance.
- Contract with Engineering Company to manage demolitions.
- Create/confirm standard procedures for building demolition.
- Either provide temporary housing support to families whose homes had been destroyed or needed repairs, or set up a committee to manage such processes (latter done in larger communities).
- Paperwork when owners did not want to rebuild on the plot of land. This needed to be confirmed through documentation to give the municipality the right to give the construction rights to someone else. This was being addressed for at least two years.
- Repayment of real estate taxes.
- Write situation reports for the town council.
- Maintain cost overview and apply for support to the Prime Minister's Office.
 - Fire department personnel.
 - Salary for staff and standing committees.
 - Geologists, engineers and other specialists.
 - Rental for temporary housing.
 - Rental of containers for furniture and belongings during repair and reconstruction.
 - Damage to waste-water systems.
 - Miscellaneous.

Municipality insured losses were covered by:

- Damages to buildings: Natural Catastrophe Insurance agency
- Municipality Building content: Municipality insurance company
-

Lessons learned

- Repair and welfare was monitored at the beginning, but was not at end. Municipalities need to improve processes for monitoring on all aspects of recovery and relief.
- It is very difficult to estimate the workload on staff. New projects arose. Some normal projects became larger than normal. Various normal projects were put aside.

- Extra staff was not hired, but should be hired in future events to help in monitoring processes and help carry the workload.

14.4.8 Municipality Housing Relief Team

One municipality established a Housing Relief Team (HRT) after the 2008 earthquake to assist those who needed to move out of their homes temporarily due to repairs or permanently due to their homes being demolished. The team consisted of the head of the Building and Safety department, head of the Welfare department, and the mayor's secretary.

HRT sought various options for temporary housing, such as talking to hotels and real estate agents, and was also contacted by members of the general public who offered apartments for rent. Some families could initially stay with family members or friends, but that was not a long term solution.

The HRT met once with each family who needed temporary housing to discuss options for solutions to their housing problem, and then maintained contact via phone. However, the HRT was available for meetings, if requested by a family. The HRT monitored the situation and informed the family of any changes. On 20th August 2008 a joint meeting was held with all families who did not yet have a plan for a permanent solution. For example, if the home was to be demolished, did the family want to build on the same plot or somewhere else. If the latter, that would lead to a series of procedures regarding right to build. The HRT developed a number of forms for the homeowners to fill in, in order to guide the course of action and maintain an overview of the process.

The Municipality initially paid for the temporary housing for those who had to find new lodgings due to their homes being demolished, and those who had to leave while their homes were being repaired. The municipality paid 100% of the rent for the first 6 months and then 50% of the rent. After that the owners themselves had to pay 50%, but were often able to stay in the same location. Only very few families needed to relocate while waiting for their new home. A rough estimate that the shortest time was 3 months, and the longest 1-2 years. Real estate taxes were dropped for condemned houses.

14.4.9 Prime Minister's Office

Due to time constraints on D5.2, it was not possible interview The Prime Minister's Office regarding their experience during the 2008 recovery process. However, letters written from mayors to the Prime Minister's Office and a report published on services carried out by a service centre established by the authorities outline key elements. One being that the municipalities requested and were granted financial support from the government.

One important aspect of the municipalities being granted financial support is that it reduces the incentive for municipalities to be well organized and reduce costs. More research is needed to know whether such payments are likely to be paid to the municipalities in future events by the government.

14.5 Results

14.5.1 Simulations

The model was run to calculate the recovery timeline for the repair of 300 buildings. The model was run for two separate cases to demonstrate how it could be used to understand bottlenecks and policy analysis:

- Run1: 1 assessment team (Number of teams at the onset of a large earthquake)
- Run2: 30 assessment teams (Realistic maximum number at the height of an event)

Other variables in the model were chosen randomly by the modeler with the purpose of showing simple results. Modelling time step was one month. Anything under a month will be lost in this model and would require another model with a smaller time step. The Figure 76 highlights where in the model the input, output and calculations are. Note that it goes in the opposite cycle to its associated CLD.

Figure 76. Input rate (red box), backlog stocks (black text), output rate (green box), and results (black box)

14.5.2 Simulation Results

The Figure 77 shows the results in terms of long it will take the NTI to process the claims (who get all the claims in the same month), how long it takes the engineers to design the repairs (they only accept new work on a given rate and have a steady backlog of projects), how long it takes the Building and

Safety Department to process building permits, and how long it takes contractors to repair buildings. In total, the recovery takes approximately 8-9 years, in this fictitious example.

Figure 77. Simulation Results for 300 damaged buildings

The results are a demonstration of how stakeholders can gain an understanding of a recovery processes, it is not necessarily a realistic timeline. The graphs on the left in the Figure 77 are the results when 1 assessment team is active and the graphs on the right are for when there are 30 assessment teams. The results show that 30 teams finish much faster assessing all the buildings than one team does, as expected. The question becomes how the increase in assessment teams affects the other processes. When there is one assessment team, the engineer backlog is steady at 2 projects. When there are 30 teams, the engineer project backlog steadily increases. The building permit processing time seems to be fast relative to the engineering design time. However, the building construction backlog reaches 80 when there is one assessment team, but reaches nearly 200 when there are 30 teams.

These graphs lead to numerous questions on why the relationships are as they are? What would be the affect of changing the productivity rates for other processes than the building assessments? Is it logical that the damage building repair stock declines the same for both cases? Does the model structure need to change? Is the model correct? How do we validate and verify the model?

System Dynamics modelling is a highly iterative process of modellers and stakeholders, where problems and ideas are modelled, results are analysed leading to new questions, leading to new model structures and parametric values, and new runs and results, again to be repeated until the stakeholders feel they have a good understanding of why the model results are the way they are, and that the models provide sufficient information to answer the questions originally posed.

14.5.3 Policy Discussion

A key value of a System Dynamics model is the ability to analyse the effect of a new policy or a change in a policy before implementing it (last step of the modelling process). For example, based on the results of the runs herein, a municipality might decide to try to shorten the recovery timeline by finding ways to attract more contractors to town (and disregarding the lowering of jobs per contractor of local contractors). While the balance of supply and demand of contractors may be the responsibility of the free market, the local government may see benefit in trying to expedite the recovery so that people can get back to productive (tax paying) work sooner and/or fewer people leave the municipality to go elsewhere due to the societal disruption.

Policy analysis includes finding leverage points in the model and determining how to use them. The policy design and analysis should also address how accurate and how precise does the information needs to be to be useful, for example in terms of range, relevancy and uncertainty.

Policies that could be studied in the model are listed below in the order of appearance in the CLD:

- Policy: Expanding processes, shortening timelines:
 - Policy 1: Increasing insurance damage assessment rate.
 - Policy 2: Increasing availability of engineers.
 - Policy 3: Increasing repair permit processing rate.
 - Policy 4: Increasing availability of repair crews.

- Effect: Decreasing cost if timeline decreases
 - Effect 1: Does the relief cost decrease? Is the level of decrease of value
 - Effect 2: Does the overall recovery cost change?
 - Effect 3: What is the ratio between policy cost and effect? Is it worth it? The answers here may not be strictly monetary.

14.6 Future Work

Possible future work based on the study herein is extensive. Future work should focus on building a generic building earthquake-damage recovery and relief simulation model, which can be calibrated on a case-by-case basis. Following are various examples of area of work. This list is not exhaustive.

Structural changes, based on stakeholder interviews and other information

The stakeholders provided significant information about their processes, which needs to be included in future modelling. In some cases the information is a basis for structural changes to the model in terms of additional stocks and new flows between stocks. In addition, future work includes additional data collection.

Parametric values based on stakeholder interviews

Future modelling development work will include developing new parametric values and new variables.

Group modelling

As more information is provided from one stakeholder, more questions arise about the affects that information has on processes of other stakeholders, calling for multiple revisits and follow-up calls with stakeholders. To address this, system dynamicists may choose to develop the models through group-modelling. Group-modelling practices is common practives in SD.

Arrayed model

The model needs to be able to address multiple types of building damage with different values of variables to calculate flow rates. The Stella software has an array feature where a model structure can be duplicated and only change the variables.

Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis is a standard quality check for System Dynamics models before the model is complete. This includes running the model with extreme values.

Goal Setting and Analysis

A System Dynamics model can include features to monitor how far from a goal the system is and features to make changes to the system to make it move towards its goals. By adding such gap analysis features, an understanding may be gained of whether the system is undershooting, overshooting, or oscillating. Future work on the Recovery Simulation Model can include determining where to implement gaps analysis and help stakeholders to identify where they want to place goals in the system and what they should be.

Leverage Points and Loop Dominance

To understand the strengths and weakness of a modelled system, models are analysed for their leverage points and for understanding which feedback loops dominate the system behaviour during different phases of the system activation. Showing stakeholders leverage points and which feedback control the system, can help stakeholders test and design policies and procedures.

Policy Analysis

A number of policies were identified during the course of the project. These were useful in helping to explain to the stakeholders how to apply the model. Additional policies should be designed and tested in future work.

Building back better

Recovery procedures and policies can aim to repair the buildings back to the same building code as before the earthquake or to an improved level. Building back the same means that there are no delays on discussing how to build back better or how to address the additional costs of building back better. The policy of rebuilding to a higher standard is a possible additional policy implementation to add to the policies currently identified herein as part of an adaptive recovery system.

Interface Building

Various software is available to create SD interfaces to give those who do not own SD software access to a model. A well designed interface can also provide information to the its users and is also likely to increase the usability of a SD model.

Additional Models

Through stakeholder interviews, it became apparent that most, if not all, stakeholders experienced a sudden demand surge for their services and a backlog of tasks was created in very short time frame, calling for them to respond. Future work includes creating models for specific stakeholders based on timesteps that suites their needs and helps them understand and improve their own systems.

Infrastructure Modelling

Future work includes creating System Dynamics models for the repair, reconstruction and reuse of roads and how it affects the housing recovery.

Combining System Dynamics Approach and Agent Based Modelling

The TURNkey infrastructure damage models is based on Agent Based Modelling, a sister approach to System Dynamics (both are based on feedback processes, the former from the perspectives of individual agents, the latter on groups). Current research is looking at how the two approaches can be used in combination. Future work based on TURNkey can look at how to combine, or intergrate in some way, Agent Based Modelling and SD for infrastructure recovery work.

Outreach Meeting

A stakeholder meeting/workshop is being planned in Iceland to keep the Iceland test-bed stakeholders on board with the idea of possible future model development. The intent is to show the stakeholders that have contributed to TURNkey the progress that has been made so far and discuss future development. The intent is also to revise the information presented herein, as the stakeholders often presented initial estimates of values that they may change given more time to consider the average values and outlying values.

Developing training material

Before an earthquake, the municipality can use CLDs and SFDs for developing training material and training its staff. The CLD and SFD show which aspects are important to a process and paths

of information flow. Municipality staff can identify the main staff members that affect the flow, see where delays are created, discuss why, and learn about the value of monitoring the recovery and relief process. Different scenarios can be run in the model to form a basis for discussion.

Functional Recovery

Future work should include a focus on study how to place a recovery and relief model within the larger context of Functional Recovery.

14.7 Summary and Conclusions

The SD model developed herein shows how stakeholders can use TURNkey platform output data immediately after an earthquake to estimate the recovery timeline. The model is a proof-of-concept of a SD approach to recovery and relief simulation modelling for improving disaster-related policy and procedure development. This is demonstrated through a SD model that calculates the recovery timeline based on four recovery components: insurance claims, engineering design, building permit process, and repair. The model was run using 300 damaged buildings. The simulation results show how projects come to a stakeholder at different rates due to delays in the processing time of the previous stakeholder. SD models show where information bottlenecks are located in the system, or indeed, if there are bottlenecks.

The value of the study lies also in the interviews with the stakeholders in the Iceland test-bed and the data collected through them, now available for future work. The model proved to be a good tool to illustrate to stakeholders the key aspects of earthquake recovery in terms of building repair and temporary housing support. Stakeholders were curious about the model and highly engaged during meetings in sharing information and ideas how to improve the model, and indeed the process itself. The model, with its Causal Loop Diagrams, Stock and Flow Diagrams, and the simulation results, provided a basis to easily explain to stakeholders what the model was calculating, where they fit into the model, and how information flows between stakeholders. Stakeholders saw how they could use the model to develop procedures – and discussions – on what to share with whom, when, and in what format. Through their active participation, the stakeholders confirmed that a quantitative Relief and Recovery Simulation model is important.

Considerable effort was put into planning and holding meetings with stakeholders. The study identified a gap in coordinated activities among stakeholders, a lack of discussion on planning such activities, and a lack of clarity on who should initiate such collaboration. While each stakeholder is responsible for its own activity, clarification is needed on who is responsible for coordinating a multi-stakeholder, multi-year project for the benefit of homeowners. As the Prime Minister's office ended up paying the bill, that should be the place to start such a discussion. The study also revealed that recovery stakeholders were indeed concerned about the welfare of the homeowners during past earthquakes in Iceland and understood the importance of managing a recovery timeline so that it does not drag on, though this concern may be influenced by the small size of the communities in the test-bed.

Finally, during the evolution of the project, the value of defining different types of SD models proved useful. At first, the study focus was on understanding how to build a model for people see the

feedback embedded in their recovery and relief efforts (Learning model). As the stakeholder captured the idea of systems thinking, they started offering information and data that gave ideas on how to shift the model to better reflect reality (Restructuring model). It became obvious that the next step would be to shift the model to test policies (Analysis model). If disagreements arise regarding how to coordinate efforts, the Coordination model can be applied. Understanding these different model perspectives proved useful to the author in maintaining an overview of the phase changes in the project.

15 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Seismic resilience of Critical Infrastructure Systems (*CISs*) is strategically crucial to the well-being of modern civilized communities under catastrophic earthquakes. However, observations on real-world seismic events have repeatedly revealed that the inadequate resilience of *CISs* due to their inherent physical vulnerabilities.

The goal of this *Task* is to develop an adaptive and inclusive modelling framework for the rapid response-based recovery and resilience of Critical Infrastructure-Community Systems (*CICSs*) exposed to seismic hazards. Overall, *Rapid Response (RR)* can be leveraged by authorities in charge of disaster management, as a new pathway to restore the functionality of earthquake-damaged *CISs*, in an expeditious and cost-effective pattern.

Of particular relevance to the applicability of the modelling framework developed within Task 5.2, is the time dependent status of the *CISs* considered and the time dependent quality and quantity of information relating to such status, which is usually increasing and changing in nature as time elapses from the disruptive event, but can also be affected by secondary events as time progresses, overlapping the immediate response and recovery phases. The application to the Test Beds is central to the modelling and informs it, so that outputs and outcomes are of immediate relevance and benefit to the stakeholders engaged in the TURNkey project. Given the resources within the Test Beds and their configuration, the study focuses on transport networks, specifically, road networks, for what concern the rapid response of physical critical infrastructure to earthquake sequence. The rapid response is also studied, by looking into the evolving perception of a host of different parties, throughout the whole post-shock recovery phases. Based on the studies, the main conclusions can be drawn in the following:

6. The granularity of the proposed *ABM* framework enables the formulation and quantification of *RNs*' resilience measures, which are crucial to the governance policy on seismic risk of modern communities;
7. Seismic resilience of the *RNs* is found to be profoundly influenced by different earthquake scenarios. In particular, the societal resilience of *RNs* could sharply decay and thus pose a significant seismic risk to the entire community, as the magnitude of the earthquake hazards reaches a certain threshold value;
8. A looped interdependence between the post-shock rapid response and the regular repair on damaged bridges has demonstrated to be playing a crucial role to seismic resilience of *RNs*. Moreover, without losses of generality, the case-study outcome shows that post-shock rapid responses can decrease the restoration duration of critical connectivity by up to 96.8%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the well-planned rapid responses can serve as a promising and viable pathway towards the future resilient *RNs*, imperilled by catastrophic earthquakes;
9. Following the *ABM* established, a *Bayesian Network* has been proposed, in order to update damage states of bridges at the component level, and connectivity loss at the system level and applied to the road network in the Luchon valley (TB-2).

10. Two types of post event observations are fed into the BN: accelerometric measures from free-field seismic stations and damage measures from structure-mounted stations. Outputs of the BN consist in the updated damage probabilities of the bridges and in the probability that any two locations of the network are connected. This outcome aims at improving situational awareness immediately after the earthquake occurrence, before taking rapid response actions.
11. Results of the BN application show that prior estimates are almost evenly distributed over several intervals of recovery duration, meaning that the generated damage scenarios are not very informative regarding the temporal extent of the disruption. The observations that are entered in the BN provide an aggravated picture of the situation (e.g., high PGA values recorded, several damaged bridges): therefore, the posterior distribution of the recovery time evolves towards much longer durations than the prior, as expected. The posterior estimates follow a sharper distribution, showing the benefits of accounting for field observations when propagating uncertainties.
12. AHP is a modelling approach that uses expert judgement to make subjective decisions on the relative importance of a hierarchy of criteria and sub-criteria to an overall goal (primary objective). This methodology has been applied to three potential TURNkey FWCR Platform end-user stakeholder groups: a business organisation, a critical infrastructure organisation, a community. The three hypothetical examples do not represent any specific organisation (business or critical infrastructure) or city, as they have been compiled from an amalgamation of data collected by the authors through the first 2 PAR cycles.
13. The models presented in this section will be further tested and refined with specific end-user stakeholders during the 3rd (and final) PAR cycle where the AHP models will be integrated with ANP models to evaluate the benefits, opportunity, costs and risk (BOCR) merits of specific stakeholder organisations or communities using the TURNkey FWCR Platform. This work is currently underway in Tasks 6.5 and 7.3.
14. The System Dynamic Model is used to determine the Behaviour Over Time Graphs for the Community recovery process. It therefore enables the description on the Dynamic Stakeholder Response (DSR), as it affects and is affected by the Physical Resilience models described above;
15. Based on the meetings with stakeholders, this Deliverable identified a gap in coordinated activities among stakeholders, a lack of discussion on planning such activities, and a lack of clarity on who should initiate such collaboration. Such a gap is posing a significant challenge to applicability of rapid response in real-world earthquake events. On the other hand, it also sheds light on how different community sectors shall chart the pathway to plan and deliver rapid responses, before and during catastrophic earthquakes, in a prompt and collective pattern.

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